

Synthetic methanol for shipping decarbonisation

SUMMARY ABOUT THE STATE OF THE ART OF THE TECHNOLOGIES

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The POSEIDON project is working to establish e-methanol as a sustainable marine fuel, addressing both technological and logistical challenges throughout its production and supply value chain. This deliverable, developed as part of Task T2.4 – Libraries of Components and Technologies, provides a comprehensive overview of state-of-the-art technologies for each step of the "e-methanol as e-fuel for vessels" value chain, which was developed and identified under Task T2.1. It includes feedstock supply (hydrogen and CO₂ sourcing), e-methanol synthesis, transportation and distribution, and onboard utilization. The insights from this study will directly support the development of the value chain simulation tool (Task 5.4) and contribute to the techno-economic, environmental, and social impact assessments (Tasks 5.1–5.3) by serving as a technical reference and data source.

Methanol is a readily available and scalable marine fuel that enables ship operators to significantly reduce SO_x, NO_x and particulate matter emissions, while transitioning toward carbon neutrality.

Methanol offers operational advantages, as it remains liquid at ambient conditions, allowing for easy storage and bunkering with existing infrastructure after minimal modifications. Leading shipping companies have already adopted it, and methanol engines, fuel supply systems, and bunkering solutions are commercially available today. Recognized by the IMO's Code of Safety for Ships, methanol provides a regulated and safe alternative to conventional fuels. Available at over 120 ports worldwide, it offers a practical and cost-effective pathway for the maritime sector to decarbonize, making it a strong contender for the future of sustainable shipping.

This report explores the alternative technologies available for each key component of the value chain, evaluating their technical characteristics, operational constraints, advantages and disadvantages, Technology Readiness Level (TRL), commercial maturity, and sustainability considerations. A structured methodology was followed, combining literature reviews, expert insights from project partners, and market analysis to ensure a comprehensive and well-balanced evaluation of both established and emerging technologies. The result is a technology library, designed to be a valuable resource for stakeholders, decision-makers, and researchers involved in e-methanol applications.

By mapping current innovations and identifying potential synergies between technologies, this deliverable supports the advancement of e-methanol as a competitive and viable alternative fuel for maritime transport. It highlights existing gaps and areas for future research while providing a detailed comparative analysis of available technologies. Additionally, it lays the groundwork for value chain simulations and scenario modeling, ensuring that the most effective technological pathways are identified for scaling up e-methanol adoption in the shipping sector.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
ASU	Air Separation Unit
AFC	Alkaline Fuel Cell
AWE	Alkaline Water Electrolysis
AFIR	Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation

ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
AD	Anaerobic Digestion
AnMBR	Anaerobic Membrane Bio-Reactor
ASBR	Anaerobic Sequencing Batch Reactor
AEM	Anion-Exchange Membrane
ATR	Autothermal Reforming
ATRM	Autothermal Reforming of Methanol
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BECCS	Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage
BPP	Bipolar Plates
BWR	Boiling Water Reactor
CAMERE	CArbon dioxide hydrogenation to MEthanol via REverse water-gas shift
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CCES	Carbon Capture and Energy Storage
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCUS	Carbon Capture, Utilization and Sequestration
CMS	Carbon Molecular Sieve
CaL	Carbonate Looping
CL	Catalyst Layer
CLC	Chemical Looping Combustion
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand
CAP	Chilled Ammonia Process
CO-PROX	CO Preferential Oxidation
CO-SMET	CO Selective Methanation
CPU	CO ₂ Purification Unit
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CAES	Compressed Air Energy Storage
CI	Compression Ignition
CfD	Contracts for Differences
CCC	Cryogenic Carbon Capture

D	Deliverable
DFT	Density Functional Theory
DIPA	Di-2-propanolamine
DEA	Diethanolamine
DME	Dimethyl Ether
DAC	Direct Air Capture
DMFC	Direct Methanol Fuel Cell
DWC	Divided-Wall Columns
DSI	Dry Sorbent Injection
ESA	Electric Swing Adsorption
EDI	Electrodeionization
ECA	Emission Control Area
ESS	Energy Storage System
EU ETS	EU Emissions Trading System
EC	European Commission
EGCS	Exhaust Gas Cleaning System
EGR	Exhaust Gas Recirculation
EPS	Extracellular Polymeric Substance
EPS	Extracellular Polysaccharide
FTM	Facilitated-Transport Membrane
GDL	Gas Diffusion Layer
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HFO	Heavy Fuel Oil
HT-PEMFC	High Temperature - Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell
HPWS	High-Pressure Water Scrubbing
HBR	Hybrid Biological Reactor
HRT	Hydraulic Retention Time
ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
IMFC	Indirect Methanol Fuel Cell
IHCaL	Indirectly Heated Carbonate Looping
IGCC	Integrated Gasification Combined Cycle

ICC	International Code Council
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LCOE	Levelized Cost Of Energy
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
LCO	Liquid Organic Carrier
LT-PEMFC	Low Temperature - Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell
LHV	Lower Heating Value
MDO	Marine Diesel Oil
MGO	Marine Gas Oil
MEA	Membrane Electrode Assembly
MAL	Membrane-Assisted CO ₂ Liquefaction
MOF	Metal Organic Framework
MMO	Methane Monooxygenase
MD	Methanol Decomposition
MDS	Methanol Distillation System
MTBE	Methyl Tert-Butyl Ether
MMM	Mixed-Matrix Membrane
MCFC	Molten Carbonate Fuel Cell
MEA	Monoethanolamine
MED	Multi-Effect Distillation
MPI	Multi-Point Injection
MSW	Municipal Solid Waste
NFPA	National Fire Protection Association
MDEA	N-methyldiethanolamine
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
OFMSW	Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste
OSRM	Oxidative Steam Reforming of Methanol
OC	Oxygen Carrier
POX	Partial Oxidation
POM	Partial Oxidation of Methanol
PM	Particulate Matter

PAFC	Phosphoric Acid Fuel Cell
PBI	Polybenzimidazole
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
PIM	Polymer of Intrinsic Microporosity
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
PtF	Power-to-Fuel
PC	Pre-fractionator Column
PSA	Pressure Swing Adsorption
PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane
PEMFC	Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell
PHS	Pumped Hydro Storage
RNG	Renewable Natural Gas
RMFC	Reforming Methanol Fuel Cell
RO	Reverse Osmosis
RWGS	Reverse Water-Gas Shift
SCR	Selective Catalytic Reduction
SOV	Service Operation Vessels
SPI	Single-Point Injection
SOE	Solid Oxide Electrolysis
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
SEWGS	Sorption-Enhanced Water Gas Shift
SI	Spark Ignition
SRM	Steam Reforming of Methanol
SMR	Steam-Methane Reforming
SC-CO ₂	Supercritical Carbon Dioxide
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSA	Temperature Swing Adsorption
TBM	Tert-Butyl Mercaptan
THT	Tetra-Hydro Thiophene
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
TDS	Total Dissolved Solids

TS	Total Solids
UF	Ultrafiltration
UASB	Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket
VSA	Vacuum Swing Adsorption
VFA	Volatile Fatty Acid
VS	Volatile Solids
WtE	Waste-to-Energy
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant
WGS	Water Gas Shift
WFGD	Wet Flue Gas Desulfurization
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

Methanol (CH_3OH , commonly referred to as MeOH) is a vital raw material for both the energy and chemical industries, with a wide range of applications. As depicted in Figure 1, it acts both as a solvent and a reactant in the production of valuable chemicals such as varnishes, paints, formaldehyde, acetic acid, methylamines, and various cleaning products. Furthermore, methanol plays a pivotal role as a precursor for fuels like Dimethyl Ether (DME) and Methyl tert-butyl Ether (MTBE), which can serve as substitutes for Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) or as gasoline additives (Biswal, et al., 2022). Methanol also finds diverse industrial uses in transportation, electricity generation and fuel cells. High-percentage methanol-gasoline blends (e.g. 85% methanol + 15% gasoline, or M85) and pure methanol (M100) have been successfully implemented in countries like Brazil and Sweden. Additionally, methanol shows great potential for use in fuel cells, whether directly or through reformers. Despite its versatility, challenges such as lower energy density, corrosiveness, and lack of lubricating properties currently limit its widespread adoption (Dieterich, et al., 2020).

Figure 1.1. Methanol derivatives for fuel and chemical uses (IRENA and Methanol Institute, 2021).

Methanol can be synthesized from concentrated carbon sources, including biomass, coal, natural gas, by-product streams, and captured carbon dioxide (CO_2) from industrial flue gases or direct air capture. Global methanol production currently stands at around 90 million tons annually, with forecasts suggesting a fivefold increase to 500 million tons by 2050. Fossil-based methods dominate the industry, with 65% of methanol produced through natural gas reforming (grey methanol) and 35% through coal gasification (brown methanol). Renewable or green methanol, derived from waste-based carbon sources or using renewable energy, accounts for only 0.2% of total production due to economic constraints. Transitioning to renewable methanol production is critical for reducing carbon emissions and achieving climate goals (Nemmour, et al., 2023), (IRENA and Methanol Institute,

2021).

Since greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are one of the most pressing environmental challenges of the 21st century, with carbon dioxide (CO₂) being the largest contributor, primarily due to fossil fuel combustion for power generation and transportation, renewable pathways of methanol production are gaining attention (Bellotti, et al., 2017). Methanol synthesis is considered renewable or "green" when (i) the carbon source is derived from waste products, biomass or DAC, (ii) the hydrogen is generated from non-fossil fuel sources and (iii) the energy required for the process comes from renewable sources. Renewable methanol can be produced through either the bio-methanol or e-methanol pathway. Bio-methanol is derived from the gasification of biomass feedstocks (including forestry and agricultural waste, biogas from landfills, sewage, municipal solid waste (MSW) and paper, among others) while e-methanol involves the use of hydrogen (H₂) produced through water electrolysis powered by renewable energy, combined with carbon dioxide (CO₂) captured directly from biogas production plants or flue gases emitted by "hard-to-abate" sectors like power plants, industries (lime, cement etc.), transportation (vehicles, aviation, maritime etc.) (Roode-Gutzmer, et al., 2019), (Nemmour, et al., 2023).

Producing CO₂-based methanol offers both economic and environmental benefits. It helps address climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions while also enabling the production of valuable products with significant economic potential (Azhari, et al., 2022). E-methanol is part of the Power-to-Fuels (PtF) concept, which converts renewable electricity into sustainable fuels. This approach offers a carbon-neutral alternative for sectors that are difficult to electrify, such as shipping, aviation and heavy transport. It also provides a means of storing excess renewable energy, balancing the grid and ensuring energy security. Despite its promise, current e-methanol production remains low, with significant growth anticipated as renewable energy expands and decarbonisation efforts intensify (Nemmour, et al., 2023), (Sollai, et al., 2023).

As a clean-burning fuel with demonstrated carbon-neutral potential, methanol is also poised to play a key role in Europe's energy transition. The EU's "Fit for 55" package includes regulations targeting greenhouse gas (GHG) reductions in the shipping sector. For example, the FuelEU Maritime Proposal mandates a 6% reduction in carbon intensity for vessels over 5000 GT by 2030, with a 75% target by 2050. Other measures, such as the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR) and integrating shipping emissions into the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), aim to reduce shipping's environmental impact while increasing the cost of conventional marine fuels (Methanol Institute, 2023).

Methanol is a well-established fuel in the shipping industry, offering an immediate way to reduce emissions and support the transition to carbon-neutral operations. Engines, fuel supply systems, and bunkering infrastructure for methanol are readily available today, and methanol produced from natural gas (known as "grey" methanol) is cost-competitive with diesel. Ship operators can already achieve significant reductions in sulfur oxides (SO_x), nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and particulate matter (PM) emissions by using grey methanol, while a future switch to "blue" and "green" methanol will provide even greater environmental benefits as these sustainable alternatives become more widely available (Sollai, et al., 2023), (Methanol Institute, 2023).

Methanol stands out as a cost-effective carbon-neutral fuel option for various vessel types, outperforming alternatives like ammonia, liquefied biogas, and hydrogen in terms of total cost of ownership. Dual-fuel engines that support methanol and diesel facilitate adoption for both new builds and retrofits. A notable example is Stena Line's retrofitted 1500-passenger ferry "Stena Germanica," which became the world's first roll-on/roll-off passenger vessel powered by methanol (Verhelst, et

al., 2019). With over 120 ports worldwide supporting methanol bunkering and an annual production capacity of 120 million tons, infrastructure is well-prepared to meet growing demand. By 2050, methanol production is expected to reach 500 million tons annually, with bio-methanol and e-methanol comprising 80% of the total supply (Sollai, et al., 2023), (Methanol Institute, 2023).

The POSEIDON project aims to establish e-methanol as a sustainable marine fuel by demonstrating innovative solutions across its production and supply value chain. To achieve this, the project will test two complementary CO₂ utilization routes: biogenic CO₂ from a biogas plant and industrial process CO₂ from a lime plant. Additionally, a hybrid power-to-e-methanol technology will be developed while the resulting e-fuel will undergo rigorous testing in engine test bed facilities and aboard a pilot vessel at sea. POSEIDON also seeks to establish e-methanol value chains at the ports of Valencia and Thessaloniki, while fostering communities of practice to enhance collaboration and stakeholder awareness. Through a combination of environmental, economic, and social impact assessments, market studies, and business modeling, the project will identify the deployment potential of e-methanol across the EU. Deliverables include an EU deployment roadmap (D6.5 - EU deployment roadmap including local roadmaps), a modeling tool for feasibility assessments (D5.3 - Value chain Modelling tool), and a public guidebook (D7.6 - Project guidebook) with key findings and policy recommendations. These efforts will leverage the expertise of the project's 19 diverse partners.

This deliverable summarizes the work undertaken in Task T2.4, which focuses on "Libraries of Components and Technologies" as part of WP2 (Identification of Value Chain Requirements and Barriers, and Creation of Local Communities of Practice). The objective of this deliverable is to define the requirements, constraints, limitations, boundary conditions, and planned evolution of each technological component within the value chains under investigation, which are already described and presented in deliverable D2.2 about the "Mapping of the 'e-methanol as fuel for vessels' Value Chain. The findings from this work will contribute to subsequent tasks, including Tasks 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3, which focus on the techno-economic, environmental and social impact assessments of WP5 as well as to T5.4 regarding the development of the modeling tool.

In the subsequent sections, each value chain step is analyzed in detail. The analysis presents a comprehensive description of the technologies involved, including their technical characteristics, main operating parameters, comparative strengths and weaknesses, technology readiness levels, and associated environmental and economic impacts. By systematically addressing each component of the value chain, this deliverable provides a comprehensive understanding of the technologies crucial for enabling the adoption of e-methanol as a sustainable shipping fuel.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 IDENTIFICATION OF MAIN TECHNOLOGICAL BRICKS BASED ON THE MAPPING OF THE VALUE CHAIN

The methodology for identifying the main technological bricks within the value chain for "e-methanol as e-fuel for vessels" of the POSEIDON project, was structured to ensure technical feasibility, alignment with project goals and inclusion of state-of-the-art solutions. The value chain consists of four key steps: feedstocks supply, e-methanol synthesis, transport and distribution to ships and end-use onboard ships, as illustrated in Figure 2. These steps were initially outlined by project partners EIFER and Steinbeis and were refined during a collaborative process involving contributions from technical experts and project stakeholders. The detailed process of the value chain development is described in Deliverable 2.2 of "Mapping of the "e-methanol as fuel for vessels" value chain under the task T2.1 "Mapping of the value chain and the key stakeholders".

Figure 2.1. Key steps of the "e-methanol as fuel for shipping" value chain.

The identification and selection of technologies and processes for each value chain step were based on their technical relevance, compatibility with upstream and downstream processes, and ability to fulfill specific roles within the value chain. This was performed while ensuring alignment with the selected materials and feedstocks. In cases where multiple technologies could achieve the same function, all alternatives were comparatively analyzed to provide a comprehensive evaluation of their technical characteristics, operational performance, Technology Readiness Level (TRL), environmental and economic attributes, as well as their advantages and potential trade-offs.

The identification and evaluation of these technological components relied on a comprehensive data collection approach. This process included extensive literature reviews of peer-reviewed journal articles, books, surveys and technical reports, as well as leveraging partner expertise to gain valuable insights into available technologies. Input from project partners played a critical role in ensuring the accuracy and relevance of the findings by sharing targeted literature and datasets tailored to their specific areas of specialization, thereby enhancing the depth of the analysis. ICODOS provided specific technical details on their patented methanol synthesis technology, EIFER contributed expertise on hydrogen production processes and EIFER offered insights into methanol production systems. In certain instances, market analyses were conducted to assess the current state of technology deployment, cost structure and environmental considerations.

2.2 VALUE CHAIN STEPS

As depicted in Figure 2 above, the “e-methanol value chain for vessels” has been divided into four main steps that cover the entire lifecycle of the fuel, from production to utilization onboard ships. The detailed diagrams of the value chain steps, along with their respective technologies and configurations, are presented in the following sections of the deliverable. By avoiding redundancy, this section provides a concise overview of the four main steps while directing attention to the in-depth analysis that follows.

The first step focuses on feedstock supply, which involves sourcing the raw materials necessary for e-methanol production. These include hydrogen, produced via electrolysis, and carbon dioxide, captured either from industrial processes or biogenic sources. The second step centers on e-methanol synthesis in which hydrogen and carbon dioxide are combined through catalytic processes to produce e-methanol. This step includes a range of synthesis pathways, encompassing both established technologies and emerging solutions that vary in efficiency and environmental impact.

The third step of the value chain addresses the transport and distribution of e-methanol from the production plant to ships. This step involves the logistics required to deliver the fuel, including the use of pipelines, storage tanks, trucks and port bunkering systems, ensuring efficient transfer to the final consumers. Finally, the fourth step focuses on the end-use of e-methanol in ships. This step involves adapting ship propulsion systems to utilize e-methanol as a fuel, including the implementation of engines and fuel cells designed for methanol applications. Additionally, it includes identifying suitable ship types for which the use of e-methanol would be the most viable and efficient.

3 FEEDSTOCK AND OTHER RESOURCES

The POSEIDON project aims to demonstrate innovative and cost-effective value chains that utilize both biogenic and industrial process CO₂, along with renewable green hydrogen, to produce and deploy renewable e-methanol, significantly advancing sustainable maritime fuel solutions. The project explores two alternative CO₂ feedstock routes through case studies based on the Global Omnium wastewater treatment plant in Valencia, Spain, and the CaO Hellas lime production plant in Thessaloniki, Greece. The following sections analyze the supply of green hydrogen and captured CO₂ in relation to the latest technologies available for their production. Specifically, detailed information will be presented on ultra-pure water and electricity supply, water electrolysis, CO₂ capture and purification and biogas production and upgrading.

3.1 GREEN HYDROGEN SUPPLY

Hydrogen, a clean energy carrier that emits no greenhouse gases (GHGs) during use, is often associated with GHG emissions during its production. The methods for producing hydrogen include the utilization of both fossil and renewable sources and incorporate processes such as the thermochemical or biochemical conversion of fossil fuels, biomass or algae and water electrolysis. Electrolysis relies on electricity to split water into hydrogen and oxygen, with the electricity source determining whether the hydrogen is classified as renewable. Renewable or Green hydrogen, produced using renewable electricity sources, is emerging as a crucial step in the transition towards a sustainable energy system, offering a versatile energy carrier and feedstock capable of decarbonizing a range of sectors. However, despite its potential, renewable hydrogen currently represents only a small fraction of global hydrogen production, which remains predominantly fossil-fuel-based and carbon-intensive. The growing demand for climate-friendly solutions is expected to drive an increase in renewable hydrogen production, supported by the decreasing costs of renewable electricity and targeted measures aimed at expanding the market and reducing electrolyzer costs (EPRS, 2023).

The POSEIDON project aims to demonstrate innovative and cost-effective value chains that utilize renewable (or green) hydrogen to produce and deploy renewable e-methanol fuel, focusing on hydrogen produced through water electrolysis powered by renewable electricity, as illustrated in the block diagram in Figure 3.1. The following sections analyze the different classification systems for hydrogen production routes and state-of-the-art hydrogen electrolysis technologies currently being developed and used in modern industry. The water supply and water purification procedures as well as the electricity supply value chain steps are also being examined in terms of current advances in high purity water and electricity blends (renewable or not) to supply to the electrolyzers.

Figure 3.1. Value chain for hydrogen production via water electrolysis.

3.1.1 HYDROGEN PRODUCTION ROUTES CLASSIFICATION

Hydrogen fuels can generally be classified into different types based on their "color" designation which is used as an indication of their environmental friendliness. Figure 3.2 illustrates the various methods for producing hydrogen fuels derived from two main sources: (i) fossil fuels and (ii) renewable resources. Each of these methods has its own advantages and disadvantages, which will be discussed in the following sections (Nazir, et al., 2020).

Figure 3.2. Commonly hydrogen production strategies (Le, et al., 2023).

With the depletion of fossil fuels and the intensification of the greenhouse effect, the use of renewable resources is anticipated to dominate the energy mix. One of the most crucial and urgent objectives of the scientific community today is to decarbonize hydrogen production (Vidas & Castro, 2021). As shown in Table 1, each hydrogen color (or hydrogen production technology) is associated with its corresponding CO₂ emissions and varies in the hydrogen production costs, taking into account the necessary equipment, materials and energy required for production. Additionally, each technology results in the production of different by-products, such as oxygen in electrolysis or solid carbon in pyrolysis. As observed, in most cases, CO₂ emissions are high since hydrogen is typically produced from fossil resources. In terms of carbon footprint, green hydrogen appears to be the least polluting fuel and the most promising regarding its ability to address climate change issues and meet global net-zero challenges.

Table 1. Hydrogen colors and their technology, source, cost and CO₂ emissions (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022), (Farhana, et al., 2024), (Incer-Valverde, et al., 2023).

HYDROGEN COLOR	TECHNOLOGY	SOURCE	PRODUCTS	COST (\$/KG_{H2})	DIRECT CO₂ EMISSIONS (KG_{CO2EQ}/KG_{H2})
Brown Hydrogen	Gasification	Natural gas or brown coal (Lignite)	H ₂ + CO ₂	1.3-2.5	High (18-25)
Black Hydrogen	Gasification	Black coal (Bituminous)	H ₂ + CO ₂	1.3-2.5	High (18-25)
Grey Hydrogen	Steam reforming	Natural gas	H ₂ + CO ₂ (CO ₂ released)	0.7-2.3	Medium (7.5-13)
Blue Hydrogen	Steam reforming + CCS	Natural gas	H ₂ + CO ₂ (CO ₂ captured 85%-95%)	1.2-3.2	Low (0.8-4.8)
Turquoise Hydrogen	Pyrolysis	Natural gas	H ₂ + C(s)	1.6-3.4	Low (1.9-4.8)
Pink Hydrogen	Water electrolysis (Nuclear electricity)	Water	H ₂ + O ₂	2.2-7	Minimal (0.3-0.6)
Red Hydrogen	Thermolysis (Nuclear electricity)	Water	H ₂ + O ₂	2.2-2.4	Minimal (0.3-0.6)
Yellow Hydrogen	Thermolysis (Solar renewable electricity)	Water	H ₂ + O ₂	7.9-8.4	Minimal (N/A)
Green Hydrogen	Water electrolysis (Renewable electricity)	Water	H ₂ + O ₂	1.9-8.2	Minimal (0.8-2.8)

Despite hydrogen's potential to help achieve decarbonization goals, inconsistent and inadequate regulatory frameworks, along with a lack of transparent international hydrogen markets, hinder the

development of a robust hydrogen economy. While the color-coding system of categorization shapes public perception, it provides limited insight into the actual CO₂ emissions, technical viability and broader economic, environmental, social and governance impacts of hydrogen production and trade. To scale up sustainable hydrogen projects and promote international trade, it is crucial to harmonize national regulations and support mechanisms. Establishing clear legal definitions and a well-defined taxonomy for hydrogen would provide legal certainty, encouraging collaboration and investment (EPRS, 2023), (ECE, 2022).

The European Commission and Parliament are shifting towards a classification system based on the definitions of renewable and low-carbon hydrogen. Through the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (ECE), the EU established a taxonomy system in 2018 that recently expanded to include hydrogen production methods. UNFC is the first standardized system for classifying environmentally sustainable economic activities and it serves as a transparency tool to guide private investments toward sustainable initiatives, thereby accelerating the transition to a cleaner and more sustainable future. It is a global standard for sustainable resource management, encompassing minerals, petroleum, renewable energy and more. It enables countries to manage their resources holistically, ensuring that environmental, social and economic factors are integrated and viable (UNECE, 2020).

As a principles-based system, UNFC classifies resource projects by using a numerical coding system that is based on three primary criteria: technical feasibility (F), environmental-socio-economic viability (E) and confidence in the estimated parameters (G). As shown in Figure 3.3, these criteria form a three-dimensional classification system, with categories and sub-categories that reflect the project's maturity and viability. The system can be extended to interconnected projects, allowing for a comprehensive view of how different projects, such as hydrogen production and energy generation, align in terms of quantities and timelines. Projects carry metrics such as sources, costs, emissions and supply chain elements, which are tracked over time. The classification reflects the project's level of confidence and uncertainty and the categories combine to form "Classes" that guide project management and decision-making (ECE, 2022).

Figure 3.3. Three dimensional UNFC categories and examples of classes (UNECE, 2020).

3.1.1.1 HYDROGEN PRODUCTION ROUTES FROM FOSSIL SOURCES

Currently, the majority of global hydrogen production relies on fossil fuels (natural gas: 48%, heavy oils and naphtha: 30%, coal: 18%), primarily through two industrial processes: reforming and pyrolysis of hydrocarbons. Hydrocarbon reforming is the process by which fuel is converted into H₂ through reforming techniques. In addition to hydrocarbons, other reactants can be steam (steam reforming), oxygen (partial oxidation) or both (auto-thermal reforming) (Le, et al., 2023).

Steam-methane reforming (SMR) is the most widely used, efficient and mature technology with thermal efficiencies reaching up to 85% while being the dominant method for large-scale hydrogen production. In steam reforming, hydrocarbons such as natural gas, liquefied petroleum gas and other methane-containing gases (through various combinations of light hydrocarbons including ethane, propane, butane, pentane, light or heavy naphtha, bio-methanol or bio-ethanol) react with high-temperature steam, typically between 700°C and 1000°C, in the presence of a catalyst such as nickel. The reactions involved include the steam reforming of methane (CH₄), the water-gas shift reaction and CO₂ reforming generating a mixture of H₂, CO and CO₂ called synthesis gas or syngas. The process typically operates at pressures between 3 and 25 bar and the heat necessary for the reaction is supplied by the combustion of natural gas, resulting in approximately 9 kg of CO₂ emissions per kg of hydrogen produced (Le, et al., 2023).

Despite its efficiency and decades of optimization, reliance of SMR on fossil fuels and its significant CO₂ emissions have spurred growing interest in carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies to mitigate environmental impacts. Hydrogen produced from SMR without CCS is known as "grey hydrogen" while SMR combined with CCS results in the production of "blue" hydrogen, reflecting its reduced carbon footprint (Le, et al., 2023), (Nazir, et al., 2020).

Partial oxidation (POX) is an alternative to steam reforming for hydrogen production, suited both for methane as well as for heavier feedstocks like heavy fuel oil residues and coal. It is typically a non-catalytic reaction where hydrocarbons are partially oxidized with oxygen or sometimes air, at high temperatures (950°C to 1500°C) and pressures (30 to 80 bar), to produce syngas. POX's exothermic nature removes the need for an external energy input. However, the process is capital-intensive due to oxygen recirculation and desulfurization requirements (Nazir, et al., 2020).

Another production method involves using coal as the feedstock in a process known as coal gasification producing hydrogen classified as "black". Although coal gasification operates on a mechanism similar to partial oxidation (POX), it is more costly due to the need for extra handling of unreacted solid feedstock and the production of significant amounts of byproduct ash (Tang, et al., 2023).

The method for producing hydrogen by combining partial oxidation with catalytic steam reforming is known as autothermal reforming (ATR). In ATR, partial exothermic oxidation supplies heat for endothermic steam reforming, thereby boosting hydrogen production. In short, steam and oxygen (or air) are injected into the reformer for simultaneous reforming and oxidation producing a thermodynamically neutral reaction that, compared to POX, can be carried out at low pressure. Compared to steam methane reforming, autothermal reforming offers advantages such as not needing an external heat source, being simpler and having lower investment costs, approximately 25% less than SMR and 50% less than coal gasification (Nazir, et al., 2020).

Hydrocarbon pyrolysis is a thermal decomposition or degradation process used to produce hydrogen and carbon from hydrocarbons in an oxygen-free or anaerobic environment avoiding CO₂ emissions.

Light hydrocarbons (e.g. ethane, methane, propane) decompose at temperatures between 750-900°C, producing hydrogen and elemental carbon. Heavier hydrocarbons require higher temperatures, and involve a two-step process: hydrogasification followed by methane cracking. The use of catalysts, such as nickel (Ni), iron (Fe) or cobalt (Co), can lower the required decomposition temperatures, making the process more energy-efficient. This makes it a more cost-effective method, with capital costs up to 30% lower than those of SMR and partial oxidation (POX) (Le, et al., 2023). In addition to hydrogen, pyrolysis can generate valuable carbon byproducts such as carbon nanotubes, which have applications in various industries (Rojas, et al., 2024).

3.1.1.2 HYDROGEN PRODUCTION ROUTES FROM RENEWABLE SOURCES

Hydrogen produced from renewable sources, involves processes such as the thermochemical and biological conversion of biomass, as well as water splitting techniques using electricity from renewable sources. Regarding thermochemical processes, the most established and widely recognized method for generating hydrogen is biomass gasification. This process involves the controlled application of heat, steam and oxygen to convert biomass into hydrogen and other by-products without combustion (Le, et al., 2023). Biomass is one of the most important sources for hydrogen production and a strong candidate to replace fossil fuels, given its abundance and environmental advantages. As a renewable organic material, biomass encompasses a wide range of sources, including forest and agricultural residues, animal waste and other organic solid waste (Le, et al., 2023), (Nazir, et al., 2020).

During gasification, biomass is heated to produce hydrogen gas along with carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide and water as by-products. The gas stream produced is filtered and inserted into a water-gas-shift reactor in order to produce additional hydrogen from carbon monoxide. Common feedstocks for this process include wood waste and rice husks, but it can also use a variety of other materials such as paper waste, sugarcane residue, wood chips, food waste, sandstone wastewater, palm oil and polyethylene (Tang, et al., 2023).

Another approach for producing hydrogen from biomass is pyrolysis. Essentially, pyrolysis is a modified form of gasification that occurs in the absence of oxygen. Biomass gasification is more challenging than coal gasification. Furthermore, in the absence of oxygen, the gas stream produced contains additional hydrocarbons that need further catalytic reforming to produce a clean syngas stream containing only H₂, CO and CO₂. Subsequently, carbon monoxide is converted into carbon dioxide using steam in a water-gas shift reaction, similar to gasification (Le, et al., 2023).

The primary biological methods of hydrogen production include direct and indirect bio-photolysis, as well as photo- and dark fermentation. These methods are favored owing to their low energy requirements and straightforward operating conditions even though they face limitations such as low production rates and the need for large operational areas. In contrast, thermochemical processes are often considered superior due to their faster kinetics and environmentally friendly nature. Direct and indirect bio-photolysis processes utilize green microalgae or cyanobacteria with hydrogenase or nitrogenase enzymes to split water into hydrogen and oxygen ions. These ions then combine to release hydrogen gas. Another approach, known as photo-fermentative hydrogen production, involves microbes breaking down organic matter using sunlight, although this method faces challenges such as low production rates and poor solar-to-hydrogen efficiency (Le, et al., 2023).

Among the biological methods for hydrogen production, dark fermentation stands out as a key technology. It involves the fermentative conversion of organic substrates, such as crop residues,

livestock waste and food waste by microbes into organic acids and then into bio-hydrogen gas in the absence of light using dark fermentative bacteria. This method has gained significant attention due to its cost-effectiveness and independence from light energy, making it one of the simplest processes for obtaining bio-hydrogen. Although dark fermentation is advantageous for using renewable resources and reducing pollution, it faces challenges such as low efficiency and trace element deficiencies. Adding trace elements like Fe, Zn, Mn, Cu, Co and Ni can improve its performance (Mehmeti, et al., 2018).

Beyond the above techniques, water splitting is one of the most promising approaches, being a cleaner and more environmentally friendly method. Water splitting methods are generally classified into three categories: (i) low-temperature water electrolysis, (ii) high-temperature water electrolysis (or water thermolysis) and (iii) photonic (or photocatalytic) water splitting. One of the key advantages of this technique is its ability to produce hydrogen with more than 99.99 % purity (Le, et al., 2023).

Low-temperature water electrolysis is an environmentally friendly method that incorporates water as a reactant to generate hydrogen and oxygen via water splitting using an electric current. However, it accounts for only 4% of global hydrogen production due to economic challenges related to costly electricity consumption, typically obtained from non-renewable energy sources. There are four main types of water electrolysis each differing in their electrolytes and ion-based agents (i.e. H^+ , OH^- , O_2^-) (Tang, et al., 2023). These technologies will be covered in detail in the upcoming sections.

By integrating electrolyzers with existing nuclear power plants, these plants can supply electricity and heat to the electrolyzers, creating a hybrid energy system. Some countries view nuclear power as a major source of low-carbon electricity and heat. In the future it can also be used to produce “pink” or “yellow” hydrogen using a number of low-carbon processes. This approach not only enhances the viability of nuclear plants by providing an additional revenue stream but also supports the decarbonization of regional industries through the produced hydrogen (ECE, 2022).

With regard to the rest of the water splitting techniques, the thermolysis (or thermochemical) process involves splitting water at high temperatures, around 2500°C, due to its high Gibbs free energy. To enhance sustainability, several thermochemical water-splitting cycles using CuCl or SnO₂-based catalysts have been proposed, utilizing solar flux or nuclear energy. Future research will likely focus on advancements in solar collectors. The cost of hydrogen production through this method is still high and depends on the expense of component materials, corrosion challenges and overall system efficiency (Nazir, et al., 2020).

Finally, photocatalytic water splitting has recently emerged as a promising method for hydrogen production. This process uses a semiconductor photocatalyst, activated by solar light, to generate electron-hole pairs. The holes oxidize methanol, while electrons reduce water to produce hydrogen. For efficiency, the semiconductor must have proper band potentials and a suitable energy band gap. Its morphology, crystallinity, and surface-active sites also impact performance. TiO₂ is widely studied but suffers from fast charge recombination and low solar utilization. To address this, heterostructure photocatalysts (e.g. TiO₂/rGO-Mo₂C) and noble metal nanoparticles (e.g. AuNPs) are used to improve charge separation and hydrogen generation. Despite its promise, photocatalysis has a low solar-to-hydrogen (STH) conversion efficiency (~0.2%). However, research on narrow band gap semiconductors (e.g. g-C₃N₄, MoS₂, CdS, CdSe) aims to enhance efficiency and lower costs (Tang, et al., 2023).

3.1.2 WATER ELECTROLYSIS TECHNOLOGIES

Water electrolysis is a method that operates by using an electric current to split water (H₂O) to produce high-purity hydrogen (up to 99.9999%) and release oxygen as a byproduct, as shown in the following reaction (Vidas & Castro, 2021):

Water electrolysis technologies have been continuously developed and utilized in industrial applications since the 18th century. Its progress during its evolution led to the development of four primary types of electrolysis techniques that can be categorized based on the electrolytes or ionic agents used and operating parameters into: Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolysis, Alkaline Water Electrolysis (AWE), Anion-Exchange Membrane (AEM) electrolysis and Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOEC) (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022). All of the aforementioned technologies share a common design principle: electrolysis takes place inside a cell which consists of an anode and a cathode, separated by a diaphragm, a membrane or an electrolyte solution that work as the media responsible for transporting the generated chemical charges (anions (-) or cations (+)) from one electrode to the other. These cells are encased by a bipolar plate and a current distributor. The cells are arranged in a zero-gap electrolysis stack where multiple cells are connected in series (Thyssenkrupp, 2024).

In brief, proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers operate in an acidic environment, which necessitates the use of costly materials but delivers superior performance and the ability to produce pressurized hydrogen. The half-reactions for PEMs are:

In contrast, alkaline water electrolyzers (AWE) and anion-exchange membrane (AEM) electrolyzers both function in a liquid alkaline electrolyte solution, typically KOH or NaOH. The relevant half-reactions are as follows:

Finally, solid oxide electrolyzers function at high temperatures, which thermally activates the migration of oxide ions and facilitates the reactions at the electrodes, thereby reducing overpotentials. The half-reactions for SOE are (Rojas, et al., 2024):

3.1.2.1 PROTON EXCHANGE MEMBRANE (PEM) WATER ELECTROLYSIS

The fundamental components of a proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzer include the anode, cathode and the proton exchange membrane itself, which separates these two electrodes. During electrolysis, water is introduced into the anode chamber, where it undergoes oxidation, resulting in the production of oxygen gas and positively charged hydrogen ions (H⁺) as shown in Figure 3.4. These protons then pass through the PEM to reach the cathode, while the electrons

generated from the reaction travel through an external circuit. At the cathode, these electrons combine with hydrogen ions and water to produce hydrogen gas and negatively charged hydroxide ions (OH^-). The PEM is crucial as it selectively allows only protons to pass through while blocking electrons and gas molecules, thereby preventing gas crossover and ensuring the separation and high purity of the produced gases (Tang, et al., 2023).

Figure 3.4. Schematic view of proton exchange membrane (PEM) water electrolyzer working principle (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022).

The conventional anode and cathode catalysts used in PEM electrolyzers are iridium oxide (IrO_2) and platinum (Pt). The most typically used membrane is the Nafion membrane (a sulfonated polymer membrane), a solid electrolyte that facilitates the conduction of hydrogen ions (H^+) between the electrodes. PEM electrolyzers operate at high current densities typically ranging from 1 to 2 A/cm^2 and at temperatures between 50 to 80°C, with the optimal temperature depending on the specific catalysts and membrane materials used. The pressure of hydrogen and oxygen gases, which ranges from 1 to 30 bar, is also crucial for the efficiency and performance of the electrolyzer. Proper humidification is essential for proton exchange membrane's performance, necessitating a humidification system to maintain the required moisture levels (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022), (El-Shafie, 2023), (Tang, et al., 2023).

PEM electrolyzers offer significant advantages, such as the ability to handle load fluctuations effectively due to their quick response time and the ability to produce extremely high-purity hydrogen and oxygen gases, with purity levels reaching up to 99.9999 %. This high level of efficiency (55-80%) is partly due to the faster kinetics which are accelerated by the acidic nature of the electrolyte and the high reactivity of the metallic electrode surfaces compared to alkaline electrolysis (Tang, et al., 2023).

In addition to its efficiency, PEM water electrolysis is considered safer than its alkaline counterpart, as it eliminates the use of caustic electrolytes and requires a smaller system footprint. Additionally, they offer operational flexibility, allowing them to function safely at atmospheric pressure on the anode side while maintaining higher pressures on the cathode side. These advantages have led to

significant global interest in the commercial development of large-scale PEM electrolyzers, with several manufacturers now producing systems up to the megawatt (MW) scale for industrial and transportation applications. The stability of PEM water electrolyzers is another noteworthy feature, with reported operational lifespans of up to 50000 hours with minimal performance degradation. The target for future developments aims to extend this stability to 100000 hours (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022), (El-Shafie, 2023).

The widespread adoption of PEM water electrolysis is hindered by the high cost of its components, particularly the electrode materials (noble metals), current collectors and bipolar plates. Reducing capital costs remains a significant challenge for broader implementation of this technology. Other significant challenges involve scaling up for large-scale applications, such as those required for megawatt (MW) systems which involves addressing issues related to system design, cost and longevity. Therefore, comprehensive analysis and validation of large-scale PEM electrolyzer units are essential to ensure their effectiveness and reliability over extended operational periods (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022), (El-Shafie, 2023).

3.1.2.2 ALKALINE WATER ELECTROLYSIS (AWE)

Alkaline water electrolysis (AWE) is a reliable, safe and mature technology widely used for industrial hydrogen production, with capabilities reaching the multi-megawatt scale. Since 1789, when Troostwijk and Diemann introduced the concept of alkaline water electrolysis, significant advancements have been achieved. The first large-scale industrial alkaline water electrolyzer plant, with a capacity of 10000 Nm³H₂/h, began operation in 1939. By the early 20th century, over 400 industrial alkaline electrolyzer units have been successfully installed and utilized for various industrial applications (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022). AWE is relatively simple to manufacture and involves immersing two electrodes in a water solution containing 20 to 40% of either sodium hydroxide (NaOH) or potassium hydroxide (KOH). The electrolyte solution generates the necessary alkalinity by circulating across both electrodes. The electrodes that are used are noble metal-free and typically made of nickel (Ni) and cobalt (Co) oxides for the anode and cathode materials, respectively and are separated by a porous diaphragm made of ceramic oxide materials like asbestos or polymers within the electrolyte solution (El-Shafie, 2023), (Tang, et al., 2023).

Figure 3.5. Schematic view of alkaline water electrolyzer (AWE) working principle (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022).

As shown in Figure 3.5, in these systems, hydroxyl ions (OH^-) serve as the ionic charge carriers, moving through the porous diaphragm structure to facilitate the electrochemical reactions necessary for hydrogen and oxygen production (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022). Hydrogen and hydroxide ions are produced at the cathode, while oxygen is generated at the anode through the reaction of hydroxide ions (El-Shafie, 2023). The diaphragm allows hydroxide ions (OH^-) and water molecules to pass across while effectively separate the produced hydrogen (H_2) and oxygen (O_2) gases. This separation is vital for maintaining the purity and safety of the hydrogen, with typical purity levels ranging from 99.5% to 99.9%. Through catalytic gas purification processes, this purity can be increased to as high as 99.9998% (Tang, et al., 2023).

Alkaline water electrolyzers typically operate at moderate temperatures ranging from 70 to 90°C, with a conversion efficiency of 50-80% and an operating cell voltage between 1.8 and 2.4 V (El-Shafie, 2023). The performance of an AWE is influenced by the material type and thickness of the diaphragm, anode and cathode. While the temperature of the electrolyte does not greatly influence hydrogen production, it can help minimize energy consumption in the system. In contrast, the efficiency of hydrogen production is more strongly dependent on the concentration of the electrolyte solution. A key distinction between AWE and PEM electrolysis is the type of electrolyte used. AWE uses a highly corrosive liquid electrolyte while PEM uses a compact polymer membrane as its electrolyte. This difference significantly impacts the operational characteristics and suitability of each method for various applications (Tang, et al., 2023).

Alkaline water electrolysis is particularly favourable for large-scale applications due to the long system lifespan of approximately 80000 hours and its relatively low investment cost (CAPEX), with values ranging from approximately EUR 1180 per kW for smaller plants (<1 MW) to around EUR 700 per kW for larger plants (>40 MW). Operational expenditures (OPEX) are typically around 7% of the total cost for medium-sized plants, but advancements in technology and increased system lifespans are expected to reduce this to approximately 2% by 2030 (Vidas & Castro, 2021), (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022).

However, AWE has some limitations. It generally operates at lower current densities (0.1–0.5 A/cm²) due to the moderate mobility of hydroxyl ions (OH⁻) and the use of corrosive KOH electrolytes leading to reduced energy efficiency. This makes AWE more suited for applications with an almost constant power supply, such as when connected to the grid. Despite these drawbacks, some high-powered AWE systems have demonstrated a dynamic response fast enough to align with the output of renewable energy sources (Vidas & Castro, 2021), (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022). Additionally, the KOH electrolyte is highly sensitive to ambient CO₂, which can lead to the formation of potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃) salts. These salts reduce the number of available hydroxyl ions, lower ionic conductivity and clog the pores of the anode's gas diffusion layer, thereby decreasing the efficiency of ion transfer through the diaphragm and reducing overall hydrogen production. Another significant drawback is the production of lower-purity gases due to the inability of the diaphragm to completely prevent gas crossover between the half-cells. This limitation can affect the quality and purity of the hydrogen produced, making it less suitable for applications requiring ultra-high-purity hydrogen (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022).

3.1.2.3 SOLID OXIDE ELECTROLYSIS (SOE)

The development of solid oxide water electrolyzer (SOE) technology began in the 1970s in the United States, led by General Electric and Brookhaven National Laboratory and later continued by Dornier in Germany. The technology is still in development and although it hasn't been commercialized yet, several companies are working to bring it to market focusing on the development of pilot and demonstration plants. SOEs typically operate with water in the form of steam at high temperatures ranging from 700 to 850°C and ambient pressure (1 atm), which significantly reduces the power required to split water into hydrogen and oxygen, thereby increasing energy efficiency. The high temperature allows for the utilization of inexpensive thermal energy or waste heat, leading to a substantial reduction in hydrogen production costs, as power consumption is the primary contributor to these costs in electrolysis (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022).

In SOE systems, the process begins at the cathode, where water molecules from the inlet steam are reduced to hydrogen (H₂) and oxide ions (O²⁻) through the addition of two electrons. As shown in Figure 3.6, hydrogen is released from the cathode surface, while the oxide anions (O²⁻) generated at the cathode then migrate through the ion exchange membrane (solid electrolyte) to the anode. There, the oxide ions are further reduced to generate oxygen (O₂) and electrons. The produced oxygen is released from the anode and the electrons are conducted through an external circuit back to the cathode, driven by the positive attraction of the cathode. The components of SOEs include noble metal-free ceramic anodes and electrolyte membranes, with cathodes typically made from yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) and anodes made of La_{1-x}Sr_xMnO₃ (LMS). Despite these materials being effective, further research is needed to develop superior catalysts and electrode materials (Tang, et al., 2023), (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022).

Figure 3.6. Schematic view of solid oxide electrolyzer (SOE) working principle (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022).

SOE technology offers key advantages over existing electrolysis methods since it can produce pure and dry hydrogen from steam without the need for costly downstream processes for gas separation and compression (Vidas & Castro, 2021). Furthermore, its high operating temperature results in favorable thermodynamics and reaction kinetics, enabling unmatched conversion efficiencies up to 90%. Solid oxide electrolyzers are particularly advantageous in areas lacking electricity infrastructure, as they can reduce transportation and storage costs by generating hydrogen on-site. Moreover, SOEs can be easily integrated with downstream chemical synthesis processes, such as the production of methanol, dimethyl ether and ammonia. Additionally, solid oxide electrolyzers do not require the use of noble metal electrocatalysts, further enhancing their conversion efficiency (Tang, et al., 2023), (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022).

SOE cells can generate over 20% more hydrogen than AWE and PEM electrolysis with the same electrical power input, making them an attractive option in situations where thermal energy is available and reducing energy consumption and operational costs is crucial. Furthermore, SOE cell's ability to perform carbon dioxide electrolysis positions it as a promising solution for producing syngas-based products like synthetic fuels and supporting carbon recycling initiatives (Thyssenkrupp, 2024).

However, despite the advantages of solid oxide electrolysis in hydrogen production, challenges such as limited electrical efficiency, due to poor electrode kinetics and electronic leakage, as well as instability and degradation of the electrodes have hindered its commercialization on a large scale. Currently, the reported stability of SOECs is only 20000 hours when using yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) thin electrodes. It is currently more suitable for coupling with stable power sources like nuclear or combined cycle power plants, rather than intermittent renewable sources (Vidas & Castro, 2021), (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022). Challenges in the commercialization of SOEs also remain due to the high investment and operating costs associated with the technology as it requires very high operating temperatures. The capital costs of solid oxide electrolysis systems are reaching values of up to 2200 EUR/kW_{el}, but experts anticipate significant cost reductions by 2030, potentially reaching as low as

EUR 750/kW_{el} with an increased production scale. Addressing these challenges requires careful management of energy resources, optimized water usage and significant investments in infrastructure, particularly in regions with limited electricity access (Tang, et al., 2023).

3.1.2.4 ANION EXCHANGE MEMBRANE (AEM) WATER ELECTROLYSIS

Anion exchange membrane (AEM) electrolysis technology represents the latest advancement in this field. Focusing on electrochemical hydrogen production, AEM electrolyzers combine the benefits of both AWE and PEM technologies (El-Shafie, 2023). The AEM electrolyzer utilizes a basic electrolyte (water solution with low concentrations of KOH) and an anion exchange membrane to decompose water (H₂O) into hydrogen (H₂) and oxygen (O₂) gases. In this system, the anode and cathode are separated by an anion exchange membrane that permits the passage of negatively charged hydroxide ions (OH⁻) while blocking other ions and gases. During electrolysis water is introduced into the anode chamber, where it undergoes oxidation to produce oxygen gas and hydroxide ions. The typical operating temperature range is 40-60°C and the operating pressure is below 35 bar. As shown in Figure 3.7, these hydroxide ions then travel through the AEM to the cathode compartment, where they combine with incoming electrons and protons to produce hydrogen gas (Tang, et al., 2023).

Figure 3.7. Schematic view of Anion Exchange Membrane (AEM) water electrolysis working principle (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022).

Typically, anion exchange membranes are made from a polymer backbone such as polysulfone (PSF) or polystyrene cross-linked with divinylbenzene (DVB), combined with anion exchange functional groups like quaternary ammonium salts. Key attributes of an effective AEM include high mechanical, thermal and chemical stability, as well as good ionic conductivity and barrier properties. The polymer backbone ensures mechanical and thermal stability, while the functional groups influence ionic conductivity and chemical stability (Vincent & Bessarabov, 2018).

One advantage of AEM cells is their potential to use non-noble metal catalysts, which can reduce hydrogen production costs (El-Shafie, 2023). Compared with proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers, AEM electrolyzers operate at higher pH levels and lower pressures. This setup can lower system costs and complexity but requires materials capable of withstanding the highly basic environment. Instead of using a 20 to 40% NaOH or KOH solution, AEM electrolyzers employ a low-

concentration alkaline solution. Additionally, AEM electrolyzer cathodes are typically made from nickel (Ni) and nickel–iron (Ni–Fe) components, while the anodes are constructed from nickel foams or titanium components (Tang, et al., 2023).

Despite these advantages, the performance of AEM systems remains suboptimal due to challenges such as poor catalyst activity and the balance between mechanical stability and ionic conductivity. Excessive ion exchange groups can enhance conductivity but may reduce mechanical strength due to increased water uptake. This can lead to chemical instability and decreased ionic conductivity due to hydroxide attack. Additionally, the degradation of quaternary ammonium groups through nucleophilic substitution and Hoffmann elimination reactions can further compromise the membrane's performance (El-Shafie, 2023), (Vincent & Bessarabov, 2018).

AEM electrolyzers are still in the research and development (R&D) phase and are less advanced than alkaline and PEM technologies. While AEM technology offers benefits like lower overall costs and stable hydrogen production, significant development is required before it can be implemented for large-scale hydrogen production. Thus, AEM water electrolysis needs further research, particularly in improving membrane materials, reducing cell costs and enhancing overall efficiency (El-Shafie, 2023). Recent advancements include the use of alkaline polyelectrolyte membranes. Discussions on the development of these membranes, including their ionic conductivity, stability and degradation characteristics, are based on density functional theory (DFT) calculations and other research findings. Although the field is progressing rapidly, there is a need for improved in-situ techniques, standardized evaluation protocols for AEM water electrolysis conditions, and innovative catalyst designs (Vincent & Bessarabov, 2018).

3.1.2.5 COMPARATIVE CHART FOR WATER ELECTROLYSIS TECHNOLOGIES

Table 2. Comparative chart for water electrolysis technologies (Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022), (Chaudhary, et al., 2024).

WATER ELECTROLYSIS PROCESS	TRL	ENERGY CONSUMPTION	MAIN FEATURES & ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES & LIMITATIONS	PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY
Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolysis (PEM)	9 Commercial	4.5-7.3 kWh/Nm ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commercialized technology. Operates at higher current densities. High purity of the gases. Compact system design. Quick response/start time. High efficiency. Low operational cost. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High cost of the cell components. Noble metal electrocatalysts. Generations of intermediates. Difficulties in scaling-up. 	55%-80%
Alkaline Water Electrolysis (AWE)	9 Commercial	4.5-7.5 kWh/Nm ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Well established - mature technology. Commercialized for industrial applications. Noble metal-free electrocatalysts. Relatively low capital cost. Long-term stability and durability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited current densities. Crossover of the gasses. Corrosive - high concentrated (5M KOH) liquid electrolytes used. Slow start. Long response time. 	50%-78%

WATER ELECTROLYSIS PROCESS	TRL	ENERGY CONSUMPTION	MAIN FEATURES & ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES & LIMITATIONS	PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY
Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOEC)	7 Demonstration	> 3.7 kWh/Nm ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Noble metal-free electrocatalysts. • High working temperature which results in favorable reaction kinetics. • High efficiency. • High current density. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited stability and delamination of electrodes due to degrading materials used. • Safety problems. • High capital and operation costs. • Underdeveloped technology. 	>90%
Anion Exchange Membrane Electrolysis (AEM)	4 R&D	4.8-5.2 kWh/Nm ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Noble metal-free electrocatalysts. • Low concentrated (1M KOH) liquid electrolytes used. • Non-corrosive reaction medium. • Fast start. • Low operational costs. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Simple design. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited catalyst stability. • Difficulty in balancing mechanical stability and ionic conductivity of the membrane. • Underdeveloped method. 	57%-59%

3.1.3 HYDROGEN STORAGE TECHNOLOGIES

Hydrogen (H₂) storage systems, are included in the hydrogen supply value chain of the POSEIDON project, as not mandatory elements *applied depending on the case study). They might be however as critical as hydrogen production and a brief overview of available storage technologies, along with their comparative advantages and constraints is essential for a comprehensive understanding of hydrogen supply as a feedstock. Hydrogen, after being synthesized and prepared using various methods, can be stored in two primary forms: gas and liquid. Over the past two decades, numerous techniques for hydrogen storage have been investigated. The main storage methods fall into two categories: physical storage, which includes compression and liquefaction, and material-based storage, which involves chemical and physical absorption using liquid organic carriers (LOCs) and solid-state materials such as metal hydrides, ammonia borane, carbohydrates, carbon-based materials, zeolites, glass microspheres and Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs). These methods are illustrated in Figure 3.8 (Tang, et al., 2023), (Le, et al., 2023).

Figure 3.8. Schematic illustration of hydrogen storage technologies (Tang, et al., 2023).

For transportation, compressed hydrogen gas is stored in specially designed tanks made from materials like steel with carbon coatings or lightweight composites. The most common storage method involves compressing hydrogen to pressures exceeding 300 bars. Cryo-compressed gas is an alternative approach that combines low temperatures and high pressures to enhance the volumetric energy density of the storage systems. Advancements in technology have also enabled underground hydrogen storage in deep geological formations, such as salt mines, solid rock caves, and depleted oil and gas fields. This method preserves hydrogen equilibrium despite weather variations and climate fluctuations, making it suitable for large-scale storage (Le, et al., 2023).

High-pressure compressed hydrogen storage is a well-established and efficient method and is

currently the most widely used storage technology. It offers high rates of hydrogen filling and release without requiring additional energy for release. This method is valued for its simplicity, low cost, rapid charge and discharge cycles across a wide temperature range, and minimal energy requirements. However, compressing hydrogen to higher pressures results in a significant energy loss of 13-18% of its heating value, impacting operational costs. To mitigate this, cylindrical containers are preferred over spherical ones, and lightweight, durable materials that are resistant to hydrogen diffusion and embrittlement are utilized. Despite these advancements, several challenges remain. Compressed hydrogen is volatile, increasing the risk of leaks and explosions. Material weakening, premature degradation of mechanical properties and cracking can compromise the integrity of the storage cylinder. Additionally, although compression requires less energy than liquefaction, storing hydrogen as a compressed gas demands significantly more space, making it less practical for some applications (Vidas & Castro, 2021), (Tang, et al., 2023).

Liquid hydrogen (H_2) offers a significantly higher volumetric energy density compared to its gaseous or cryogenic forms. At -253°C , liquid hydrogen achieves a density of approximately 71 g/L and an energy density of 8 MJ/L. To maintain this liquid state, hydrogen must be cooled below its critical melting point of -240°C in specialized containers, facilitating transportation over long distances, including intercontinental routes. Despite its advantages, liquid H_2 storage is costly and energy-intensive due to the substantial power required for liquefaction and pre-cooling, which can result in a loss of 30-40% of the net hydrogen heating value. Furthermore, the boil-off phenomenon, caused by evaporation as external heat increases the tank's internal temperature, leads to daily hydrogen losses of 1.5-3% (Tang, et al., 2023), (Le, et al., 2023).

To mitigate these issues, multilayer insulation (commonly referred to as vacuum super insulation) is employed. This insulation comprises alternating layers of metal foil and padding material to minimize heat ingress. Additionally, large spherical tanks with capacities reaching thousands of cubic meters are often used in stationary facilities to reduce evaporation losses. For transportation, horizontal tubular tanks are preferred for road travel, while spherical tanks are favored for maritime transport, such as on ships carrying liquefied petroleum gas. Although cryogenic hydrogen tanks are lighter than pressurized tanks, their insulated storage systems are complex and present maintenance challenges (Tang, et al., 2023), (Le, et al., 2023).

Alternative material-based hydrogen (H_2) storage techniques, such as chemical storage methods, provide safer and more efficient solutions compared to traditional physical storage. Among these, metal hydrides, liquid organic hydrogen carriers, clathrate hydrates and ammonia-based systems have gained significant attention for their potential to enhance hydrogen storage and delivery. Metal hydrides store hydrogen in solid form by chemically bonding it to metals, offering high volumetric efficiency and safety even under extreme conditions (Vidas & Castro, 2021). Liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs), also known as liquid organic hydrides, chemically bind hydrogen to organic molecules and release it through dehydrogenation for use in power generation or transport. This closed-loop process ensures minimal carbon emissions by rehydrogenating the dehydrogenated carriers off-site before returning them to fuel stations (Tang, et al., 2023).

Ammonia, a well-established hydrogen storage medium, boasts a high hydrogen density and flexible applications in both stationary and mobile systems. Unlike other storage methods, ammonia does not require high pressures, making it suitable for large-scale hydrogen storage. However, the process of releasing hydrogen from ammonia is energy-intensive, limiting its efficiency. Meanwhile, methanol presents an alternative with a higher energy density than ammonia but a lower hydrogen content by weight and volume, adding another option to the suite of chemical storage technologies.

Table 3 summarizes the major advantages and disadvantages of the leading hydrogen storage technologies described so far (Vidas & Castro, 2021).

Table 3. Summary of technical characteristics, advantages and disadvantages of current hydrogen storage methods (Vidas & Castro, 2021).

Storage Technology	Compression	Liquefaction	Chemical
Basic Properties			
Storage temperature (°C)	~25	<-252.90	~25
Storage pressure (bar)	690	1	9.90
Density (kg/m ³)	39	70.80	600
Hydrogen Content			
Gravimetric (wt%)	100	100	17.80
Volumetric (kg-H ₂ /m ³)	39	70.80	106.80
Energy Density (LHV)			
Gravimetric (MJ/kg)	120	120	18.60
Volumetric (MJ/L)	4.50	8.49	12.70
Transfer Mechanism			
Discharge method	Pressure release	Evaporation	Catalytic decomposition (T = 400 °C)
Extraction energy (kJ/mol-H ₂)	-	0.91	30.60
Miscellaneous			
Advantages	Ambient temperature operation; low cost; rapid (dis-)charge cycles at wide range of temperatures; simple operation	Ambient pressure operation; lighter cheaper storage tanks	Safer and smaller storage; ambient temperature and pressure operation; non-reactive
Disadvantages	Very high pressures needed; large and heavy storage tanks required; gas volatility; premature degradation of tanks	High energy consumption; very low temperatures needed; severe insulation requirements	Emerging technology, high cost; high temperature requirements

3.1.4 WATER SUPPLY AND WATER PURIFICATION TECHNOLOGIES

Green hydrogen production relies on the use of various types of water including raw water, pure water for electrolysis (resulting from the purification of raw water) and cooling water for the rest of the electrolysis system (if applicable). Each has distinct requirements in terms of both quantity and quality with pure (or demineralized) water being the most critical for electrolyzer efficiency containing very low levels of dissolved ions (i.e. low salinity) (Madsen, 2022).

The quality of pure water used can vary based on factors such as the type of electrolyzer, electrode materials and system design. Although water quality standards may vary, maintaining very low conductivity is a key requirement for proper electrolyzer operation as impurities can disrupt the electrolysis process by forming deposits on electrode surfaces or within membranes. This can lead to increased operational costs due to corrosion and reduced efficiency through irreversible damage. For alkaline electrolyzers, water conductivity should be below 1 µS/cm, while PEM electrolyzers require even higher purity, with conductivity levels reaching below 0.1 µS/cm. The American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) established a high-purity water classification system, as outlined

in Table 4, based on which ASTM Type I or Type II water is applicable for most electrolysis processes, although in some cases systems can tolerate water with a slightly higher conductivity of up to 5 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, which corresponds to Type IV pure water (Madsen, 2022), (Simoes, et al., 2021).

Table 4. ASTM Standard specification for reagent water (ARUP, 2022).

PARAMETERS	UNIT	TYPE I	TYPE II	TYPE III	TYPE IV
Electrical conductivity	$\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at 298 K	0.056	1.0	0.25	5
Electrical resistivity	$\text{M}\Omega\text{-cm}$ at 298 K	18	1.0	4.0	0.2
pH	pH at 298 K	-	-	-	5.0-8.0
Total Organic Carbon (TOC), max	$\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$	50	50	200	No limit
Sodium, max	$\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$	1	5	10	50
Chlorides, max	$\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$	1	5	10	50
Total silica, max	$\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$	3	3	500	No limit

Water used in hydrogen production is generally obtained by treating a raw water source. Common water sources include surface water from lakes, streams, rivers, creeks or dams, groundwater from wells and aquifers, recycled or treated urban or industrial wastewater, cooling tower water, rainwater, public grid water, brackish water from saline surfaces and highly saline water like seawater or estuary water. Regardless of the location, a water purification system is required. Even valuable drinking water must be treated as high-purity water before the electrolysis process (ARUP, 2022). Key water contaminants of concern for industrial systems include the following:

- Algae and organic matter (potential biological fouling).
- Dissolved solids like sulfate and chlorides (corrosive).
- Minerals such as calcium, magnesium and high alkalinity contaminants (can cause scaling).
- High silica levels (may cause amorphous silica scale).
- Metal solids like iron and manganese (can oxidize to insoluble forms and precipitate in cooling systems).
- Macro-organisms like clams and mussels (can cause blockages and equipment damage).

Different water sources are often classified by their conductivity, a key parameter in hydrogen production, with total dissolved solids (TDS) used as an indicator to represent water quality. This classification helps to determine the most suitable and sustainable water source for specific hydrogen production methods based on treatment needs and efficiency. Figure 3.9 outlines typical ranges of TDS and conductivity for various water sources as well as the treatment steps necessary for achieving standard and high purity drinking water quality (ARUP, 2022).

	High Purity Water	Fresh Water	Brackish/ Saline Water	Highly Saline	Hyper Saline	
Conductivity (uS/cm)	0.056	5	~1700	~15000	~53000	70,000+
TDS (mg/L)	0.03	2.5	800	10,000	35,000	50,000+
	Demin. water	Rain Water Drinking Water Recycled Water (Various Classes) Domestic Wastewater Surface Water Greywater Groundwater		Estuary		Seawater
Treatment steps to achieve drinking water quality		Screening Clarification Filtration Reverse Osmosis (One Pass)	Screening Clarification Filtration Reverse Osmosis (One Pass)	Screening Clarification Filtration Reverse Osmosis (Two Passes)	Screening Clarification Filtration Reverse Osmosis (Two Passes)	
Treatment steps to achieve high purity water from drinking water	Electro-deionisation	Electrodeionisation	Electrodeionisation	Electrodeionisation	Electrodeionisation	Electrodeionisation

Figure 3.9. Water sources and typical TDS ranges (ARUP, 2022).

Not all contaminants affect all water sources equally. For example, algae are a concern in surface water and seawater but not in groundwater. The selection of contaminants for treatment is determined by the specific risks associated with each water type. The treatment process for each raw water source, to ensure the necessary water quality for hydrogen production, can be divided into three main steps (ARUP, 2022):

- Pre-treatment: This stage focuses on removing large debris and reducing suspended solids from raw water sources. The processes available include screening, chemical flocculation and clarification and filtration.
 - Screening is used to remove large debris and protect equipment. Typical opening sizes in the screens range from 1.5 to 6 mm.
 - Chemical flocculation and clarification help reduce turbidity, color and organic matter by adding coagulants like iron or aluminum salts. These bind to impurities, forming larger particles (flocs) that can be removed. Fine screening, coagulation-flocculation, and filtration show minimal water losses and consume around 0.5-0.15 Wh/m³ and 0.05 kWh/m³, respectively.
 - Filtration eliminates remaining suspended solids, often using media such as sand or anthracite coal.
- Primary treatment: In this step, the focus is on reducing total dissolved solids (TDS). Multiple techniques can be employed based on the type of water and the required purity levels. Ultrafiltration (UF) is a common method used, incorporating membranes to more efficiently remove smaller particles and reduce TDS. Ultrafiltration is more compact and requires less maintenance, producing less waste and operating at lower costs compared to traditional methods. Ultrafiltration requires around 0.025-0.1 kWh/m³ of energy.

- Final polishing: This final step further reduces total dissolved solids, especially when a higher degree of purity is required, as is often the case for hydrogen production. Reverse osmosis (RO) is commonly used to achieve high purity. RO utilizes a semi-permeable membrane to remove ions, unwanted molecules and larger particles. By applying pressure, the system forces water through the membrane, leaving contaminants behind and achieving demineralized water quality. Despite RO's efficiency, recovering up to 50% of feedwater demands significant amount of energy, ranging between 3-6 kWh/m³ while necessitating significant infrastructure investments, making them unsuitable for small-scale or remote applications. After RO, electrodeionization (EDI) can be applied, a water purification technology that combines electrochemical ion transport with ion exchange by incorporating conductive ion exchange resin, to produce highly pure water, primarily from low-dissolved solids feeds like the reverse osmosis permeate. The process effectively depletes ions in the diluate compartments while concentrating them in the adjacent compartments, facilitating the removal of contaminants and the production of ultrapure water. Although EDI reduces energy consumption compared to traditional methods, it may still demand significant energy input, especially when treating feedwater with higher salt concentrations (Alkhadra, et al., 2022).

Assuming that the stringent purity standards of ASTM Type II demineralized water, suitable for green hydrogen production are met, the following treatment process trains were suggested in the literature. As shown in Table 5, for surface water, the treatment process begins with coarse screening to remove large debris, followed by clarification through chemical treatment with lime, carbon dioxide and sodium hypochlorite to adjust pH and facilitate softening. Coagulants and flocculants are introduced, allowing the water to undergo clarification. The clarified water is then filtered through a Dissolved Air Flotation (DAF) system, with options for further purification through reverse osmosis (RO) and Electrodeionization (EDI) for demineralized water. Waste products, including sludge and brine, are managed carefully, with brine reused for filter backwashing, thereby reducing operational costs and environmental impact. In contrast, groundwater treatment omits the initial screening step and follows a similar chemical treatment route, leading to sediment clarification and filtration. On the other hand, recycled water treatment focuses on converting free chlorine or ammonia into chloramine to minimize biofouling in the ultrafiltration membranes. This treated water is then subjected to two passes of RO, with intermediate polishing by EDI to ensure high-quality demineralized water. Brackish water undergoes a comparable treatment regime, utilizing sulfuric acid for pH adjustment and a media filter before RO processing. High salinity and seawater treatment mirrors the brackish process but draws cooling water only after the second RO pass (ARUP, 2022).

Table 5. Pretreatment technologies for each raw water source (ARUP, 2022), (Simoes, et al., 2021).

	SURFACE WATER (TDS<800)	GROUND WATER (TDS<800)	RECYCLED WATER (TDS<800)	BRACKISH WATER (800<TDS <10000)	HIGH SALINITY WATER (10000<TDS <35000)
Target contaminants	Algae, suspended solids, silica, metals, BOD.	Silica, calcium, dissolved solids, magnesium, metals.	Silica, metals, suspended solids, organics.	Silica, chlorides, calcium, metals, potential algal content.	Silica, chlorides, calcium, metals, potential algal content.
Nominated technologies for pretreatment	Coarse screen Lamella clarifier DAFF RO EDI	Conventional clarifier (for softening) Media filter RO EDI	Chloramination UF Dechlorination RO (Double pass) EDI	Coarse screen Media Filter RO (double pass) EDI	Coarse screen Media Filter RO (double pass) EDI

Based on the above, the most preferred source is advanced recycled water, specifically Class A water treated with reverse osmosis (RO), as it requires the least processing. This is followed by surface water and groundwater with low salinity (TDS below 800 mg/L), which also have relatively low treatment requirements. Class A water without additional RO treatment, brackish water and seawater, which requires the most intensive treatment, round out the list of potential sources (ARUP, 2022).

On average, approximately 9 kg of ultrapure water is required to produce 1 kg of hydrogen, although actual water consumption can vary depending on the type of electrolyzer used, as mentioned above. Electrolyzers differ in technological performance, which leads to variations in water consumption. Manufacturer specifications report water usage ranging from 10.01 to 22.40 liters per kg of hydrogen (Simoes, et al., 2021). Understanding the overall impact of green hydrogen systems on local water resources requires considering both ultrapure and raw water needs (44% and 56% respectively). As shown in Figure 3.10 below, different raw water sources require varying treatment systems and thus have different recovery rates. Groundwater can achieve high recovery rates of over 98%, treated wastewater around 90-95%, and seawater around 40-50% due to the complexities of desalination (Madsen, 2022).

Green hydrogen

Volume requirements for alternative water sources
 River: 17.2 L
 Groundwater: 17.2 L
 Seawater: 28.6 L

Figure 3.10. Schematic of process-specific water withdrawal and consumption in liters of typical green hydrogen technology to generate 1 kilogram of hydrogen (IRENA and Bluerisk, 2023).

While the use of water in clean hydrogen production has sparked debate, these discussions often lack a deep understanding of the still-emerging technologies involved. As Europe transitions its hydrogen production, water demand is projected to rise significantly by 2040, adding pressure to water-stressed regions. Green hydrogen could present an opportunity to reduce rather than exacerbate water stress. Water supply systems for hydrogen production could be expanded to serve other water users, such as providing clean drinking water and sanitation, while achieving economies of scale and minimizing additional costs. However, comprehensive data on water use in large-scale hydrogen production are lacking, particularly for processes like cooling, which are critical for commercial-scale operations. Early identification of water-related challenges can help developers pivot to more viable projects (IRENA and Bluerisk, 2023).

3.1.5 ELECTRICITY SUPPLY

Electricity is essential throughout the POSEIDON value chain, with various generation technologies offering distinct benefits and drawbacks. Coal has long been a base-load power generator but ranks

poorly on environmental assessments, as it is the largest CO₂ emitter and requires substantial water and land resources. Despite these drawbacks, coal remains vital for affordable energy in developing nations. Natural gas is favored for its affordability, lower emissions compared to coal and operational flexibility, especially in the U.S. However, geopolitical tensions, such as those during the Russia-Ukraine conflict, can threaten access. Although it emits about half the CO₂ of coal, natural gas is not carbon-free. Nuclear energy offers a cleaner alternative but often faces high initial capital costs. Renewables like wind, solar, and hydroelectric power, on the other hand, generate emission-free electricity and are becoming more financially competitive although they typically require significant land and are often intermittent, making them unreliable as the sole energy source. Emerging solutions and advances in large-scale energy storage can enhance efficiency and address the variability of renewable energy (Vella, 2024).

The EU's electricity mix is becoming increasingly sustainable, with renewables more than doubling since 2004 and projected to grow further under the European Green Deal, aiming for climate neutrality by 2050. This initiative seeks to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent, to benefit citizens and businesses. Renewables lower greenhouse gas emissions, reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and foster growth in green technologies, creating job opportunities (EUROSTAT, 2024). At the EU level, renewable energy is now the largest source of power generation, followed by fossil fuels and nuclear energy. As depicted in Figure 3.11, in 2022, the EU generated 2641 TWh of electricity, with nearly 40% coming from renewables, 38.7% from fossil fuels and over 20% from nuclear power (EC, 2024).

Figure 3.11. Net electricity generation in the EU by fuel type in 2022 (EC, 2024).

Following this, in 2023, the EU achieved a record drop in coal, gas and CO₂ emissions, leading to the cleanest electricity mix to date. The shift away from fossil fuels has accelerated, with fossil fuel generation decreasing by 19%, accounting for less than one-third of the electricity mix. Renewables rose to a record 44%, driven by wind and solar power, which produced 27% of EU electricity and saw their largest capacity addition. Wind power surpassed gas generation for the first time, marking

a significant milestone. Coal generation fell to its lowest level ever and the decline is expected to continue as many coal plants face closure in 2024. Gas generation also dropped for the fourth consecutive year, reflecting a long-term decline as coal phases out. Alongside this clean growth, electricity demand fell by 3.4% compared to 2022, but this trend may not continue as demand is projected to rise due to increased electrification (Brown & Jones, 2024).

As global electricity demand rises, a diverse energy mix becomes crucial for ensuring reliability and minimizing environmental impact. While natural gas effectively complements renewables, regions rich in coal may still rely on coal-fired plants for stable base-load generation (Vella, 2024). As shown in Figure 3.12, the electricity mix varies widely across EU member states, with renewable energy contributing from over 90% to less than 15% of total electricity generation. These differences are influenced by factors such as geographical conditions, availability of natural resources (like coal or gas), the economic structure of each country and political decisions, such as whether to invest in nuclear energy. As depicted below, thirteen EU countries generate some of their electricity from nuclear power, with shares ranging from 3% in the Netherlands to over 60% in France and Slovakia (EC, 2024).

Figure 3.12. Share of renewables, fossil fuels and nuclear in electricity generation in each of the 27 EU countries (EC, 2024).

The 2021-2023 energy crisis revealed the strong correlation between gas and electricity prices. Surging gas prices due to the Ukraine invasion led to rising inflation, soaring energy bills, increased energy poverty and job losses, highlighting flaws in the current electricity market design. The crisis revealed a lack of long-term contracts, including those covering shorter timeframes like 1-3 years ahead. This led to unexpected windfall profits and prompted measures to reclaim excess revenues. However, these actions came at the cost of higher expenses for consumers. A clear example is in

the renewable energy sector, where some countries designed support schemes as market premiums without mechanisms to recover surplus revenues. Europe had a critical opportunity to redesign its electricity market following the increased consumer expenses and calls for market reform aimed at fairer pricing and enhanced consumer protection. The primary goals of the electricity market reform are to address concerns from consumers, industries and investors about exposure to fluctuating short-term prices (Zachmann, et al., 2023), (Fabra, 2023).

The European Commission aims to stabilize electricity prices through four key proposed strategies: (a) preserve short-term electricity markets to support efficient, flexible energy distribution across member states and manage renewable variability, (b) promote long-term contracts like Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs) and Contracts for Differences (CfDs) to encourage investments since short-term markets alone cannot sustain investment in renewable energy and electrification, (c) allow retail price regulation during emergencies and crises to protect consumers and shield electricity costs from gas price surges and (d) require fixed-price contracts from retailers to minimize bill volatility. Properly designed contracts can coexist with short-term markets, offering revenue stability without distorting grid operations. The EC proposal aims to boost market liquidity through virtual trading hubs, facilitating decarbonization while promoting price stability in the evolving energy landscape (Fabra, 2023).

As shown in Figure 3.13, Contracts for Differences (CfDs) are financial agreements between producers and retailers or industrial entities, providing payments if electricity prices fall below a predetermined strike price. Under a CfD, electricity generators sell power in the open market and settle the difference between the "strike price" (a predetermined rate) and the "reference price" (market price) based on a specified "reference quantity". The strike price can be regulator-set or determined through competitive auctions, with pre-investment auctions typically setting the strike price to reflect the average cost of the highest-priced accepted unit. CfDs, often lasting 20-30 years, are seen as an attractive policy tool, especially during high electricity price periods, as they generate public revenue (Zachmann, et al., 2023).

Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), in contrast, are long-term contracts between electricity producers and consumers that secure pre-negotiated prices for 5-20 years. While PPAs allow large energy consumers to manage energy needs independently, smaller companies often face higher costs and less transparency due to limited bargaining power. CfD auctions, however, could provide a more scalable and equitable solution, supporting renewable investments while ensuring cost benefits for all consumers equally (Zachmann, et al., 2023).

Figure 3.13. Mechanisms for long-term contracting (Fabra, 2023).

3.1.5.1 ELECTRICITY STORAGE USING BATTERY TECHNOLOGIES

As analyzed in the previous section, the future of energy generation is set to lean heavily on sustainable sources, with wind, solar and hydro becoming primary power sources due to their technological maturity and rapid deployment. The integration of these renewables into electric grids, however, presents challenges because of their intermittent and variable output. To maintain stability, modern power grids must rely increasingly on Energy Storage Systems (ESSs), which help balance generation and consumption (Farivar, et al., 2023). EESs address this need by enabling grids to store excess energy when supply surpasses demand and release it during shortages, supporting the power grid during high-demand hours and mitigating the effects of renewable energy variability. As grids shift to more decentralized and renewable-dependent models, advanced, affordable and sustainable EESs will be essential for realizing the full potential of smart grid concepts, allowing reliable and balanced power management. Various EES technologies have been developed to meet the different demands of modern power systems. These technologies can be broadly categorized into mechanical, thermal, electrical, electrochemical and chemical storage systems (Medina, et al., 2014).

Mechanical storage systems include Pumped Hydro Storage (PHS) and Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES). PHS is the most established mechanical storage technology, accounting for over 90% of global grid energy storage capacity. Using either elevated dams or underground caverns, PHS stores potential energy in water, which is later converted to electricity by releasing the water to drive turbines. CAES functions similarly to PHS by using pressurized air to store potential energy, typically in underground caverns. This stored energy is released to drive turbines when needed. Thermal storage includes Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) systems that store heat, often in molten salts, generated by solar radiation. This heat is then used to power steam turbines, similar to conventional thermal power plants, allowing for power generation even when sunlight is unavailable (Farivar, et al., 2023), (McIlwaine, et al., 2021).

Electrical storage includes Supercapacitors and Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage (SMES) which are high-power-density technologies used for applications that require rapid charge and discharge. However, their low energy density limits their widespread grid applications and SMES

systems remain expensive due to their need for extreme cooling. Another option is electrochemical storage through Batteries. Batteries represent one of the most versatile and rapidly expanding EES technologies, crucial not only for grid storage but also for applications in the automotive sector. Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) stand out for their ability to balance grid loads and provide backup power, making them a linchpin for renewable energy integration (Farivar, et al., 2023), (Medina, et al., 2014).

BESS include a variety of chemistries like lead-acid, lithium-ion, sodium-ion and solid-state, each with unique properties tailored to different sectors, from consumer electronics to electric vehicles. Among these, lithium-ion batteries have become the dominant choice for renewable energy storage due to their high energy density, long lifespan, and cost-effectiveness, making them essential for consistent power delivery (McIlwaine, et al., 2021). Battery performance is shaped by factors like round-trip efficiency, lifespan cost, and environmental impact. Lead-acid batteries, while affordable, suffer from lower energy density and shorter cycle life, limiting their suitability for intensive applications. Lithium-ion batteries, in contrast, offer higher energy density and a longer lifespan, though at a higher initial cost. They now approach energy densities near 304 Wh/kg and 700 Wh/L, nearing their theoretical limits. These characteristics make them well-suited for both grid-scale storage and electric vehicles, although challenges remain in acquiring resources and managing heat effectively (Schmidt-Rohr, 2018).

BESS technologies provide both economic and technical benefits. By leveraging off-peak power, BESS can lower electricity costs, stabilize market prices and reduce peak generation requirements. They encourage investment in renewable energy, minimize congestion costs and support efficient resource use. High-power systems provide essential high-quality energy delivery during demand spikes or outages. From a technical point of view, batteries enable energy time-shifting, peak shaving and load balancing, which optimize grid functionality and support renewable integration. They offer instant power responses, facilitating rapid stabilization and black-start capabilities while reducing transmission congestion. The portability of BESS allows for flexible deployment, deferring expensive infrastructure upgrades and improving service reliability (Medina, et al., 2014).

Despite declining costs, the economic feasibility of BESS depends on factors such as storage duration, capacity and round-trip efficiency. Short-duration batteries offer lower installation costs per MW but incur higher costs per MWh, making them suitable for applications requiring short bursts of high power. In contrast, long-duration batteries, which sustain energy release over extended periods, offer more competitive pricing per energy unit stored. Lithium-ion batteries, for instance, have seen their levelized cost of energy (LCOE) drop from \$300/MWh to \$187/MWh, highlighting their potential as storage solutions. However, these economic advantages are tempered by challenges associated with raw material sourcing, environmental impacts of mining and waste disposal. To address these, advancements in solid-state and cobalt-free batteries aim to improve energy density, extend battery lifespan and reduce dependency on rare materials, which will be crucial as renewable energy use expands and BESS continues to enable a resilient, low-carbon energy infrastructure (McIlwaine, et al., 2021), (Schmidt-Rohr, 2018).

At last, chemical storage can be implemented through hydrogen production and storage by generating hydrogen via electrolysis during low-demand periods. Hydrogen can later be converted back into electricity through fuel cells or gas turbines, offering a high-energy-capacity storage solution suitable for seasonal or long-term energy needs. This makes chemical storage technologies, particularly hydrogen, vital for achieving near-total energy sustainability (Farivar, et al., 2023), (Medina, et al., 2014).

3.2 CO₂ SUPPLY

3.2.1 CO₂ SOURCES FOR CARBON CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES

The presence of CO₂ in the environment comes, among other sources, from various human activities with the primary sources being the combustion of fossil fuels used for energy production in power plants, transportation and various industrial processes (Adam & Ozarisoy, 2023). Power plants that burn coal, oil and natural gas to produce electricity are the largest contributors to CO₂ emissions. In 2020, CO₂ emissions from the electricity and heat production sector accounted for 36.6% of global CO₂ emissions, according to the Joint Research Centre (JRC) - European Commission's science and knowledge service. Industrial processes also significantly contribute to CO₂ emissions, accounting for about 21.8% in 2020. This mainly includes cement and lime production, where CO₂ is released from the calcination of limestone (CaCO₃) to produce lime (CaO), steel manufacturing, where emissions occur during the reduction of iron ore in blast furnaces and various chemical industries where CO₂ is a by-product of chemical reactions, particularly in the production of ammonia and hydrogen through methane steam reforming (Dziejarski, et al., 2023), (Crippa, et al., 2021).

An additional major contributor to CO₂ emissions, particularly in urban areas, is road transportation, which includes cars, trucks and buses. Other modes of transportation, such as aviation, shipping and railways, also contribute to CO₂ emissions, albeit to a lesser extent. In 2020, the transportation sector, including road and non-road transport, contributed approximately 20.1% to global CO₂ emissions, according to estimates by the JRC. Residential and commercial activities, such as heating and electricity consumption using fossil fuels, also play a significant role, accounting for about 9.4% of total CO₂ emissions in 2020. Deforestation and land use changes, which involve the removal of trees that act as carbon sinks and alterations in soil management practices, also play a significant role. Moreover, livestock farming and rice paddies produce methane which can oxidize to CO₂, indirectly impacting CO₂ levels. Furthermore, the decomposition of organic waste also generates CO₂ (aerobic digestion) or methane and CO₂ (anaerobic digestion) (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

Carbon capture, utilization and sequestration (CCUS) technologies have been identified as important tools for achieving decarbonization goals, particularly in sectors that are difficult to electrify or decarbonize. Point source emissions from power plants and industrial facilities, as analyzed above, are two primary sources of CO₂ utilized in carbon capture technologies. CCUS technologies function by capturing CO₂ emissions and transforming them into useful commodities, such as fuels, chemicals and energy products or sequestering them within geological structures or other designated sites (Nagireddi, et al., 2023), (Zhao & Itakura, 2023). Contrary to carbon capture technologies aiming in separating CO₂ from large point sources before atmospheric emission, Direct Air Capture (DAC) technologies aim to extract CO₂ directly from ambient air with the prominent advantage that it has the potential to address emissions from both point and distributed sources since it is not location-specific (Sanz-Pérez, et al., 2016).

Another important source of CO₂ is biogenic CO₂ (bio-CO₂), a climate-friendly carbon source originating from biomass decomposition, digestion, or combustion. Bio-CO₂ holds immense potential for enhancing the circularity and climate benefits of biogas. Unlike fossil-based CO₂, bio-CO₂ is part of the natural short carbon cycle, where released CO₂ is reabsorbed by new biomass through photosynthesis. It is considered one of the most cost-effective paths to achieve "negative emissions", aiming to induce a net reduction of atmospheric CO₂ through the combined effects of photosynthesis

and CO₂ capture (FAO, 2024), (Fridahl & Lehtveer, 2018).

The following sections analyze the main state-of-the-art CO₂ capture technologies applicable to point-source or atmospheric CO₂ capture. This analysis includes an in-depth presentation of each technology’s primary design and operational characteristics, along with a comparative assessment of their technical, economic and environmental advantages and disadvantages, as well as their technological readiness level. It also provides a comprehensive view of the available alternatives for CO₂ purification technologies, as CO₂ cleaning methods depend on the specific impurity requirements for methanol synthesis catalysts and are applicable to both biogenic and industrial CO₂ streams.

3.2.2 CARBON CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES

3.2.2.1 CATEGORIZATION OF CO₂ CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES BASED ON CO₂ FORMATION STAGE

Carbon capture technologies are categorized into post-combustion, pre-combustion and oxy-fuel combustion capture, based on the stage of CO₂ formation in a CO₂ emitting system. As shown in Figure 3.14, post-combustion capture removes CO₂ directly from exhaust (flue) gas streams of power plants and industrial operations, after combustion. This process typically involves solvent-based carbon capture implementing chemical solvents, like amine-based solutions, to absorb CO₂ from the flue gas. The CO₂-rich solvent is then regenerated to produce a concentrated CO₂ stream for storage or utilization. Post-combustion technologies are the most mature and widely used, with over 20 large-scale projects globally. However, these technologies face challenges such as high energy demands for capture and regeneration, which can reduce the overall efficiency and increase costs. Additionally, the use of chemical solvents can have environmental impacts, including the discharge of hazardous substances and the generation of waste byproducts (Nagireddi, et al., 2023).

Figure 3.14. Flowchart illustration of the three different CO₂ capture technologies based on CO₂ formation stage (Adam & Ozariso, 2023).

Pre-combustion CO₂ capture involves extracting CO₂ from fossil fuels before the combustion process. This technique is commonly used in gasification, where feedstock is partially combusted with steam and air at high temperatures and pressures to produce synthesis gas (syngas), composed of hydrogen, carbon monoxide and other gases. The syngas undergoes a water-gas shift reaction increasing the CO₂ concentration, which can then be captured and recovered by physical or chemical absorption-based techniques and later conditioned and compressed for storage or utilization. The remaining hydrogen-rich gas can be used as fuel in boilers or gas turbines in an Integrated Gasification Combined Cycle (IGCC) system to generate electricity (Nagireddi, et al., 2023), (Dziejarski, et al., 2023). This method is promising for industries like steel, chemicals and refining, which use large amounts of hydrogen and produce significant CO₂ emissions. One advantage of pre-combustion capture is its relatively high efficiency and lower energy penalty compared to post-combustion capture. However, although pre-combustion capture can achieve high CO₂ capture efficiency (up to 80%), its implementation faces challenges such as the need for high-purity feedstocks, technical complexity and is costly due to the gas synthesis process and the high capital investments needed. Ongoing research aims to improve efficiency, reduce costs and address technical challenges, including alternative technologies like membrane-based separation and adsorption-based capture (Nagireddi, et al., 2023), (Adam & Ozariso, 2023).

Oxy-fuel combustion technology involves burning fuel in a mixture of high-purity oxygen and recycled flue gas instead of air. This process produces flue gas that is primarily composed of CO₂ and water vapor, from which CO₂ can be easily captured for storage or utilization (Nagireddi, et al., 2023). This method offers several advantages, including reduced NO_x emissions, due to the use of recycled flue gas, reduced flue gas volume, improved boiler energy conversion efficiency and the potential for direct CO₂ sequestration. Furthermore, the resulting flue gases can reach CO₂ concentrations of 80-98%, facilitating CO₂ capture and reducing recovery costs (Dziejarski, et al., 2023). Oxy-fuel combustion also offers a low-efficiency penalty of 4%, compared to 8-12% for post-combustion capture and it is generally considered as the most promising technology for achieving near-zero CO₂ emissions in power generation (Adam & Ozariso, 2023), (Al-Mamoori, et al., 2017). However, it also presents challenges mainly coming from the need for large quantities of oxygen, produced through energy intensive Air Separation Units (ASU), and the technical complexity of the process. Ongoing research aims to improve efficiency, reduce costs and address these technical challenges (Nagireddi, et al., 2023).

3.2.2.2 SOLVENT-BASED ABSORPTION CARBON CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES

Absorption or solvent-based CO₂ capture is the most established method that is currently used in industries such as oil refining, natural gas production, steel, iron, cement, power generation, etc. The development of chemical absorption dates back to the 1930s and it has been employed in industrial applications for many decades. This technique involves the chemical or physical absorption of CO₂ into a liquid solvent that acts as a CO₂ carrier. Important properties of solvents for CO₂ capture are: (i) CO₂ solubility, (ii) absorption kinetics and (iii) speciation distribution. Solvent-based CO₂ capture is commonly applied for both post-combustion capture (using mainly chemical solvents) and pre-combustion capture (using mainly physical solvents) (Al-Mamoori, et al., 2017).

Chemical absorption relies on the reaction between CO₂ and a solvent, forming an intermediate compound through either a reversible or irreversible chemical reaction. Solvents used in this process include ammonia and amine-based solvents such as monoethanolamine (MEA), diethanolamine

(DEA), N-methyldiethanolamine (MDEA), 2-amino-2-methyl-propanol (AMP), piperazine (PZ), as well as alkaline solvents like $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, NaOH and KOH. The regeneration of the solvent is mainly achieved through heating, which causes the intermediate compound to break down and decompose releasing CO_2 and regenerating the primary solvent. The primary advantage of chemical absorption is its high efficiency in removing low concentrations of CO_2 from exhaust gas mixtures at relatively low pressures. However, one of the limitations of the process is the need to purify the flue gases from O_2 , SO_2 , NO_x and particulate matter in order to prevent interference with the absorber column. Furthermore, the corrosive nature of the solvents, the large volume of water required as a reaction medium and the high energy consumption associated with solvent regeneration are also disadvantages of the specific technology. Even though heat integration can mitigate energy requirements in some industrial sectors like power generation, it is not easily applicable in cement, iron and steel production plants (Dziejarski, et al., 2023), (Al-Mamoori, et al., 2017).

An essential balance in chemical absorption lies between reaction heat and reaction speed. The separation efficiency can be improved by utilizing thermally stable solvents with low regeneration energy and high heat of absorption (>60 kJ/mol) to lower the process energy requirements. However, impurity tolerance, oxidation resistance and solvent vapor losses are also critical factors for solvents selection (Al-Mamoori, et al., 2017).

The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) for CO_2 capture methods via chemical absorption is closely linked to post-combustion approaches and varies based on the type of liquid solvents used. Amine solvents are a highly mature technology, which is currently considered as the benchmark, reaching a TRL of 9. It is widely applied in natural gas, fertilizer and soda ash processing facilities. In contrast, other technologies using solvents like sterically hindered amines, ammonia and phase change solvents have a TRL of 6-7 (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

On the other hand, physical absorption involves dissolving CO_2 in a solvent that does not chemically react with it but is bound by weak van der Waals forces. Physical absorption adheres to Henry's law which states that the concentration of a dissolved gas in the absorption liquid is proportional to the partial pressure of the gas above the liquid's surface. Regeneration of the solvent occurs through desorption, by increasing temperature, reducing pressure or both. The advantages of physical absorption include low energy consumption for solvent regeneration and lower temperatures required compared to chemical absorption. Physical absorption is particularly efficient at high CO_2 partial pressures, like those in Integrated Gasification Combined Cycle (IGCC) systems, requiring CO_2 concentrations of at least 15% by volume to be economically viable (Dziejarski, et al., 2023), (Al-Mamoori, et al., 2017).

Commonly used solvents in natural gas processing and coal gasification include Selecot (polyethylene glycol dimethyl ethers) and Rectisol (cold methanol), at TRL 9, along with Purisol and Fluor at lower TRLs. Physical absorption for carbon capture is also applied in ammonia production (TRL 9), methanol synthesis (TRL 7-8) and high-value chemicals development (TRL 7-8). Recently, ionic liquids (ILs) have emerged as promising alternatives to traditional physical solvents due to their advantageous properties such as low volatility, low vapor pressure, high thermal stability and low energy requirements for regeneration. Despite these benefits, their low working capacity and high cost of production remain significant barriers to their widespread adoption for CO_2 capture with respective TRL typically around 3 to 4 (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

3.2.2.2 GAS SEPARATION MEMBRANES FOR CARBON CAPTURE

Gas separation membranes (permeators) for CO₂ capture involve the use of a thin layer of semipermeable material (membrane) where different molecules permeate at different rates, providing selective separation of a specific gaseous component. It typically operates under steady-state, continuous operation conditions, driven by an applied driving force, e.g. a pressure gradient, temperature difference or electric potential across the two sides of the membrane. The membrane divides the feed gas stream into a permeate gas stream (enriched in the most permeable component) and a residue stream called retentate (enriched in the least permeable component). The performance of gas separation membranes is influenced by their configuration, morphology and material composition. To achieve high CO₂ separation efficiency, a membrane must have high permeance, high selectivity and also physical, chemical, mechanical and thermal stability in industrial applications.

While suitable for high-pressure pre-combustion processes, post-combustion CO₂ capture from low-pressure flue gas presents significant challenges. Membranes offer several advantages compared to absorption processes such as avoiding weeping, entrainment, foaming, or flooding and providing flexibility of operation and easy and linear scale-up. However, their efficiency drops at CO₂ concentrations below 20% and face challenges with high temperatures, corrosive gases and long-term efficiency maintenance (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

Among the various membrane materials, polymer-based options offer significant advantages in terms of processability, solubility in common solvents and low cost relative to inorganic materials. The solution-diffusion and facilitated transport mechanisms are widely recognized and used to guide the design of new polymers. Polymers such as polyacetylene, polyaniline, polyetherimides, polycarbonates, polyphenylene oxide, polyethylene oxide and polysulfone have been explored for post-combustion CO₂ capture. By adjusting polymer preparation and chemical composition, these membranes can achieve highly tunable permeability and selectivity. However, issues like swelling and plasticization due to CO₂ adsorption remain significant challenges (Chen, et al., 2022). Polymeric membranes are very promising for large-scale applications and are commercialized for CO₂ capture in natural gas sweetening (Hou, et al., 2022).

Polymers with intrinsic microporosity (PIMs) offer a solution with higher CO₂ flux due to large free pores within the polymer matrix. Facilitated-transport membranes (FTMs), including ion-exchange, liquid and fixed-carrier membranes, are highly selective for CO₂ but are susceptible to poisoning by trace acid gases in flue gas. Future advancements may involve the use of composite membranes that combine the benefits of inorganic and polymeric materials. For example, Mixed-Matrix Membranes (MMMs) combine highly selective molecular sieve particle (carbon nanotubes, zeolites, MOFs and layered silicates) with a polymer matrix achieving the merge of the processing advantages of polymer membranes with the superior performance of molecular-sieving materials. However, their commercialization is challenged by costly and complex fabrication procedures (Al-Mamoori, et al., 2017).

Inorganic porous membranes, such as ceramics, zeolites, carbon molecular sieves (CMS), metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) and oxides like alumina, titania and zirconia, are well-studied. Although they withstand high temperatures and offer mechanical stability, their low reproducibility, high production cost and long-term stability issues hinder large-scale use (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

Gas separation membranes in natural gas processing have reached commercial operations (TRL 9), while polymeric membranes and their hybrids ones are also effective for pre- or post- combustion

capture, reaching a TRL 7 in large pilot installations. Zeolites, ceramics, metals and other inorganic materials also show significant potential, but they are currently at lower TRL of 4-6 depending on the material and the application. Electrochemical membranes integrated with Molten Carbonate Fuel Cells (MCFCs) are at TRL 7, while room temperature ionic liquid (RTIL) membranes are at TRL 2 (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

3.2.2.3 ADSORPTION BASED CARBON CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES

Adsorption is defined as the adhesion of ions, atoms or molecules from a liquid, gas or dissolved solid to a surface. The adhered particles form a film on the surface of the adsorbing material, known as the adsorbent. Adsorption occurs only on the surface, leading to lower surface energy due to the bonding requirements of the adsorbent being fulfilled by the adsorbate atoms. The type of bonding that occurs during adsorption depends on the species involved. Adsorption can be physical (physisorption, involving weak van der Waals forces), chemical (chemisorption, involving covalent bonding), or due to electrostatic attraction. The adsorption process is cyclical, consisting of adsorption and desorption of CO₂ through temperature or pressure modulation (Ben-Mansour, et al., 2016).

During adsorption, the adsorption column is filled with the adsorbent and the CO₂-rich flue gas is passing through the solid material where CO₂ molecules are being adsorbed allowing the rest of the gas mixture to exit the column. After adsorption, the adsorbent layer is being regenerated by CO₂ desorption in order to be reused in the next adsorption cycle. The desorbed CO₂ is transported, conditioned and compressed in the downstream processes. The effectiveness of CO₂ capture by adsorbent material is mainly determined by two factors: its chemical properties and the development of its porous structure. The first factor affects the interaction forces between CO₂ molecules and the solid surface while the second determines the available space for gas adsorption (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

Common adsorbents include Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs), zeolites, silicates, activated carbon, organic and inorganic polymers and biochar. MOF-based adsorbents consist of metal centers and organic linkers that coordinate to form a continuous network. These materials are particularly suited for gas separation and capture due to their tunable pore sizes, which can be optimized for the capture of specific gas molecules such as CO₂, CH₄ and H₂O. Organic polymers also exhibit effective CO₂ adsorption and capture capabilities. These materials can take the form of organic covalent frameworks with microporous cavities that accommodate CO₂ molecules, or long chains with specific functional group orientations providing adsorption sites for CO₂. Inorganic materials, typically in the form of inorganic salts or natural minerals incorporated into support or additive matrices using impregnation methods, include metal oxides, hydroxides, metallic salts and minerals that interact with CO₂ through acid-base reactions, given the basic nature of many metallic oxides and hydroxides. Silicon-based materials are a notable class of inorganic adsorbents due to their wide range of applications as porous materials. Chemically and physically stable materials include zeolites, porous silica and other molecular sieves. The use of biomass byproducts, such as lignocellulosic biomass, tar and biochar from burnt carbon sources like fly ash and natural plant-based materials, also offers a sustainable alternative (Soo, et al., 2024).

Key factors in adsorption efficiency include the ease of regenerating adsorbed CO₂ and as a result the low energy consumption of the process, the durability and selectivity of the adsorbent for CO₂ and the adsorption capacity and the stability of the adsorbent after several adsorption/desorption

cycles. The regeneration step is the primary contributor to the overall energy requirement of the process. Nevertheless, CO₂ capture using physical sorbents and inorganic porous materials, such as carbonaceous materials and zeolites, consumes less energy compared to chemical sorbents. This is due to the absence of new bond formation between the adsorbate and adsorbent, resulting in lower energy requirements for CO₂ regeneration (Ben-Mansour, et al., 2016).

Challenges remain in commercializing these materials as further research is needed to improve their performance and stability. Suitable materials for carbon capture must account for the size and electronic behavior of gas molecules. Since the kinetic diameters of gas molecules are similar (e.g. CH₄: 3.76 Å, CO₂: 3.30 Å, N₂: 3.64 Å), CO₂ separation cannot be based solely on molecule size. Instead, differences in electronic properties such as quadrupolar moment and polarization provide a basis for separation, as these properties vary significantly between gases. Despite their low cost and high availability, materials such as activated carbon face challenges with poor CO₂/N₂ selectivity. Moreover, although molecular sieve membranes show great potential, traditional molecular sieves like zeolites suffer from lower CO₂ loading and reduced efficiency in the presence of water exhibiting limitations in CO₂/N₂ separation due to the similar kinetic diameters of N₂ (3.64 Å) and CO₂ (3.3 Å) (Ben-Mansour, et al., 2016).

Physical and chemical adsorption technologies are at different stages of technological readiness. Pressure swing adsorption (PSA) is the most advanced method achieving TRL 9 with variants like vacuum swing adsorption (VSA), vacuum pressure swing adsorption (VPSA), temperature swing adsorption (TSA) and electric swing adsorption (ESA) having different readiness levels, with VSA also approaching TRL 9. Physical adsorption, using materials like activated carbon, silica, alumina, MOFs and zeolites, is widely used in industries (TRL 5-8) such as cement, chemical and iron and steel. In contrast, chemical adsorption, involving materials like metal oxides, metal salts, amine-based adsorbents and hydrotalcites, remains at the research and development phase. Other innovative technologies, such as enzyme-catalyzed adsorption (TRL 6), sorbent-enhanced water gas shift (TRL 5) and electrochemically mediated adsorption (TRL 1-2) are under exploration (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

3.2.2.4 CRYOGENIC DISTILLATION BASED CARBON CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES

Cryogenic distillation consists of compressing a flue gas mixture and cooling it across several stages to the appropriate temperature to separate CO₂ based on its dew point compared to the rest of the flue gas components. Cryogenic Carbon Capture (CCC) is commonly implemented in natural gas purification as proposed by Ryan and Holmes. In this method, to avoid solidification of CO₂, extractive distillation or “Ryan Holmes” technology uses heavier hydrocarbons (e.g. methane or heavier hydrocarbon such as ethane), which increases the solubility of CO₂ in the liquid phase, operating temperature and relative volatility, facilitating separation. The feed gas is pre-cooled and then further chilled by a heat exchanger before entering a distillation column. Within the column, vapor-liquid contact devices facilitate the separation of methane at the top and condensed CO₂ at the bottom. Part of the CO₂-rich stream is recycled through a reboiler, while the rest is further separated and finally, the purified CO₂ product is extracted from the separator. (Song, et al., 2018), (Font-Palma, et al., 2021).

This method can achieve a CO₂ recovery and purity of 99.99% and is particularly suitable for CO₂-rich flue gases (concentrations over 50%) from oxy-fuel combustion, integrating well with CO₂ purification units (CPUs) for low-temperature separation. The primary advantages of this CO₂

separation method include the absence of chemical reagents and ease of transporting CO₂, which is obtained directly in the liquid phase. Despite its widespread use, cryogenic distillation is costly because of the need to reduce water content to avoid issues like ice formation and equipment clogging. It is also considered energy-intensive, accounting for over 50% of plant operating costs. To address this, energy-efficient solutions such as cyclic distillation, heat-integrated distillation columns, reactive distillation and thermally coupled columns have been proposed. CCC methods are currently being advanced in combination with other CO₂ capture technologies such as polymeric membranes, hydrates, adsorption (zeolites 4A and 13X) and absorption (chilled ammonia process) (Nagireddi, et al., 2023), (Song, et al., 2018).

Cryogenic methods for CO₂ capture are primarily being explored at low technology readiness levels (TRLs) to advance this approach and integrate it with other capture processes, such as polymeric membrane techniques (TRL 6). Hybrid cryogenic-based CO₂ capture systems involving membranes, hydrates, adsorption (e.g. zeolites), and absorption (e.g., chilled ammonia) are mostly at the laboratory scale (TRL 3). Current R&D efforts focus on cement production, with notable projects like Sustainable Energy Solutions aiming to scale up to 30 tonnes of CO₂ captured per day (TRL 5) at the Central Plains Cement Plant and the University of Illinois working on a combined pressure swing adsorption and cryogenic unit for high-purity CO₂ production at Holcim Ste. Genevieve, aiming for a commercial-scale system with 95% CO₂ separation (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

3.2.2.5 CHEMICAL LOOPING CARBON CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES

Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC) proposed by Ritcher and Knoche is a CO₂ emission reduction method that employs the combustion of fossil fuels using solid-state oxygen carrier materials, typically transition metal oxides. This method avoids using air which dilutes the combustion effluent stream because of the N₂. By this approach, combustion is divided into reduction processes and intermediate oxidation which are carried out independently with a solid oxygen carrier (OC) circulating between two separated units. While some researchers list CLC as a form of pre-combustion CO₂ capture technique, others consider it as a distinct fourth technology. CLC can concentrate CO₂ in the effluent stream up to 100% while pre-combustion CO₂ capture technologies can reach a maximum concentration of 50% (Alalwan & Alminshid, 2021).

CLC technology consists of two internally connected reactors. One is an air oxidizer while the other is a fuel reactor, also called reducer. The reduced metal oxides are directed to the air reactor, where they undergo oxidation. After oxidization, the oxygen carriers are transported to the fuel reactor, where they are reduced to provide a source of oxygen for the fuel, ultimately oxidizing it to produce CO₂ and H₂O. The combustion products (CO₂ and water vapor) and concentrated CO₂ can be easily obtained by condensing the water vapor. Key properties of oxygen carriers that increase the CLC efficiency include high oxygen capacity, high re-oxidation rate, high reactivity, excellent stability during CLC cycles, mechanical strength to withstand the stress associated with circulation, high resistance to agglomeration, minimal environmental effect and cost-effectiveness (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

The primary advantages of the chemical looping combustion technology are the lack of harmful compounds in the air reactor exhaust gases and the ease of CO₂ separation from the fuel reactor exhaust gas stream using a condenser. This approach eliminates the need for CO₂ separation, purification, compression, transportation and storage, thereby reducing energy penalties, lowering costs and minimizing safety risks. Although it presents a promising technology by enabling

simultaneous capture and conversion through an efficient and safe process, most studies have explored the reactivity and stability of oxygen carriers, with relatively few investigating the underlying surface chemistry, the reduction and re-oxidation reaction mechanisms of the OC and the economic impact of the technology. Other disadvantages include poor stability of the oxygen carrier and slow redox kinetics (Jin, et al., 2023). Currently, most CLC systems are evaluated at Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 5–6, corresponding to pilot tests. Compared to another solid looping technology, calcium looping (CaL), which involves high-temperature looping cycles, CLC is less advanced in terms of commercial-scale implementation (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

3.2.2.6 HYBRID CARBON CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES

Hybrid processes can be categorized based on the primary carbon capture technology used, including absorption-based, adsorption-based, membrane-based and cryogenic-based configurations, each offering various options in process layout, as depicted in Figure 3.15. Hybrid processes offer significant potential for CO₂ capture due to their high performance and flexibility in operating parameters, cost-effectiveness, scalability and sustainability (Yu, et al., 2023). CO₂ recovery and energy consumption vary depending on the source of the CO₂ emissions. The selection of suitable hybrid processes depends on factors such as the properties of the feed gas (e.g. CO₂ concentration, temperature and pressure), the required product purity and the availability of carbon capture equipment (Song, et al., 2018).

Figure 3.15. Existing hybrid CO₂ capture technologies (Song, et al., 2018).

These processes can generally be configured in three main ways: in-series, parallel and integrated arrangements. In-series arrangement is currently a popular research focus and involves configuring

membrane units to function as either pre-treatment or post-treatment in series with other carbon capture technologies. In contrast, in the parallel arrangement, the flue gas stream of the power plant is split and treated simultaneously by different systems. Compared to the in-series arrangement, the parallel arrangement offers the advantage of reducing the size of the equipment due to the reduced volume of gas treated, resulting in lower capital costs. Well-studied integrated arrangements include the combined solvent absorption and membrane separation technology (membrane contactor process). These integrated processes have the potential to achieve both economic and technical feasibility (Yu, et al., 2023).

Membrane contactors is one of the most promising hybrid technologies, applied in CO₂ capture processes. A membrane contactor – comprised of porous hollow fibers – is a device that allows gas-liquid mass transfer at the membrane pores' openings without direct contact of the two phases which flow at the different sides of the membrane. Conventional membrane processes often require flue gas compression, permeate side sweep, application of a permeate-side vacuum or a combination of these methods to create the separation driving force. In membrane contactors, the separation driving force comes from the solvent as in conventional absorption processes and the membrane is just providing a very high and well defined contact area between the two phases. The integration of absorption and membrane technologies combines the high selectivity of liquid absorption with the modularity and compactness of membrane separation, making it particularly effective at low CO₂ concentrations (Asimakopoulou, et al., 2021), (Damartzis, et al., 2022). However, a drawback of membrane contactors is the increased mass transfer resistance, especially when the membranes become wetted (Song, et al., 2018).

Apart from membrane contactors, combining absorption and membrane technologies in series or parallel arrangements is also a promising hybrid CO₂ capture method, offering cost savings from reduced regeneration energy and capital costs. Absorption-adsorption hybrid technologies use advanced sorbent materials like carbon, silica or polymers integrated with amine compounds to separate CO₂ from gas streams. The CO₂ absorbed on the amine sites is released by increasing the temperature (TSA) or pressure (PSA). The adsorption-catalysis process is used in H₂ purification through the sorption-enhanced water gas shift (SEWGS) reaction, combining a high-temperature water gas shift (WGS) catalyst and a CO₂ sorbent in the same reactor. Combining the SEWGS with a membrane in an adsorption-catalysis-membrane process is a promising option for producing ultrapure H₂ (>99.9%) (Song, et al., 2018).

One of the key advantages of membrane-based hybrid CC technologies is the maturity and frequent application of gas permeation membranes. Compared with absorption-based processes, gas permeation is efficient for moderate gas purification. In membrane-absorption processes, a membrane-amine hybrid is used for post-combustion CO₂ capture, with the membrane recovering most CO₂ and the retentate feeding the amine unit to achieve the desired recovery (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

Finally, adsorption-cryogenic technology uses a vacuum swing adsorption (VSA) unit followed by low-temperature separation to produce high-purity CO₂, which can be pumped to a supercritical state for transportation and sequestration. Adsorption-Membrane technology, used in biogas upgrading, involves a two-stage membrane process coupled with temperature-swing adsorption (TSA) as pre-treatment to produce pipeline-quality methane. Finally, low temperature-based technologies, including cryogenic processes, produce high-quality CO₂. In cryogenic hybrid processes, condensed liquid CO₂ can be more readily pumped to a supercritical state compared to gaseous CO₂, which would require a separate compression stage (Song, et al., 2018).

3.2.2.7 COMPARATIVE CHART FOR CARBON CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES

Table 6. Comparative chart for carbon capture technologies (Nagireddi, et al., 2023) (Al-Mamoori, et al., 2017) (Adam & Ozarisoy, 2023), (Shen, et al., 2022).

CC PROCESS	TRL	ENERGY CONSUMPTION	MAIN FEATURES & ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES & LIMITATIONS	CO ₂ RECOVERY
Chemical and physical absorption	9	1.83–9 GJ/t _{CO2}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mature and well-established process. • High capture efficiency at relatively low gas pressure for chemical absorption. • High capture efficiency at particularly high gas pressure for physical absorption. • Many different solvents used. • Short startup time. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High operating cost because of high energy consumption. • No tolerance to SO₂, O₂, dust and hydrocarbons. • High equipment corrosion rate. • Environmental impact because of solvent emissions and losses. • Large capital cost resulting from plant equipment size (voluminous equipment) and high-performance sorbent. 	60-95%
Membrane	7	0.5-6 GJ/t _{CO2}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low operating cost because of low energy consumption. • Smaller equipment, modular scale-up. • No hazardous chemicals used. • Tolerance to SO_x and NO_x. • Short startup time. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low membrane durability, potential fouling effect. • High cost of inorganic membranes. • Requires constant flue gas compression. • Limitations in materials choice at high operating temperatures. 	60-90%

CC PROCESS	TRL	ENERGY CONSUMPTION	MAIN FEATURES & ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES & LIMITATIONS	CO ₂ RECOVERY
Adsorption	7-9	2.4-9 GJ/t _{CO2}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mature and well-established process. • High capture efficiency. • Low cost of sorbents. • Sorbents can be regenerated and reused with lower energy requirements compared to solvents. • Can be used for low CO₂ concentrations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low CO₂ selectivity. • Large pressure drop in flue gas and adsorbent attrition. • High energy consumption imposed by high pressure requirement for CO₂ adsorption and temperature for sorbent regeneration. • Needs periodic operation. • Periodic sorbent regeneration leads to quick degradation of sorbents and subsequent replacement. 	80-95%
Cryogenic	6	0.8-3.4 GJ/t _{CO2}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very high capture efficiency (99.99%). • Liquid CO₂ produced is ready for transport. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High operational cost due to high energy consumption. • Solid CO₂ can accumulate on the surface of the heat exchanger reducing efficiency and affecting heat transfer phenomena. 	99.99%
Chemical looping combustion	6	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No hazardous chemical handling, disposal or emissions issues. • Very high capture efficiency • Low operating cost. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High attrition rate and vulnerability. • High capital investment. • Requirement of an air separation unit to obtain pure O₂ for calcination. 	Up to 100%

3.2.3 CARBON DIOXIDE STORAGE AND TRANSPORTATION

CO₂ storage and transportation is considered just as important as CO₂ capture within the broader framework of carbon capture, utilization and storage (CCUS) technologies. After CO₂ is captured from industrial sources and subsequently separated and purified, the gas stream can either be directly converted to e-methanol on-site or transported in an appropriate phase to a remote e-methanol synthesis facility. Permanent geological and oceanic storage methods, along with mineral storage through mineral carbonation, fall outside the scope of the POSEIDON project. Therefore, the following analysis focuses on temporary storage methods involving high-pressure gas and cryogenic storage tanks, as well as the main transportation technologies available.

Carbon dioxide has a melting point of 194.7 K and a boiling point of 216.6 K, making it denser than air under normal conditions and slightly soluble in water. It is chemically inactive, exhibits high thermal stability (only 1.8% degradation at 2000°C), non-flammable, does not generally assist in combustion, and is non-toxic in low quantities. Carbon dioxide reaches its critical state at a temperature of 304.1 K and a pressure of 7.38 MPa, making it relatively easy to attain the supercritical state. When the temperature and pressure of carbon dioxide exceed these critical values, it is classified as supercritical carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂) (Ma, et al., 2024).

Temporary CO₂ storage can take place in compressed gas or cryogenic storage tanks. CO₂ storage and cryogenic tanks provide a safe and reliable method for storing both liquid and vaporized CO₂. These tanks safely store CO₂ at high pressures while ensuring high safety standards. Made from high-grade metals, they are designed to offer complete protection against corrosion. The tanks are leak-proof and available in both horizontal and vertical configurations. They are widely used across various industries, including beverage production, beer bottling plants, firefighting, welding, fisheries, dry ice blasting and cooling storage. Additionally, the tanks feature bayonet couplings for easy installation and come with superior insulation to maintain stability against temperature fluctuations and adverse weather conditions (TechnoEngineers, 2025).

In case of liquid storage, liquefaction of the CO₂ containing gas stream is necessary. The liquefaction of carbon dioxide is a sophisticated process involving multiple compressions and expansions to achieve high pressures and extremely low temperatures, resulting in the formation of liquid CO₂. This process involves refrigerating gaseous CO₂ below its critical temperature, requiring high-performance compressors and pumps to elevate pressure. Cooling systems play a crucial role in chilling the compressed gas, preparing it for liquefaction. Heat exchange technology is central to this process, utilizing temperature differentials to efficiently transfer heat to or from the CO₂. Expansion valves further regulate the pressure release, ensuring a controlled expansion of the gas, ultimately leading to the formation of liquid CO₂ (TechnoEngineers, 2025).

Technologically advanced alternatives to compressed gas or cryogenic storage tanks, are Carbon Capture and Energy Storage (CCES) systems that stand out as promising solutions among various energy storage methods, offering numerous benefits such as easy liquefaction, high energy storage density, and environmental sustainability. CCES technology is rapidly advancing due to its efficient storage of both liquid and gaseous CO₂ under high pressure. The CCES system operates through multi-stage compression, thermal energy storage, high-pressure gas storage and expansion processes. During the energy storage phase, excess electrical energy is used to compress carbon dioxide to a supercritical state, storing heat in thermal devices. High-pressure carbon dioxide is then stored and later used to generate electricity through expansion turbines, optimizing cycle efficiency

and energy storage density. Carbon dioxide is chemically stable and thermally efficient, easily reaching the supercritical state under high pressure. The system leverages innovative approaches, such as geothermal gradients, to eliminate the need for heat accumulators in underground storage, showcasing a promising future for advanced energy storage solutions (Ma, et al., 2024).

Regarding CO₂ transportation to a remote storage or e-methanol synthesis site, transporting CO₂ as a gas is not economically efficient, often leading to significant pressure losses. There is general agreement that large quantities of CO₂ are best transported either in a liquid state or, preferably, in a supercritical state (above the critical temperature and pressure), or as a dense-phase fluid (above critical pressure but below critical temperature). The dense phase offers significant advantages due to its energy-efficient conditions, combining gas-like viscosity with liquid-like density. Beyond phase state considerations, other factors such as density, viscosity, heat capacity, and thermal conductivity of CO₂ have been studied for their impact on transport costs, pressure drops, and temperature variations (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

CO₂ transportation processes are well-established and can be categorized into offshore and onshore systems. Onshore transport includes highways, railroads, and pipelines, while offshore options involve pipelines and ships, with the choice largely dependent on the distance to the CO₂ storage or utilization site. Among the most technically advanced and widely adopted methods are onshore and offshore pipelines, as well as transport ships. While CO₂ can also be transported by road and rail tankers, these are not ideal for large-scale CCS projects (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

CO₂ pipelines are a well-established technology that has been extensively used worldwide for decades, with over 5000 miles of pipelines operational in the United States as of 2017. They present minimal risk of leakage due to CO₂'s non-toxic and non-flammable nature. CO₂ pipelines operate by compressing the gas to pressures of 100-200 bar (above the critical pressure of ~73.8 bar), avoiding multiphase flow and reducing transport challenges and costs. Pipeline capacity is determined by factors such as diameter, pressure, flow rate, and fluid properties, with investment costs closely linked to pipeline diameter. Optimal design seeks to balance these factors to minimize costs while meeting transport requirements. Current research focuses on improving pipeline materials and design, addressing challenges like the impact of impurities (e.g., H₂S, O₂, H₂O) on phase equilibrium, and mitigating corrosion. Innovative construction methods and advanced detection technologies are also key areas of development to enhance efficiency, safety, and reliability (Dziejarski, et al., 2023), (Smith, et al., 2021).

Over the past 30 years, CO₂ has been transported by ships for applications related to food and industrial use. This method utilizes cryo-compressed conditions, with a working pressure of 15–20 bar and a temperature of -30°C, ensuring optimal transport efficiency. In some cases, especially over long distances, shipping may be the most cost-effective option due to its flexibility and economic advantages. Ship transport involves essential equipment, such as intermediate storage tanks, loading and unloading facilities, and CO₂ carrier/cargo tanks. These tanks are typically classified into three types: pressurized, fully refrigerated and semi-refrigerated. The design of these tanks is influenced by three key factors: boiling temperature, internal pressure (based on vapor and liquid pressures), and cargo density, which impact tank design and stability. The primary challenge in CO₂ shipping lies in maintaining strict control over temperature and pressure, while also managing potential risks such as mechanical damage, leakage, and varying atmospheric conditions during transport (Dziejarski, et al., 2023).

CO₂ can also be transported by train or truck, which may be economical over short distances and

for small volumes. While these modes of transport could be useful during the initial phases of carbon capture and storage (CCS) deployment, they are unlikely to play a significant role in large-scale CCS implementation. Pipelines and ships are expected to be far more cost-effective for transporting megaton-scale quantities of CO₂ annually due to economies of scale (Smith, et al., 2021).

3.3 CO₂ FROM AN INDUSTRIAL SOURCE AS FEEDSTOCK – PORT OF THESSALONIKI CASE STUDY

The POSEIDON case study in Thessaloniki, Greece, examines CO₂ emissions from CaO Hellas, a lime production plant approximately 10 km from the port of Thessaloniki and a member of the POSEIDON project consortium. The plant's CO₂ emissions originate from two main sources: exhaust gases from the heat production unit and lime-off gas, a byproduct of CaCO₃ calcination, which contains approximately 40% CO₂ by volume. The calcination process, described by the highly endothermic reaction (2), occurs at high temperatures (900–1200°C), requiring significant heat input from the combustion of fuels such as coal, coke, or natural gas:

CO₂ emissions per ton of lime produced range from 1 to 2 tons, with lime-off gas contributing approximately 70% of the plant's total emissions. This source is considered unavoidable. The plant generates about 100 tons of CO₂ daily (70% from the calcination process and 30% from fuel combustion), resulting in approximately 27,000 tons of annual emissions from calcination and a total of 40,000 tons of CO₂ emissions per year. While emissions from fuel combustion can be reduced by using renewable fuels like biomass, emissions from the calcination reaction itself can only be mitigated through carbon capture technologies, as discussed in Section 3.2 (Greco-Coppi, et al., 2023). Figure 3.16 illustrates the proposed simplified value chain under investigation within the POSEIDON project. As depicted, CO₂ emissions from the CaO Hellas plant can undergo carbon capture, with the captured CO₂ being purified before being directed to a methanol (MeOH) synthesis unit. The CO₂ purification technologies available for industrial CO₂ streams are analyzed in the following section.

Figure 3.16. Value chain of CO₂ from industrial sources as feedstock for e-MeOH synthesis.

Regarding recent advancements in CO₂ capture from lime plants, the research is limited. However, similarities with the cement production industry - where calcination is also the primary energy-intensive step - make many approaches transferable. Both industries emit comparable CO₂ levels from raw materials and flue gases contain similar components when using the same fuels. Two primary carbon capture methods can address these emissions: post-combustion and oxyfuel combustion. Pre-combustion capture is unsuitable for lime production as it does not address process

CO₂ emissions. Post-combustion capture technologies can capture the majority of CO₂ emissions effectively. Oxyfuel combustion, capable of capturing CO₂ from both fuel and process emissions, requires an energy intensive air separation unit to supply pure oxygen. Alternatively, oxyfuel combustion carbon capture could be integrated to de-centralized e-fuel production facilities, where water electrolysis for hydrogen generation, inherently produces oxygen as a byproduct. This surplus oxygen can be redirected to the lime or cement plant's oxyfuel combustion process, reducing the need for separate oxygen production facilities and enhancing overall energy efficiency (GrecoCoppi, et al., 2023).

Monoethanolamine-based absorption is a benchmark post-combustion technology used in cement carbon capture. However, solvent-based post-combustion technologies demand high energy for sorbent regeneration, typically around 3.5 GJ/tCO₂. A notable carbon capture technology is the carbonate looping (CaL) process, which captures CO₂ using limestone (CaCO₃) as a sorbent. In this process, the sorbent binds with CO₂ from kiln flue gases within a carbonator and is then regenerated by raising the temperature in a calciner, following equation (2) above. In the standard oxy-fired CaL process, fuel is burned directly in the calciner for sorbent regeneration, using technically pure oxygen, which requires an air separation unit (ASU). CaL technology holds significant potential to efficiently capture CO₂ from lime plants by leveraging the synergies inherent in the calcination process. An alternative approach, Calix's Direct Separation Technology, is under development in the LEILAC (Low Emissions Intensity Lime And Cement) project, which indirectly heats raw meal to capture unavoidable process CO₂ emissions. Furthermore, the CEMCAP (Making CO₂ Capture Retrofittable to Cement Plants) project evaluated four other CO₂ capture technologies for the cement industry - oxyfuel combustion, chilled ammonia process (CAP), membrane-assisted CO₂ liquefaction (MAL) and carbonate looping (CaL) - finding that oxyfuel (42.4 €/tCO₂) and CaL (52.4 €/tCO₂) had the lowest CO₂ avoidance costs (Greco-Coppi, et al., 2021), (Greco-Coppi, et al., 2023).

The efficiency of the CaL process can be improved by avoiding the need for pure oxygen, achieved by using steam for sorbent regeneration or indirect heating methods, like heat pipes. Indirectly heated carbonate looping (IHCaL) provides several advantages: reduced energy and investment costs, lower impurities in the Ca-loop, higher-purity spent sorbent, lower sorbent deactivation rates and an almost pure CO₂ stream. The IHCaL process has shown promise in power plant applications, with CO₂ avoidance costs estimated at 22.6 €/tCO₂ (excluding storage). The ANICA project has now adapted IHCaL for lime plants, studying two concepts for integration: a tail-end solution for capturing flue gas CO₂ and an integrated solution where lime production and capture are combined. Both designs were numerically evaluated, and experimental validation is planned with pilot tests at a 300 kW_{th} scale (Greco-Coppi, et al., 2021).

3.3.1 INDUSTRIAL CO₂ PURIFICATION TECHNOLOGIES

The level of purification that the CO₂ stream exiting industrial facilities depends on its intended application. An overall maximum impurity requirement level that covers applications such as CO₂ pipe transportation and storage is shown in Table 7 (Abbas, et al., 2013).

Table 7. Purification limits for pipeline transportation of CO₂ stream (Abbas, et al., 2013).

COMPONENT	PURITY REQUIREMENT	REASON
H ₂ O	< 50 ppmv	Corrosion and hydrate formation.
H ₂ S	< 10-200 ppmv	Hydrate formation & toxicity.
O ₂	< 10 ppmv	Corrosion and two-phase flow.
N ₂	< 4% vol. (All Non-condensables)	Increases Minimum Miscibility Pressure.
H ₂	< 4% vol. (All Non-condensables)	Two-phase flow.
Ar	< 4% vol. (All Non-condensables)	Two-phase flow and volume efficiency (pipeline capacity is reduced).
CO	2000 ppmv	Health and Safety consideration.
NO _x	< 100 ppmv	Health and Safety consideration.
SO _x	< 50 ppmv	Health and Safety consideration.
Hydrocarbons (HCs)	< 2%	Hydrate formation and MMP.

In the POSEIDON project, the CO₂ stream produced from either the lime production plant or the WWT plant (after biogas upgrading) is introduced into a catalytic methanol synthesis process to produce liquid e-methanol. Currently, commercially used low-pressure catalysts for methanol synthesis are primarily based on CuO and ZnO, usually supported by Al₂O₃, supplemented with promoters and additives for stabilizing such as Cr, Zr, Mg and rare earth metals. In industrial applications, the typical lifespan of these catalysts ranges from 4 to 6 years, with some reports extending up to 8 years. Catalyst deactivation is mainly due to poisoning and thermal sintering. Major poisons for copper catalysts include sulfur compounds, which block active sites, and chlorides, which accelerate sintering. The tolerance for sulfur is generally higher than for chlorides, as sulfur is neutralized by the ZnO component in Cu/ZnO catalysts. Other significant poisons include arsenic and carbonyls (formed at high CO concentrations in certain steel types), which reduce selectivity by promoting Fischer–Tropsch side reactions. Table 8 summarizes typical gas purity requirements for this type of catalysts (Dieterich, et al., 2020).

Table 8. CO₂ feed gas stream purity requirements for Cu/ZnO methanol synthesis catalysts (Dieterich, et al., 2020).

COMPONENT	PURITY REQUIREMENT
H ₂ S	< 0.05-0.5 ppm
HCl	1 ppb
Metal carbonyl	Few ppb
Particles	< 0.1 mg/Nm ³
Tar	< 1.0 mg/Nm ³
Alkalis	< 0.25 mg/Nm ³

According to data from the CaO Hellas lime production plant, the average flue gas composition consists of N₂ (51% vol.), CO₂ (40% vol.), O₂ (9% vol.) and SO₂ (70 ppm). The removal of nitrogen gas is not considered necessary before or after carbon capture, as it is an inert, non-toxic gas that can be released into the atmosphere through the CC exiting gas stream after CO₂ has been captured from the flue gas. Oxygen removal typically can be achieved by the carbon capture process itself. If it cannot be achieved or any remaining traces need to be removed, this can be done through various methods, including catalytic oxidation of carbon monoxide (using cobalt oxides in a combustion reactor), catalytic oxidation of propane (in the presence of Co₃O₄ nanorods as a catalyst), catalytic oxidation of methanol (using an AuCeDP catalyst), coal/carbon oxidation and catalytic oxidation of hydrogen (with noble metal catalysts such as platinum or palladium). Oxygen can also be removed through cryogenic distillation and chemisorption on copper, forming copper oxides. Literature indicates that catalytic oxidation of hydrogen is the most promising method due to its high removal efficiency, optimal operating temperature (80 °C), low energy consumption, and safety. Cryogenic distillation and catalytic oxidation of methanol follow, despite their high energy requirements and challenging temperatures (-56.6°C and 320°C respectively), due to their effective removal and safety profiles. Chemisorption on copper and catalytic oxidation of propane, while effective, are more costly and require stringent operational conditions. Catalytic oxidation of carbon monoxide and coal oxidation rank lowest due to safety issues, particularly the toxicity associated with CO (Abbas, et al., 2013).

Regarding SO₂ removal, several widely used large-scale emission control processes are available for flue gas streams: wet flue gas desulfurization (WFGD), dry sorbent injection (DSI) using solid sorbents and various hybrid semi-wet and semi-dry techniques. WFGD is currently the most prevalent technology for SO₂ removal from industrial emissions due to its high efficiency and reliability. It utilizes alkaline chemical reagents such as limestone and lime (used in approximately 80% of WFGD systems), ammonia or sodium hydroxide, in order to convert SO₂ into liquid or solid

byproducts like gypsum. WFGD is favored for its high removal efficiency (up to 90%) and relatively low operating costs, although it faces challenges, including high capital costs, complex equipment, significant land use and potential secondary pollutant formation (Pasichnyk, et al., 2023), (Rezaei, et al., 2015).

On the other hand, dry sorbent injection involves injecting dry sorbents, often based on lime or limestone, into the flue gas to capture SO₂. Various adsorbents, including metal oxides, zeolites, calcium-based materials and activated carbon, have been tested, while more advanced materials such as metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) and supported amine adsorbents are gaining traction. DSI offers several advantages, including a lower environmental footprint, reduced water consumption (40% less than wet WFGD) and lower capital costs. Growing interest in optimizing DSI systems focuses on improving sorbent characteristics and regeneration conditions. Lastly, hybrid approaches (semi-dry and semi-wet desulfurization) combine features of both wet and dry methods (Pasichnyk, et al., 2023), (Rezaei, et al., 2015).

Finally, semi-dry desulfurization involves injecting a slurry or absorbent solution into the flue gas, followed by filtration, while semi-wet methods inject a dry sorbent with a limited amount of liquid to create a humid environment. These approaches reduce water usage and achieve higher SO₂ removal efficiencies compared to purely dry methods, offering flexible system designs suitable for varying plant needs and regulations (Pasichnyk, et al., 2023), (Rezaei, et al., 2015).

3.4 CO₂ FROM BIOGAS PRODUCTION AS FEEDSTOCK – PORT OF VALENCIA CASE STUDY

The value chain examined in the Valencia, Spain, case study differs from the previous one by incorporating biogenic CO₂ from a biogas plant integrated within wastewater treatment facilities. More specifically, the case study focuses on CO₂ emissions from two wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) operated by GOMSL near Valencia port: Pinedo WWTP, situated 1 km from the port of Valencia, and Quart Benàger WWTP, located approximately 10 km away from the port. Pinedo is the largest facility in the region, capable of treating wastewater for 1,038,889 population equivalents, with a treatment capacity of 333,501 m³/day, generating 65,277 tons of dry sludge annually. Quart Benàger WWTP treats wastewater for 156,988 population equivalents, handling a flow rate of 30,850 m³/day and producing 11,596 tons of dry sludge per year. Currently, both facilities utilize biogas in combined heat and power (CHP) engines and burn it in boilers, without upgrading it to biomethane. Pinedo produces 900 Nm³/h of biogas, while Quart Benàger generates 300 Nm³/h. The biogas mainly consists of 35% CO₂ and 65% CH₄, resulting in approximately 315 Nm³/h of CO₂ and 585 Nm³/h of CH₄ from the Pinedo plant, and 105 Nm³/h of CO₂ and 195 Nm³/h of CH₄ from the Quart Benàger plant. In the context of the value chain development of the POSEIDON project, additional CO₂ emissions could be captured from containerhips docking at the port of Valencia.

Although biogas produced from the GOMSL WWTP will serve as feedstock for the ICODOS MeOH synthesis plant without additional treatment, the following sections will explore all steps involved in biogas and raw CO₂ production and treatment to provide a comprehensive overview, as these stages impact the economic, environmental and other aspects of the entire value chain. As shown in Figure 3.17, the value chain includes wet biomass sourcing, anaerobic digestion, digestate management, raw biogas purification, biogas upgrading, biomethane management and CO₂ purification. The

following chapters will examine the state-of-the-art technologies available for each step, highlighting their primary advantages and disadvantages in terms of technical configuration, efficiency and adaptability. At the end of the value chain, CO₂ emissions from biogas upgrading can either be captured through a pre-combustion carbon capture process or used directly at the MeOH synthesis facility.

Figure 3.17. Value chain of CO₂ from a biogas plant as feedstock for e-MeOH synthesis.

Biogas is a blend of methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂) and trace gases generated by the anaerobic digestion of organic matter in an oxygen-free environment. Its composition varies based on feedstock and production methods, which primarily include biodigesters, landfill gas recovery systems and wastewater treatment plants. Biodigesters are systems where organic materials mixed with water are broken down by microorganisms to produce biogas. Before further utilization, contaminants and moisture are typically removed from the produced biogas. In landfill gas recovery systems, biogas is produced from the anaerobic decomposition of municipal solid waste (MSW) at landfills, and it is captured through pipes and extraction wells, using compressors to direct it to a central collection point. Lastly, wastewater treatment facilities, which are the subject of the Valencia case study, can recover organic matter and nutrients from sewage sludge. This material can then be treated in anaerobic digesters to produce biogas (IEA, 2020).

Biogas typically contains 45% to 75% methane by volume, with CO₂ making up most of the remainder. The lower heating value (LHV) of biogas ranges from 16 to 28 MJ/m³. Figure 3.18 illustrates biogas consumption by end-use sector in 2018. As depicted, biogas can be used directly for power generation (electricity), heating buildings or industrial facilities or for co-generation of electric and thermal energy. Furthermore, biogas can be upgraded to biomethane. The upgrading process focuses on the removal of CO₂ to separate the biomethane stream, which contains more than 95% methane. Biomethane, or renewable natural gas, is a nearly pure methane source produced by upgrading biogas or through the gasification of solid biomass followed by methanation. Biogas upgrading accounts for about 90% of global biomethane production and utilizes the different properties of gases in biogas to separate them, with water scrubbing and membrane separation representing nearly 60% of this process worldwide. Biomethane has an LHV of approximately 36 MJ/m³ and is chemically identical to natural gas. Therefore, it can be used without modifications to existing transmission and distribution infrastructure or end-user equipment, making it fully compatible with natural gas vehicles (IEA, 2020).

Figure 3.18. Biogas consumption by end use in 2018 (IEA, 2020).

3.4.1 WET BIOMASS AND ANAEROBIC DIGESTION

3.4.1.1 WET BIOMASS SOURCES

Anaerobic Digestion (AD) can be used to process a wide variety of biodegradable organic materials. As shown in Table 9, common AD feedstocks include biodegradable wastes that fall into one of three main categories: agricultural waste including livestock manure and crop residues, industrial waste including food processing waste, dairy product and agro-processing waste, and municipal waste including the Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste (OFMSW), sewage sludge and food waste from restaurants, supermarkets etc. (Uddin & Wright, 2022). The characteristics and composition of the feedstock are crucial to the efficiency of AD and biogas production. Feedstocks rich in highly biodegradable organic matter, with well-balanced macro- and micro-nutrients, promote microbial growth and enhance biogas yields. Key factors such as particle size, total solids (TS), moisture content and volatile solids (VS) must also be evaluated to optimize the digestion process (Dhull, et al., 2023).

Table 9. Common anaerobic digestion feedstocks grouped by waste category (Uddin & Wright, 2022).

CATEGORY	SOURCE
Agricultural waste	Livestock manure
	Energy crops
	Harvest remains
	Farm mortality
Industrial waste	Food/Beverage processing
	Pharmaceutical industry
	Slaughterhouse waste
	Dairy product waste
	Agro-processing residues
Municipal waste	Organic fraction of MSW (OFMSW)
	Sewage sludge
	Yard trimmings
	Food waste from restaurants/cafeteria
	Supermarket waste

AD biomass feedstock can be either wet or dry. Regarding wet digesters, the moisture content exceeds 85% vol. and they are the most commonly used for feedstocks. In this system, mechanical stirring prevents solid precipitation and the substrate is continuously fed and removed after a set hydraulic retention time (HRT). Wet digestion is particularly suitable for high-moisture feedstocks like sewage sludge and animal manure, as reducing their moisture content would require significant energy. On the other hand, dry digesters are designed for solid-rich feedstocks with a higher solid content (above 15%). These materials, such as solid manure, biosolids from municipal waste, food waste, yard trimmings and energy crops, are stacked in sealed tanks where hot water or slurry is applied to maintain the required digestion temperature (Uddin & Wright, 2022).

Anaerobic digestion (AD) of wet wastes presents several challenges, including long start-up times, low biogas quality and unstable production. While AD can process a variety of feedstocks, each type has its own limitations that must be managed through careful selection, pretreatment and co-digestion strategies to ensure stable and efficient biogas production. Furthermore, feedstocks must be highly biodegradable and free of toxic components that could inhibit microbial activity. For

instance, sewage sludge contains organic contaminants (such as antibiotics) and inorganic substances (like heavy metals), along with microbial aggregates and extracellular polymeric substances (EPS). The EPS structure gives the sludge a gel-like composition that hinders cell rupture and lysis, reducing its dewaterability and biodegradability. Animal manure, another common AD feedstock, also has limitations, such as impurities like sand and gravel, low organic content, an imbalanced carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio and the low biodegradability of lignocellulosic fibers. Wet waste AD is often impacted by these types of contaminants, reducing process efficiency (Li, et al., 2022).

Furthermore, some materials, such as woody biomass or those with high lignin content, require pretreatment to improve their digestibility. While co-digestion or mixing multiple feedstocks can enhance biogas yields, certain combinations may negatively impact performance. For example, livestock manure is commonly used due to its availability and nutrient content. However, it generates lower biogas volumes as it is partially digested in the animal's gut. Despite this, manure is frequently co-digested with other substrates because of its favorable characteristics. Other feedstocks, such as sewage sludge and slaughterhouse waste, may contain harmful substances like antibiotics or heavy metals that need to be treated before digestion to protect anaerobic microbes (Uddin & Wright, 2022).

Food waste, due to its high organic content, is another promising feedstock for biogas production in AD. It typically includes spoiled food, fruit and vegetable peels, expired products, bread, dairy, grains and inedible parts like eggshells, bones and skins. Rich in fibers, sugars, fats, oils and carbohydrates, food waste is ideal for AD. Sources of food waste include kitchens, restaurants, food processing industries and farms. In industrialized nations, food waste is often driven by excessive purchasing and improper storage, leading to spoilage. This waste can be redirected to AD for energy recovery (Devi, et al., 2023). However, despite its potential, food waste also contains high levels of nitrogen and salts, particularly sodium, potassium, calcium and magnesium, which can inhibit the growth of anaerobic microbes, posing challenges for efficient AD (Li, et al., 2022).

3.4.1.2 ANAEROBIC DIGESTION TECHNOLOGIES

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a biological process in which bacteria decompose organic matter (called biopolymers) in the absence of free oxygen, resulting in the production of biogas - a gaseous mixture primarily composed of methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂), along with smaller amounts of hydrogen (H₂), hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) and other impurities (Devi, et al., 2023). AD has gained recognition as a widely adopted waste-to-energy (WtE) technology due to its environmental advantages, such as lower emissions of CO₂ and CH₄ compared to landfill disposal (Li, et al., 2022). This process typically takes place in a sealed vessel, which creates an anaerobic environment necessary for the survival of specific bacteria that thrive without oxygen. During AD, residual solids and organic matter remain in the vessel, collectively referred to as digestate. This digestate can be separated into liquid and solid fractions, both of which are nutrient-rich and can be used as fertilizers in agriculture (Uddin & Wright, 2022).

The biochemical AD reactions taking place during digestion can be divided into four distinct stages: hydrolysis, acidogenesis, acetogenesis and methanogenesis. As shown in Figure 3.19, during hydrolysis, the first step of anaerobic digestion (AD), biopolymers like complex lipids, proteins and carbohydrates are broken down into simpler monomers with the assistance of water and extracellular enzymes. This process involves specific hydrolases released by bacteria, which facilitate the

degradation of polymeric organic matter. For example, polysaccharides are converted into monosaccharides, while proteins yield peptides and amino acids. Key hydrolases include glycosidases for carbohydrates, esterases for lipids and peptidases for proteins. Some compounds from hydrolysis are ready for biogas conversion, but most require further degradation in subsequent AD stages. During the second stage of acidogenesis, acidogenic bacteria convert hydrolytic products into volatile fatty acids (VFAs) like acetic, propionic and formic acids, as well as alcohols and ketones. Byproducts such as CO₂, H₂, and NH₃ are also produced. This process occurs in an acidic environment where anaerobic bacteria thrive requiring energy input. While some compounds like acetate can be directly utilized by methanogens in the next stage, others need further decomposition. It is important to note that rapid acidogenesis can lead to the accumulation of VFAs, which may cause digester toxicity (Banerjee, et al., 2022), (Devi, et al., 2023), (Uddin & Wright, 2022).

Figure 3.19. Anaerobic digestion biomass decomposition stages (hydrolysis, acidogenesis, acetogenesis and methanogenesis) and key compounds (Uddin & Wright, 2022).

During the acetogenesis stage, acetogenic bacteria convert products from acidogenesis and long-chain fatty acids from hydrolysis into acetate, CO₂ and H₂. This stage is not thermodynamically spontaneous if the partial pressure of H₂ exceeds 10⁻⁴ atm. Methanogenic bacteria help lower this pressure by consuming H₂, establishing a syntrophic relationship that makes acetogenesis thermodynamically feasible. This interspecies H₂-transfer acts as an electron transfer, significantly impacting the overall digestion rate. Thus, acetogenesis plays a crucial role in further breaking down volatile acids into acetates and acetic acid (Uddin & Wright, 2022). Finally, during methanogenesis, methanogenic microorganisms convert intermediates like acetic acid, hydrogen and carbon dioxide into methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). This strictly anaerobic process involves two main groups of archaea: acetoclastic bacteria, which transform acetate into methane and carbon dioxide, and hydrogenotrophic bacteria, which use hydrogen and carbon dioxide to produce methane (Banerjee, et al., 2022), (Devi, et al., 2023).

As noticed above, anaerobic digestion (AD) is significantly affected by operating strategies and process parameters, as the process involves several stages of biochemical reactions that are influenced by multiple factors and conditions. As analyzed below, the efficiency of biogas production depends on parameters such as particle size, temperature, pH, hydraulic retention time (HRT), carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio and nutrient balance. By optimizing these key parameters anaerobic digestion can achieve more efficient and stable biogas production. Each parameter interacts with the microbial processes at different stages of digestion, influencing overall system performance (Banerjee, et al., 2022), (Rajeshwari, et al., 2000).

- **Substrate particle size:** Reducing the size of substrate particles through pretreatment enhances biogas generation by increasing the surface area available for microbial action. Smaller particles improve feedstock biodegradability, speeding up the digestion process by methanogens. Conversely, larger particles can clog the digester disrupting the process (Banerjee, et al., 2022).
- **Hydraulic Retention Time (HRT):** HRT represents the time that the sludge remains in the AD reactor, enabling microorganisms to degrade organic matter and produce biogas. If the HRT is too short, incomplete degradation occurs, reducing biogas yield and potentially causing microorganism washout, which disrupts the process. The typical HRT range is 16-25 days (Bachmann, 2015).
- **Temperature:** Temperature significantly affects anaerobic digestion, which can be categorized as psychrophilic (0-20°C), mesophilic (20-42°C) and thermophilic (42-75°C). Each range corresponds to the optimal growth temperature for different species of microorganisms with anaerobic bacteria being the most active microorganisms in the mesophilic and thermophilic ranges. Most systems operate within the mesophilic range (37-43°C). While anaerobic bacteria are generally resistant to temperature changes, significant drops in temperature can slow bacterial activity, halving growth for every 10°C below 35°C. Low temperatures can be used to preserve anaerobic sludge for long periods without much loss of activity, which is particularly useful for seasonal wastewater treatment (Rajeshwari, et al., 2000).
- **pH:** The pH of an anaerobic system is critical, with an optimal range of 6.8-7.2 for methane-producing bacteria and a more acidic range favoring acid-forming bacteria. Maintaining a balanced pH is crucial to prevent volatile fatty acid (VFA) accumulation and thus the formation of localized acid zones in the digester, which can disrupt methanogenesis. Buffer capacity, often provided by sodium bicarbonate, helps neutralize acids and stabilize the process without

disturbing the microbial community (Rajeshwari, et al., 2000), (Banerjee, et al., 2022).

- **Carbon/Nitrogen (C/N) ratio:** The C/N ratio is a key factor for efficient anaerobic digestion, with an optimal range between 20:1 and 30:1. Carbon provides energy for microbes, while nitrogen supports microbial growth because it is used by methanogenic bacteria to meet their protein requirements. For too high C/N ratios, the bacteria utilize nitrogen quickly while the extra carbon in the feedstock is not able to react resulting in the reduction of the biogas yield. In contrast, if the C/N ratios is too low, excess nitrogen leads to ammonia buildup, which increases pH over 8.5 and inhibits bacterial activity, ultimately lowering gas production (Banerjee, et al., 2022).
- **Nutrients:** Micronutrients and trace elements, including nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, calcium, iron and others, are essential for microbial growth and reactor stability, especially in upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactors. Methanogenic bacteria specifically require iron, nickel and cobalt, which may need supplementation in wastewater streams lacking these elements, such as those from certain agro-industrial processes. Nutrient concentrations should be adjusted to ensure there is a slight excess for efficient microbial activity (Rajeshwari, et al., 2000).

Optimal biogas production also relies on selecting the appropriate anaerobic digester (AD) system for each application. Several standard reactor designs are available and the choice depends on key factors such as feedstock composition, environmental temperature and microbial requirements. Digesters are typically classified as either batch or continuous and as mixing or non-mixing systems. In batch digesters, feedstock is added at the start and left to digest for a set period before being emptied, making them simple to operate but resulting in intermittent biogas production. Continuous digesters, on the other hand, allow for the constant addition of feedstock, leading to steady biogas production with minimal downtime, making them more efficient. Additionally, mixing of biomass is essential to prevent dead spots, ensure uniform conditions and avoid the buildup of toxic compounds. Common mixing methods include mechanical agitation, biogas recirculation and the use of pumps. While mixing increases system complexity and costs, it significantly boosts biogas production, often offsetting the additional expense (Uddin & Wright, 2022). Some of the most widely used reactor designs include plug-flow digesters, fixed film digesters, anaerobic sequencing batch reactors (ASBR), tubular reactors, baffled digesters, upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactors, anaerobic membrane bio-reactors (AnMBR), open digestion chamber reactors, complete mix (CSTR) reactors, as well as hybrid biological reactors (HBR) and anaerobic biotrickling filters (Banerjee, et al., 2022), (Rajeshwari, et al., 2000).

Two of the most widely adopted ways to effectively improve AD performance has been proven to be co-digestion with other biomass sources. Co-digestion refers to the simultaneous anaerobic digestion of multiple organic waste types in a single digester in order to enhance methane production by combining low-yielding or hard-to-digest materials with organic-rich waste (e.g. food waste). Compared to single-substrate digestion, co-digestion offers various technological, ecological and economic benefits, including improved nutrient balance and dilution of inhibitors. Co-digestion can address issues related to low nitrogen/carbon (C/N) ratios in primary substrates, which can lead to elevated ammonia levels in the digestion system. Careful selection of feedstock combinations is essential to optimize digestion efficiency (Devi, et al., 2023).

Pretreatment of wet biomass before anaerobic digestion can also significantly improve its performance. More specifically, the pretreatment process is crucial for enhancing the hydrolysis

process, which is often a rate-limiting step. The need for pretreatment arises due to challenges like slow microbial activity and the production of inhibitory compounds such as ammonia, heavy metals, and sulfur, all of which reduce biogas yield. Various methods such as chemical, mechanical, thermal, biological and also electrical, ultrasound and magnetic pretreatments are used. These techniques reduce particle size and increase the solubility of organic components, accelerating the digestion process and reducing retention time. Effective pretreatment improves the biodegradability of substrates and increases methane production in biogas while preserving the organic compounds and being environmentally and economically viable (Devi, et al., 2023), (Dhull, et al., 2023).

Further advancements in AD technology include the use of two-stage digesters, which separate the acidogenic and methanogenic stages, optimize conditions for each bacterial group, improving overall performance. Moreover, process monitoring, including real-time tracking of volatile fatty acids (VFA), helps maintain stability. To address process instability, nutrient supplements are often added, and emerging additives like biochar help counteract inhibitory elements, enhance buffering capacity and promote syntrophic metabolism. Although the exact role of biochar is still under research, its positive effects on AD performance are well documented, along with similar additives like charcoal and zeolite. However, excessive dosages of these materials can be detrimental (Dhull, et al., 2023).

3.4.2 DIGESTATE MANAGEMENT

Depending on the feedstock and system design, approximately one-third of the solid organic matter in the anaerobic digestion feeding sludge is converted into biogas, resulting in a highly liquid digested product sludge known as digestate. Digestate is a nutrient-rich slurry that constitutes 90-95% of the AD input materials and can contain high concentrations of macro- and micro-nutrients (Lamolinara, et al., 2022). Effective digestate management is critical for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and supporting a circular economy by promoting the sustainable use of biowaste. Selecting the appropriate digestate management method depends on the characteristics of the feedstock, regulatory requirements and available resources (Chojnacka & Moustakas, 2024).

After leaving the anaerobic digester, the digestate usually requires additional thickening. Depending on its intended use, the sludge is then pressed, centrifuged or heat-dried to separate and partition the solid and liquid fraction with different nutrient profiles. Phase separation of digestates tends to concentrate nutrients into the liquid fraction and the organic matter into the solid fraction, but the mass balances are highly dependent on the separation technique whose choice depends on digestate characteristics thus AD input type (Guilayn, et al., 2020). Research indicates that the solid fraction contains a significant fraction of the primary digestate's nitrogen (~85%) and phosphorus (~70%). Phosphorus in the solid fraction is largely released from organic matter and precipitated as phosphates of calcium, magnesium and iron. The liquid fraction is rich in potassium ions and organic nitrogen in the form of ammonium (Chojnacka & Moustakas, 2024).

The valorization of digestates into value-added products can be separated into three great categories: agriculture, energy and other industrial valorization. Although direct landspreading of anaerobic digestates is the most common digestate management strategy, ensuring high-quality digestate that aligns with the specific nutrient requirements of crops to prevent nutrient overload and ensure successful growth, is essential to mitigate potential adverse effects on soil, crops and the environment. Thus, ongoing research and innovation in both quality standardization methods and in post-processing technologies is crucial to fully harness the potential of digestate for nutrient recovery

and environmental sustainability (Lamolinara, et al., 2022), (Guilayn, et al., 2020). As shown in Figure 3.20, various processing techniques are available, including thermal processes (such as pyrolysis, incineration and hydrothermal carbonisation), chemical treatments (like alkaline hydrolysis and ozonation) and also processes like combustion, co-composting, drying, integrated biorefineries and nutrient recovery, offering multiple advantages for managing the solid and liquid fraction of anaerobic digestate. These methods can reduce volatile fatty acids (VFAs), enhance nutrient bioavailability and sanitize the digestate, making it safe for use (Chojnacka & Moustakas, 2024).

Figure 3.20. Digestate management and processing for different end-use cases (Chojnacka & Moustakas, 2024).

Agricultural valorization of digestates can be classified into three product categories: N/P/K fertilizers, soil improvers and organo-mineral fertilizers. For the liquid fraction, membrane filtration, evaporation, nitrogen stripping and phosphorus precipitation are feasible and full-scale methods that can yield value-added products. For the solid fraction, composting and co-composting are widely used as cost-effective methods that stabilize digestate, reduce volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and produce high-quality organic fertilizer with minimal heavy metals and pathogens. Composting is an aerobic process that decomposes the biodegradable fraction of the organic matter into CO₂ and microbial biomass (Guilayn, et al., 2020), (Chojnacka & Moustakas, 2024).

Regarding energy valorization, thermal conversion or fermentation processes enable both the liquid and solid fraction to be converted to syngas, biofuels and heat. Thermal conversion processes are typically categorized into combustion, pyrolysis, and gasification. Additional variants include torrefaction, hydrothermal carbonisation, vapothermal carbonisation and hydrothermal liquefaction. All these processes operate on the same fundamental principle: inducing an irreversible thermal decomposition of organic matter, which is then followed by various reorganization reactions (Guilayn, et al., 2020).

Various alternatives beyond agriculture and energy exist for valorizing AD digestates industrially: reuse water, produce animal feed products and biopesticides, produce adsorbents such as biochar and other engineered materials such as bioplastics, flame retardants (struvite or ammonium sulfate)

and functional landfill cover layers. Among these, biochar appears to be the only fully developed product with potential industrial applications. However, no instances of digestates being marketed as biochar have been identified. Another promising approach is the use of humic-like substances as biosurfactants, although this remains in development or demonstration stages (Guilayn, et al., 2020). In each case, efficient logistics for storing, mobilizing and processing digestate are vital for optimizing nutrient recycling and controlling nutrient runoff to water bodies. By implementing robust logistics and management practices, the benefits of digestate as a sustainable agricultural resource can be maximized while minimizing environmental impacts (Lamolinara, et al., 2022).

3.4.3 BIOGAS PURIFICATION

Typically, the raw biogas exiting the AD process contains methane (40-75 vol.%) and carbon dioxide (15-60 vol.%), as well as other trace compounds including hydrogen sulphide (<2 vol.%), water (1–10 vol.%), nitrogen (0–8 vol.%), ammonia (<1 vol.%), oxygen (<1 vol.%), carbon monoxide (<0.6 vol.%) and siloxanes (<0.02 vol.%). In order to inject biogas to the energy grid, use it as a fuel or otherwise, it is essential to remove the harmful and damaging impurities it may contain through biogas cleaning and purification as well as inert gases such as CO₂ through biogas upgrading. Cleaning and upgrading are usually carried out separately using multi-stage technologies, although sometimes, they are accomplished simultaneously for certain pollutants. The most widely adopted upgrading technologies are presented in detail in Section 3.4.4 (Struk, et al., 2020), (Awe, et al., 2017).

Biogas from digesters is always saturated with water, with its content being dependent on temperature (typically 5% at 35°C). Water can be removed by either physical or chemical methods. Physical drying methods through condensation processes include demisters, cyclone separators, moisture traps and water traps. While these methods reduce water content, they are less efficient, lowering the dew point to only around 0.5°C, which may cause operational issues like freezing on heat exchangers. Chemical drying involves water absorption by agents like glycol, which reduces the dew point to between -5 and -15°C, and can be regenerated at high temperatures. Other agents, such as silica gel, activated carbon and alumina, can reduce the dew point further down to -40°C under high pressure. For continuous drying, two columns packed with drying agents are used, one for drying and the other for regeneration. Hygroscopic salts can also be used to absorb water but must be replaced once saturated (Awe, et al., 2017).

Besides CO₂ and water, hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) and other sulfur-containing compounds, such as mercaptans (organic thiol compounds), are the primary contaminants found in biogas. These compounds are formed during the microbiological reduction of compounds that contain sulfur and, as a result, their concentration is largely influenced by the organic matter composition, particularly protein-rich materials. These compounds must be eliminated before biogas utilization because they are highly corrosive to pipes, pumps and engines and pose environmental risks through their conversion into sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). Hydrogen sulphide is also harmful to humans, with lethal H₂S concentrations in the air starting at 500 ppm. Similarly, siloxanes form microcrystalline silica compounds and ammonia (NH₃) are both corrosive when combusted, while NH₃ can convert to nitrogen oxides (NO_x), contributing to greenhouse gas emissions and environmental pollution (Struk, et al., 2020), (Awe, et al., 2017).

Focusing on H₂S removing, current methods used include in situ precipitation, adsorption (using iron oxides, hydroxides or activated carbon), physical and chemical absorption, membrane separation,

biofiltration, in situ microaerobic removal, microalgae-based removal and combined (hybrid) biological methods. Emerging technologies for H₂S removal include FlashH₂S and a novel electrochemical process (López , et al., 2024). In physical and chemical absorption, conventional gas-liquid contactors utilize water, organic solvents or aqueous chemical solutions to convert H₂S into elemental sulfur or metal sulfides using agents such as Selexol, which offers a compact solution for low H₂S concentrations, and Iron-chelated solutions such as Fe³⁺/EDTA, with removal rates of 90-100% for H₂S and some mercaptans, without significantly affecting CO₂ concentration. These solutions can be regenerated by oxygenation, reducing chemical consumption and operational costs (Ahmed, et al., 2021).

Membrane separation capitalizes on selective permeability to efficiently remove H₂S from biogas, often achieving up to 98% removal rates. Adsorption techniques employ materials like activated carbon, iron oxides or hydroxides to bind H₂S, enhancing effectiveness through chemical impregnation and biological desulfurization employs specialized microorganisms that oxidize H₂S into elemental sulfur and sulfates, often using air or oxygen as electron acceptors. Alternatively, in situ dosing iron chloride in the digester can facilitate the formation of insoluble iron sulfide (FeS), which can be removed with the digested solids. Additionally, injecting air into the biogas system (in situ) can reduce H₂S concentrations significantly but poses safety risks due to potential explosiveness (Ahmed, et al., 2021).

Oxygen and nitrogen are typically absent in a properly conducted anaerobic digestion (AD) process. Those impurities vary depending on the substrate and digestion conditions and they can be removed through adsorption or membrane separation. Ammonia can be eliminated through gas cooling, compression, adsorption or absorption while siloxanes and volatile methylsiloxanes are removed using commercially available methods like adsorption, absorption, cryogenic separation or biological methods that are still in preliminary research. Finally, solid particles that may exist in biogas are filtered mechanically or removed via wet dedusting systems like electrostatic precipitators and wet scrubbers (López , et al., 2024).

3.4.4 BIOGAS UPGRADE

Biogas upgrade is the process in which carbon dioxide can be separated from the purified biogas stream. It is primarily adapted from the gas refining industry, utilizing separation and sorption techniques to exploit the chemical, physical and biological properties of gas components (Ahmed, et al., 2021). Figure 3.21 shows a summary of biological and physicochemical methods used for biogas upgrading including pressure and vacuum swing adsorption, water and organic physical scrubbing, chemical absorption, membrane, cryogenic separation and biofiltering. As shown in Figure 3.22, physical and chemical methods and especially water and chemical scrubbing as well as membrane separation, are the most commonly used for biogas upgrading, although they still require a high amount of energy and chemicals. Their primary scope is the separation of CO₂ from biogas although, as mentioned above, they can also achieve purification and cleaning from other impurities such as H₂S, NH₃, N₂, O₂ and water (moisture). Perspective alternatives are biological methods utilizing microbial consortia being more competitive in terms of chemical or energy requirements (Struk, et al., 2020), (Gkotsis, et al., 2023)

Figure 3.21. Summary of physico-chemical and biological methods for biogas upgrading (Struk, et al., 2020).

Figure 3.22. Distribution of biogas upgrading technologies, from 554 facilities in the member countries of International Energy Agency (Gkotsis, et al., 2023).

Pressure swing adsorption (PSA) is a widely-used method for biogas upgrading, relying on the selective adsorption of carbon dioxide (CO₂) over methane (CH₄) due to their molecular size differences. The adsorbent characteristics are the most crucial determinant of PSA efficiency. Adsorption occurs in vertical columns packed with materials like activated carbon, silica gel or zeolites, where CO₂, nitrogen (N₂), oxygen (O₂) and hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) are captured, while CH₄ passes through. The process involves four key stages: adsorption, depressurization, desorption and pressurization. To ensure continuous operation, multiple columns are used, and after saturation, the adsorbent undergoes regeneration by depressurization or vacuum (for Vacuum Swing Adsorption).

Adsorption processes do not require any supplementary expenses for thermal regeneration or water supply. Recent advancements have improved PSA systems through technology optimization, such as using amine-containing nanogel particles and honeycomb-shaped carbon fiber supports, which have reduced operational costs and increased CO₂ recovery. Additionally, 3D-printed sorbents show promise for enhancing adsorption and desorption rates, though more improvements are needed (Struk, et al., 2020).

PSA can achieve biomethane purity of 95-99%, but up to 4% of methane may be lost. PSA units operate under pressures of 3 to 8 bars and temperatures around 50-60°C. The regeneration phase occurs at pressures as low as 0.1 to 0.2 bars, and several industrial technologies have been patented for improved efficiency and cost-effectiveness (Gkotsis, et al., 2023). Desulfurization is crucial in PSA systems to remove H₂S before biogas enters the columns, as H₂S can irreversibly adsorb onto the material, causing the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent to reduce. Similarly, vacuum swing adsorption (VSA) and temperature swing adsorption (TSA) are alternatives. Although temperature swing adsorption (TSA) can also be used, it has a longer regeneration time compared to PSA. Despite these differences, PSA remains preferred due to its simplicity, high gas quality, low energy requirements and minimal methane loss (Devi, et al., 2023).

Water scrubbing is a popular method for upgrading biogas due to its simplicity, environmental benefits and effectiveness in removing acidic components like CO₂ and H₂S. This process leverages the differing solubility levels of biogas components in water. Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) is the most water-soluble component in biogas, followed by CO₂. However, H₂S is an environmentally harmful and toxic gas. When combined with water, it becomes corrosive and emits a foul odor. For this reason, H₂S is typically removed from biogas before water scrubbing if its concentration exceeds 300 to 2500 ppmv. Following this, CO₂ dissolves 26 times more than nonpolar hydrocarbons such as CH₄. According to Henry's Law, CO₂'s solubility in water at 25°C is about 26 times greater than that of CH₄. High-pressure water scrubbing (HPWS) and organic physical solvents (OPS) are employed to absorb CO₂ while minimizing CH₄ losses (typically 2-4%). This makes the method suitable for high acid gas concentrations due to the noncorrosive properties of physical solvents (Awe, et al., 2017), (Aghel, et al., 2022).

During water scrubbing, biogas enters the absorption column from the bottom, while water flows counter-currently from the top, optimizing contact for enhanced CO₂ removal. Following absorption, water-saturated biomethane is collected from the top of the column, while the CO₂- and H₂S-laden water is decompressed in a desorption column to release CO₂ and H₂S, allowing the water to be purified and reused for scrubbing. While water scrubbing can achieve approximately 97% CH₄ recovery, allowing for the simultaneous removal of both CO₂ and H₂S, it does require significant water volumes and incurs energy costs for gas compression and air stripping. Despite these factors, this technology is highly environmentally friendly and enables efficient biomethane upgrading without the use of hazardous chemicals. Additionally, CO₂ removal efficiency is influenced by gas-liquid ratios and pressure, with increased pressure and temperature improving purification but potentially raising CH₄ losses. Techniques like vacuum and ultrasound can further enhance CO₂ stripping efficiency, making water scrubbing an effective option for biogas upgrading (Aghel, et al., 2022), (Awe, et al., 2017).

Following identical fundamentals, organic solvent scrubbing technology efficiently removes CO₂ and H₂S from biogas using dimethyl ethers of polyethylene glycol-based liquid absorbents, such as Selexol® or Genosorb®. These solvents have a higher binding capacity, allowing for a more compact

system with less solvent required and minimal loss due to low vapor pressure. The process typically operates at higher flow rates of (500-2000 Nm³/h), cooling biogas and absorbents to 20°C before compressing them to 7-8 bar. It effectively removes moisture, O₂, N₂ and trace halogenated hydrocarbons, eliminating the need for additional drying. Despite its advantages, organic solvent scrubbing only represents 6% of the global biogas upgrading market, achieving CH₄ recovery rates of 96-98.5% while maintaining losses below 2%. Challenges in solvent regeneration arise due to the high solubility of biogas components, requiring more energy and heating. While this technology offers higher efficiency, it involves greater energy demands and higher costs for the solvents compared to water scrubbing (Ahmed, et al., 2021).

Chemical scrubbing, similar to water and organic scrubbing, operates on a counter-current flow principle for biogas-liquid mass transfer, utilizing absorbents like alkanol amines or aqueous lime solutions with a high affinity for CO₂. This technology is particularly effective for medium biogas flow rates (500-1000 Nm³/h) and excels when CO₂ concentrations are low. A notable advantage is the formation of intermediate compounds during the absorption process, enhancing CO₂ solubility and allowing for more compact upgrading facilities. Chemical scrubbing typically employs a combined absorption and stripping column setup, where heat is applied at temperatures of 120-160°C to facilitate solvent regeneration. While this technology can achieve CH₄ recovery rates exceeding 99.5%, its adoption is limited due to high energy demands for solvent regeneration and potential operational challenges, such as amine degradation and foaming. Though capable of managing H₂S concentrations up to 300 ppmv, pre-removal using activated carbon filters is advisable to minimize energy consumption during desorption. Despite these drawbacks, chemical scrubbing's efficiency and ability to operate at low pressures make it a viable option for biogas upgrading, although it currently captures only 22% of the global market share (Ahmed, et al., 2021).

An alternative to traditional absorption systems for biogas upgrading is membrane technology, which typically employs polymeric materials like cellulose acetate or polyimides due to their lower cost, ease of production and stability under high pressure. During membrane separation, smaller and/or polar molecules such as CO₂, H₂S, H₂O and O₂ diffuse through the membrane materials faster, showing higher permeation rates, while larger molecules such as CH₄ and N₂ are largely retained. Its efficiency is evaluated based on the membrane's capacity to improve, prevent or regulate permeation. The key factors influencing membrane separation technology are operating temperature and pressure, followed by sorption and diffusion coefficients, molecular size, electric charge, concentration differences and the type of membrane construction material (Struk, et al., 2020), (Awe, et al., 2017).

Membrane separation technology is used in two main modes: (1) gas-gas units under high pressure, and (2) gas-liquid units under low pressure. In the gas-gas method, biogas is compressed at 20-40 bar to liquid state, resulting in biomethane-rich retentate, achieving up to 97% purity. However, the methane recovery rate is lower due to the loss of CH₄ under high pressure. Multistage setups can improve CH₄ recovery from 80% to 99.5%. On the other hand, hybrid methods with gas-liquid units based on membrane contactors operate at atmospheric pressure, using a microporous membrane to separate biogas from CO₂ with amine-based solutions as efficient absorbents, which can be regenerated through heating. Due to lower working pressure, this method has lower operational costs compared to gas-gas systems. Pre-conditioning of raw biogas by removing impurities such as H₂O, H₂S, NH₃ and siloxanes via activated carbon filtration and compression is strongly recommended to avoid system failures. The main costs associated with membrane separation involve replacing activated carbon filters, membranes (with lifespans of 5-10 years), and pre-

compression of the biogas. Despite these costs, membrane separation is easy to install and operate and well-suited for low gas flow rates, although membrane replacement is required every 1 to 5 years (Awe, et al., 2017).

The cryogenic separation method is a promising technique for upgrading biogas by utilizing temperature differences to separate gases. Carbon dioxide can be liquefied under specific pressure and temperature conditions, while methane remains in gaseous form due to its significantly lower boiling point of -161.5°C compared to CO_2 's -78.2°C . This method involves initially removing moisture, H_2S and other impurities from raw biogas to prevent operational issues such as freezing in pipes and heat exchangers. The biogas is then compressed and gradually cooled to achieve a state where pure CO_2 and CH_4 can be separated efficiently (Awe, et al., 2017), (Gkotsis, et al., 2023).

During the cryogenic process, biogas is first compressed to around 10 bars and then cooled to -25°C , followed by further cooling to -55°C to liquefy CO_2 , which is subsequently removed from the gas mixture. The remaining gas stream is cooled to approximately -85°C , causing residual CO_2 to solidify and allowing for its removal. Ultimately, the purified gas can be depressurized for use in various applications, achieving high biomethane purity levels exceeding 97% with minimal methane loss (less than 2%). Despite its effectiveness, cryogenic separation has drawbacks, including high energy requirements and significant operational and investment costs due to the complex equipment involved, such as compressors, turbines, and heat exchangers. Nevertheless, its ability to produce high-quality biomethane makes it an attractive option for biogas upgrading, especially in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and substituting fossil fuels. As the technology matures, it is expected that production costs will decrease, making it more accessible for broader applications (Devi, et al., 2023), (Gkotsis, et al., 2023).

Finally, biological processes offer a sustainable alternative to chemical methods for upgrading biogas by leveraging microorganisms that can convert CO_2 into valuable products, thereby addressing environmental concerns related to CO_2 emissions. This approach utilizes hydrogen (H_2) to facilitate the conversion of CO_2 into CH_4 . The biological CO_2 fixation process can occur through ex situ or in situ methods. In ex situ upgrading, H_2 and CO_2 are combined in a separate reactor with hydrogenotrophic methanogenic archaea, which utilize CO_2 as a carbon source and H_2 as a reducing agent to generate CH_4 . Conversely, in situ upgrading involves injecting H_2 directly into an anaerobic digester, where it interacts with endogenous CO_2 to produce CH_4 via the activity of native methanogenic archaea. This method incorporates a recycling system that sends liquid slime from the digester to a desorption column, enhancing CO_2 retention. While this cost-effective technology is beneficial for small-scale biogas plants, it typically does not meet the stringent methane purity standards of larger facilities (Aghel, et al., 2022).

3.4.4.1 COMPARATIVE CHART FOR BIOGAS UPGRADE TECHNOLOGIES

Table 10. Comparative chart for biogas upgrade technologies (Ahmed, et al., 2021), (Aghel, et al., 2022), (Gkotsis, et al., 2023), (Struk, et al., 2020).

UPGRADE PROCESS	ENERGY CONSUMPTION (CLEAN BIOGAS)	MAIN FEATURES & ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES & LIMITATIONS
Pressure Swing Adsorption	0.3-0.9 kWh/Nm ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highly efficient CH₄ recovery (95–99%). Possible H₂S, N₂, O₂ and moisture removal. Clean and water-free biomethane produced. Tolerant to impurities. Compact equipment and fast installation. Fast adsorbent regeneration. Suitable for small capacities as well. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High CH₄ losses (>4%). Difficulty in H₂S removal from adsorbent through regeneration, prior elimination is preferable. Susceptible to fouling by impurities. Off-gas (containing CO₂, H₂S and other impurities after regeneration) needs further treatment. High capital and operational costs. Complicated process control.
Membrane separation	0.14-0.26 kWh/Nm ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highly efficient CH₄ recovery (96–98% in multi-stage systems). Low CH₄ losses (<0.6%). Possible H₂S, N₂ and O₂ removal. Relatively low capital investment and operation costs due to simple system design. Easy maintenance without any chemical requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-removal of H₂S and H₂O is strongly recommended. Trade-off between the purity of CH₄ and quantity of biomethane due to limited selectivity of membranes. Not appropriate for high-purity requirements. Multiple modules are required for high purity. High membrane cost and need to be replaced within 5-10 years. High electricity consumption due to high working pressure.

UPGRADE PROCESS	ENERGY CONSUMPTION (CLEAN BIOGAS)	MAIN FEATURES & ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES & LIMITATIONS
Water scrubbing	0.3-0.9 kWh/Nm ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High CH₄ recovery efficiency (96-98%). • Both CO₂ and H₂S can be removed at once. • Losses of CH₄ are below 2%. • Not overly sensitive to impurities. • No requirement of chemicals. • Simple and not sophisticated system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High investment and operating costs. • Slow and less efficient process because of physical solubility. • High pressure is needed for compressing biogas and high energy need for water circulation. • Potential clogging due to bacterial growth. • Risk of foaming resulting corrosion due to H₂S.
Organic solvent scrubbing (Physical absorption)	0.4-0.6 kWh/Nm ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High CH₄ recovery efficiency (96-98%). • Low CH₄ losses: 2-4%. • More efficient than water scrubbing with less volume of solvent required due to high CO₂ solubility. • Concurrent separation of contaminants including H₂S. • Recovery of residual methane is possible by heating. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex process, expensive investment and operation. • High energy needs for solvent regeneration, especially if H₂S is not pre-separated. • Expensive solvent with difficult handling requirements. • Heating required for complete regeneration.
Chemical scrubbing (Chemical absorption)	0.05-0.25 kWh/Nm ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fast process with high CH₄ recovery (>99%). • Complete H₂S removal is possible. • Compression of raw biogas is not mandatory. • Low operational cost, easier regeneration of the solvent. • High CO₂ selectivity with minimal CH₄ losses (<0.1%). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High investment cost and high energy requirement for regeneration (energy-intensive). • Possible reaction between O₂ and amines, subsequent breakdown and fouling of the amines. • Risk of brackish coagulation, foaming and corrosion. • Waste chemicals require additional treatment.

UPGRADE PROCESS	ENERGY CONSUMPTION (CLEAN BIOGAS)	MAIN FEATURES & ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES & LIMITATIONS
Cryogenic separation	0.42–1.5 kWh/Nm ³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up to 98% high-purity CH₄ recovery. • Production of liquid CH₄ with minimal additional energy required. • High-purity CO₂ recovery as a by-product which can be used for example as dry ice. • Very low CH₄ loss (2%). • Eco-friendly, no chemical and water usage is involved. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of various expensive process equipment (main cooler, heat exchanger, compressor). • Expensive operation and maintenance. • High pressure. • High energy requirements. • Contaminant such as H₂S and moisture pre-treatment and removal required. • Technically complex procedure.
Biological upgrading (Biological hydrogenation)	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High CH₄ recovery (>98%). • Isolation of both H₂S and CO₂ are possible. • Conversion of CO₂ to high value-added products. • Environment friendly. • No chemical requirements. • Minimal or no heating required. • No undesirable by-product or end-product development. • Low space requirement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Still in pilot scale, no reliable data on investment, operation and maintenance cost. • Presence of small amounts of N₂ and O₂ in treated biogas. • Need for large amounts of H₂. • Requirement of additional nutrients for bacterial growth. • Operational parameters, mainly pH should be regularly monitored and controlled.

3.4.5 BIOMETHANE MANAGEMENT

Biomethane is a highly flexible resource that can be used for a variety of applications, related to both energy production and biotechnology. Methane is the main component of natural gas (80-90%) and is also found in shale gas. Biomethane is chemically identical to fossil methane and is also called Renewable Natural Gas (RNG). After biomethane is produced, it can be either directly injected into the natural gas grid, or stored and sold as a final product. Biomethane storage can occur both above and below-ground. Above-ground storage involves tanks that can store either gaseous biomethane (e.g. spherical dry tanks, tubular tanks and cylindrical bottles) or liquefied biomethane (e.g. cryogenic tanks and bottles). Biomethane can also be stored within gas grids or through specific porous materials. Below-ground storage options include depleted oil and gas reservoirs, salt caverns, aquifers and even adapted above-ground storage devices placed underground. These subterranean options can store larger quantities of biomethane and are considered safer, making them suitable for large-scale applications (Budzianowski & Brodacka, 2017).

Similar to natural gas, biomethane is colorless and odorless, so it must be odorized before being injected into transmission or distribution grids for public safety. This process involves adding odorants like Tetra-Hydro Thiophene (THT) or Mercaptan blends such as Tert-Butyl Mercaptan (TBM) or Dimethyl Sulphide (DMS) to make the gas detectable by the human nose at one-fifth the lower explosive limit, ensuring safe consumption (YZ Systems, 2024).

Its end uses also include transportation fuel, cooking/heating fuel, industrial applications, electricity cogeneration and ancillary services for power, heat and gas supply (D'Adamo, et al., 2023). It is an efficient fuel due to its high energy content (56 kJ/g) and is used industrially to produce syngas, which can be converted into methanol or synthetic fuels (Bagi, et al., 2017). Biomethane can also provide a versatile and sustainable feedstock for producing chemicals, biopolymers and proteins, supporting a circular economy while reducing emissions. Methanotrophic bacteria metabolize methane using the enzyme methane monooxygenase (MMO), aiding in bioremediation by breaking down pollutants. Advances in genetic engineering have expanded their use in environmental cleanup and biomethane-based biorefineries, which convert biomethane into valuable fuels and chemicals. Biomethane serves as a platform for producing methanol, acids, epoxides and alcohols like lactic acid (for bioplastics) and farnesene (used in diesel and cosmetics). Biodiesel and biopolymers like extracellular polysaccharides (EPS) and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are also produced from biomethane, with applications in biodegradable packaging, pharmaceuticals and medical devices. These biorefinery products can reduce costs, boost revenue and lower greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to a circular economy. Additionally, single-cell protein from methanotrophs offers a sustainable feed or food source (Bagi, et al., 2017).

3.4.6 BIOGENIC CO₂ PURIFICATION TECHNOLOGIES

According to data from the GOMSL wastewater treatment plant, a member of the POSEIDON project consortium, the average concentration profile of the produced biogas mixture mainly consists of CH₄ (62.85% vol.), CO₂ (37% vol.), O₂ (0.15% vol.) and H₂S (150 ppm). As outlined in section 3.4.3 on biogas purification, impurities like O₂ and H₂S can be removed before upgrading the biogas. If trace amounts of these impurities persist in the CO₂ stream post-upgrading, additional purification steps for O₂ and H₂S can be implemented. Regarding oxygen removal, the available technologies for the

CO₂ stream are analyzed in Section 3.4.1. Technologies used for H₂S removal during biogas purification (presented in Section 3.4.3) such as physical and chemical absorption, membrane separation, biological treatment and amine absorption can also be applied at this stage ([Ahmed, et al., 2021](#)). Additionally, methanol synthesis plants commonly use guard beds (e.g. ZnO for sulfur removal) before synthesis reactors to protect the catalyst ([Dieterich, et al., 2020](#)).

4 E-METHANOL SYNTHESIS

4.1 METHANOL PRODUCTION ROUTES CLASSIFICATION

Methanol can be produced from concentrated carbon sources such as natural gas, coal, biomass, and captured carbon dioxide (CO₂) from industrial flue gases or direct air capture. As shown in Figure 4.1, various production routes have been developed at research or industrial scales. The carbon intensity of methanol production varies depending on the feedstock and associated emissions. High carbon intensity is linked to coal gasification and natural gas reforming without carbon capture, whereas low carbon intensity is associated with renewable sources like biomass or fossil fuels with carbon capture. Nevertheless, for economic reasons, methanol production mainly depends on fossil resources, with 65% produced via natural gas reforming (grey methanol) and 35% via coal gasification (brown methanol). As a result, methanol production significantly contributes to global CO₂ emissions, representing 10% of the chemical sector's total emissions. Only about 0.2% of methanol is sourced from renewable feedstocks (green methanol) (Nemmour, et al., 2023), (IRENA and Methanol Institute, 2021).

Figure 4.1. Principal methanol production routes (IRENA and Methanol Institute, 2021).

Conventional or grey methanol production in large scale plants from natural gas via the synthesis gas (or syngas, a gaseous mixture of carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂) and hydrogen (H₂)) route involves two key processes: (i) steam reforming of methane and (ii) methanol synthesis. Natural gas undergoes desulfurization to remove acid gases like SO₂ and H₂S, along with dehydration. It is then converted into syngas via the steam reforming process, adjusting the hydrogen-to-carbon (H/C) ratio to approximately 3.0. Steam reforming follows eq. (3) and (4) and is the most expensive step. Since it is strongly endothermic, it takes place under very high temperature (up to 900°C) and pressure (16-30 bar). This reaction results in a mixture of CO, CO₂ and H₂. Also, CO₂ may form through the water gas shift reaction based on eq. (5). This reaction is usually used to

adjust the CO₂/H₂ ratio in the feed for the methanol synthesis reaction (Azhari, et al., 2022), (IRENA and Methanol Institute, 2021).

The resulting synthesis gas is compressed and directed into the synthesis reactor for methanol production. The synthesis occurs via the hydrogenation of CO and CO₂ (based on eq. (6) and (7)) using Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃-type heterogeneous catalysts under high temperature (200-300°C) and pressure (50-100 bar). Finally, a distillation unit is employed, similar to the other methanol production routes, to refine the produced methanol (Azhari, et al., 2022), (IRENA and Methanol Institute, 2021). This conventional method has a dual negative impact on the atmosphere, as it relies on the energy-intensive, endothermic steam reforming of methane, which requires external heating from natural gas combustion, leading to additional CO₂ emissions (Sollai, et al., 2023).

To produce brown methanol, coal has to be converted to synthesis gas produced through gasification, which involves steam treatment at high temperatures (800-1800°C) and partial oxidation. Compared to natural gas reforming, coal syngas often needs extensive pretreatment to remove impurities and to achieve an optimal H₂ to CO ratio (ideally at least 2:1) through a water-gas shift reaction (see eq. (5) above). Following conditioning, syngas is converted into methanol using catalysts typically composed of Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃-type, with distillation performed afterwards to remove water and by-products (Chen, et al., 2019).

Recent efforts have focused on developing methanol production methods that bypass fossil fuels by using CO₂, either captured from the environment or prevented from being released (Bowker, 2019). Producing CO₂-based methanol offers both economic and environmental benefits. It helps address climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions while also enabling the production of valuable products with significant economic potential (Azhari, et al., 2022). Methanol synthesis is considered renewable or "green" when (i) the carbon source is derived from waste products, (ii) the hydrogen is generated from non-fossil fuel sources and (iii) the energy required for the process comes from renewable sources. Renewable methanol can be produced through either the bio-methanol or e-methanol pathway. As shown in Figure 4.1 above, bio-methanol is derived from the gasification of biomass feedstocks (including forestry and agricultural waste, biogas from landfills, sewage, municipal solid waste (MSW) and paper, among others) while e-methanol is produced using captured CO₂ and green hydrogen, which is generated via electrolysis using renewable electricity sources (Roode-Gutzmer, et al., 2019), (Nemmour, et al., 2023).

4.2 GENERIC CASE OF E-METHANOL SYNTHESIS

E-methanol production from captured CO₂ requires green hydrogen and renewable electricity and can follow three alternative pathways. The first and most established route involves the electrolysis

of water to produce hydrogen (H_2), which is then used in the methanation of CO_2 . This approach presents technical maturity and scalability, making it the most viable path to large-scale implementation. The second route involves the co-electrolysis of CO_2 and water to produce syngas, a mixture of carbon monoxide (CO) and hydrogen (H_2). Through conventional catalytic processes (as in traditional methanol production), this syngas is then converted into methanol. While this route has the potential for higher conversion efficiency compared to the first, it is less developed. Conventional water electrolysis operates on a megawatt scale, whereas co-electrolysis is still confined to the kilowatt scale in laboratory settings. The third route utilizes the electrochemical reduction of CO_2 and water to produce methanol directly. However, this approach is still in the experimental stage, with only limited efficiency and yield demonstrated at a laboratory scale (IRENA and Methanol Institute, 2021).

Given these factors, the POSEIDON project focuses on the first pathway, leveraging green hydrogen and captured CO_2 , which can be sourced from biogenic and industrial emissions. This approach is the most practical and well-developed of the three. After methanol synthesis, the produced methanol-water mixture must be separated to isolate the pure methanol. The water is sent to a wastewater treatment plant, while purified methanol is stored on-site before being transported to the port, as depicted in Figure 4.2, which illustrates the complete value chain under consideration.

Figure 4.2. Generic value chain of methanol synthesis.

4.2.1 E-METHANOL SYNTHESIS TECHNOLOGIES

4.2.1.1 DIRECT AND INDIRECT METHANOL SYNTHESIS TECHNOLOGIES

Renewable e-methanol synthesis via CO_2 methanation can be achieved through two alternative routes. As illustrated in Figure 4.3, the first route involves the direct synthesis of methanol from CO_2 and hydrogen through catalytic hydrogenation. Alternatively, the second route employs an indirect synthesis process comprising two stages: first, CO_2 is partially converted into syngas via the Reverse Water-Gas Shift (RWGS) reaction, and then the syngas undergoes catalytic methanol synthesis through hydrogenation of CO and CO_2 , similarly to the conventional steam-methane reforming process. This two-step method is referred to as the CAMERE (CARbon dioxide hydrogenation to METHanol via REverse water-gas shift) process and is considered more efficient due to the low

conversion efficiency of carbon dioxide in the direct synthesis method (Anicic, et al., 2014). The indirect synthesis of methanol from CO₂ differs thermodynamically from the conventional process, as it introduces the reverse water-gas shift (RWGS) reaction, an endothermic step, which contrasts with the exothermic methanol synthesis via CO₂ and CO hydrogenation (Bowker, 2019). In contrast, the direct synthesis of methanol from pure CO₂ does not utilize the RWGS reactor. Instead, CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol occurs in a single step using commercially available catalysts (Leonzio, 2018).

Figure 4.3. Direct and indirect renewable e-methanol synthesis routes (Leonzio, 2018).

The CAMERE process, developed at the Korean Institute of Science and Technology (KIST), is an innovative two-stage method for indirectly converting carbon dioxide into methanol. The synthesis begins with the reverse water gas shift (RWGS) reaction (see eq. (8)), an equilibrium endothermic process that requires high temperatures for optimal conversion. In the first reactor, carbon dioxide is converted into carbon monoxide and water, facilitated by a ZnO/Al₂O₃ catalyst. This catalyst is widely used in commercial applications due to its high selectivity and effectiveness in approaching equilibrium, with the reactor operating optimally at temperature around 800°C and pressure of 16 bar, achieving a CO₂ conversion rate of approximately 60% (Anicic, et al., 2014), (Joo, et al., 2004).

After the RWGS reaction, the products are cooled and water is separated using a flash separator. The remaining gas mixture, containing CO, CO₂ and H₂, is then mixed with additional hydrogen to achieve the desired molar ratio of CO₂, CO and H₂ at 1:1:4 before entering the methanol synthesis reactor. In the second step, methanol is synthesized from the gas mixture based on equations (9) and (10) using a highly selective Cu/ZnO catalyst enriched with ZrO₂ to enhance CO₂ conversion efficiency. Although higher temperatures favor thermodynamic conversion, the methanol synthesis operates around 250°C to prevent thermal deactivation of the catalyst, ensuring high activity and optimal methanol conversion. The Cu/ZnO/ZrO₂ catalyst demonstrates a methanol selectivity exceeding 99%, although minor side products such as methane, dimethyl ether (DME), higher alcohols and higher alkanes may be produced (Anicic, et al., 2014).

Following the methanol synthesis, the reaction mixture is cooled down to 30°C, and a gas-liquid separation is carried out in a flash separator. The gas phase mainly consists of unreacted CO₂, CO, and H₂, and the gas phase is partly recycled into the system. The liquid phase, which consists of methanol, water, and dissolved gases, is sent to a distillation unit for further purification (Anicic, et al., 2014).

In the direct methanol synthesis process, carbon dioxide and hydrogen (in a 1:3 ratio) are fed directly into a reactor using a Cu/ZnO catalyst doped with ZrO₂. Although some carbon monoxide is produced, the methanol selectivity is over 99%, excluding CO, with total conversion of 21%. The selectivities for methanol and carbon monoxide are 68% and 31%, respectively, with side products including dimethyl ether (DME) and methane. Despite low CO₂ conversion, advancements in catalyst materials and technologies could improve this. The output stream, which contains unreacted reactants, methanol, water and carbon monoxide, is cooled and separated into two phases via a flash separator. The gas phase is split, with most of it being recycled back into the reactor, part of it being sent to a second reactor for further methanol synthesis, and the smallest portion undergoing combustion after hydrogen recovery (Anicic, et al., 2014).

The hydrogenation of CO₂ to methanol is an exothermic process, but the conversion is limited by kinetics, with only 15-25% of CO₂ being converted under standard conditions. From a thermodynamic perspective, CO₂ is more stable than CO, with a heat of formation of -393 kJ/mol compared to CO's -110 kJ/mol. Additionally, CO₂ has a high bond energy (750 kJ/mol) for its C=O double bond, making it more challenging to activate compared to other bonds like C–C, C–O, or C–H. As a result, the conversion of CO₂ into methanol requires significant energy and the use of a catalyst under specific reaction conditions (Azhari, et al., 2022).

In conclusion, while both the direct and indirect methods can achieve the goal of producing methanol from CO₂, there are notable differences in terms of thermodynamics, efficiency and process requirements. The major advantage of the indirect synthesis system, particularly the CAMERE process, lies in its high selectivity for methanol (over 99%) and the production of highly pure methanol. Additionally, the process allows for recycling of unreacted gases, minimizing waste and improving overall efficiency. However, the system has significant energy demands, particularly due to the high temperatures (around 800°C) required for the RWGS reaction. Furthermore, the methanol synthesis Cu/ZnO/ZrO₂ catalyst used in the second step faces thermal deactivation at temperatures above 250°C, which can affect long-term performance (Azhari, et al., 2022).

The direct synthesis route is simpler, as it bypasses the RWGS reaction and directly synthesizes methanol from CO₂ and H₂ in a single step. The major advantage of this process is its lower energy consumption, as it avoids the high temperatures needed for the RWGS reaction. Additionally, the use of tube-cooled reactors enhances temperature control, reduces the risk of hot spots and improves heat distribution, thereby extending catalyst life and reducing operational interruptions (Marlin, et al., 2018). However, this method typically suffers from lower CO₂ conversion rates and the formation of unwanted by-products like CO, methane, and DME. The reaction is also kinetically limited, with only about 15–25% of CO₂ being converted into methanol under standard conditions (Azhari, et al., 2022).

4.2.1.2 E-METHANOL PRODUCTION PLANTS DESIGN AND COST

E-methanol production has seen significant advancements, with facilities operating at various scales, from pilot plants with capacities of less than 30 tons per year to large-scale commercial operations. These facilities generally operate under conditions similar to conventional syngas-based methanol processes, with temperatures around 250°C, pressures between 50–100 bar, and gas hourly space velocities (GHSV) of approximately 10,000 h⁻¹. Despite these similarities, pilot plants often report varying carbon conversion rates, ranging from 40% to 97% with gas recycling (Dieterich, et al., 2020). Reactor design is a critical aspect of methanol synthesis, especially because the formation of methanol from CO is highly exothermic. The primary objective in designing methanol synthesis reactors is to efficiently manage the excess heat generated by the reaction. Proper heat removal not only shifts the reaction equilibrium toward methanol production but also prevents catalyst deactivation. Heat management can be achieved similarly to syngas-based methanol synthesis reactors, either adiabatically using external cooling or quasi-isothermally via internal cooling of the catalyst beds (Roode-Gutzmer, et al., 2019).

Traditional methanol plants often employ boiling water reactors (BWRs) due to their ability to handle the high temperatures associated with the exothermic synthesis of methanol. While effective, BWRs are complex and costly to operate. Alternative reactor designs, such as adiabatic or cold-shot reactors, offer cost advantages but are generally less efficient. These designs often require multiple reactors in series to achieve acceptable conversion rates, leading to increased operational complexity. Furthermore, the high temperatures in these reactors can result in catalyst sintering, which reduces catalyst lifespan and increases operational costs. This can lead to expensive shutdowns for catalyst replacement or regeneration. Without proper heat management, these reactors are also susceptible to uncontrolled methanation reactions, which can disrupt process control and reduce efficiency (Marlin, et al., 2018).

Among the pioneering technologies in methanol synthesis, the Lurgi process stands out as the first pilot-scale catalytic conversion of CO₂ to methanol, developed in 1994. Utilizing a Cu/ZnO catalyst, the Lurgi reactor achieved a per-pass production rate of 40% at 250°C and 80 bar. Over the years, various innovative technologies and processes have been developed to convert CO₂ into methanol at an industrial scale. Lurgi AG further advanced an industrial-scale two-stage process for CO₂-to-methanol conversion in the early 1990s. The process begins with an adiabatic fixed-bed reactor for pre-conversion, in which 10-30% of carbon oxides are converted. During this stage, the exothermic methanol formation and endothermic water-gas shift reactions occur simultaneously, causing a moderate temperature rise. After this pre-conversion step, methanol and water are separated, enhancing methanol formation in the subsequent quasi-isothermal synthesis loop. This approach enables the overall carbon conversion to methanol to reach 58-61%. Notably, pilot plant trials conducted in 2011 demonstrated significant improvements, achieving total CO₂ conversion rates of 94–97% with per-pass conversion efficiencies of 30-45% (Roode-Gutzmer, et al., 2019), (Dieterich, et al., 2020).

The first commercial-scale e-methanol facility, operated by Carbon Recycling International (CRI) in Iceland since 2011, marked a milestone in the industry. Initially producing 1300 tons of methanol annually, the plant expanded to 4000 tons per year by 2014 under the brand name Vulcanol. The plant utilizes geothermal CO₂ and renewable geothermal energy, recycling 5600 tons of CO₂ annually from a geothermal power plant. It operates with state-of-the-art Cu/ZnO catalysts under 250°C and 100 atm. The hydrogen required is supplied via a 6 MW capacity alkaline electrolyzer,

powered by Iceland's affordable geothermal electricity. Vulcanol serves various applications, including gasoline blending, biodiesel production, and wastewater denitrification. This model demonstrates how regions with abundant clean energy can harness their resources to produce sustainable methanol and explore export opportunities (IRENA and Methanol Institute, 2021), (Dieterich, et al., 2020).

Numerous large-scale projects, with capacities ranging from 8000 to 180000 tons annually, are underway globally in countries such as Sweden, Norway, Australia, and Canada. These initiatives utilize renewable hydrogen and CO₂ derived from industrial or biogenic sources. For instance, Denmark is pursuing ambitious projects that integrate municipal solid waste and biomass-derived CO₂ with green hydrogen to produce renewable methanol and jet fuel. In addition to these commercial plants, pilot and demonstration projects across Europe and Asia, such as the FresMe and Carbon2Chem projects in Germany and the Power2Met project in Denmark, are refining e-methanol production technologies. Innovative approaches like high-temperature solar thermochemical conversion and artificial photosynthesis are also being explored, offering promising, scalable, and sustainable production pathways for the future. These efforts signal a rapid evolution in e-methanol production, driven by renewable energy and cutting-edge technologies. A detailed overview of existing and planned facilities, along with available technology providers for e-methanol production, has been compiled by IRENA and the Methanol Institute in their Innovation Outlook on Renewable Methanol (IRENA and Methanol Institute, 2021).

Currently, the production cost of renewable e-methanol is much higher than that of fossil-based methanol, with the latter ranging from 100-300 \$/ton for methanol derived from natural gas and 150-250 \$/ton for coal-based methanol. E-methanol's cost depends largely on the prices of H₂ and CO₂. Hydrogen's costs are tied to renewable electricity costs as well as electrolyzer technologies, while CO₂ sourcing costs vary by method. CO₂ capturing from industrial emissions of flue gasses is more economical than direct air capture (DAC), which significantly increases production costs. Using CO₂ from bioenergy sources in combination with CCS at 10-50\$/ton, results in e-methanol production cost in the range of 800-1600 \$/ton. However, regarding CO₂ from DAC which costs 300-600 \$/ton, the production cost is raised to 1200-1400 \$/ton. Selling oxygen as an electrolysis byproduct, may offset some expenses although this benefit will likely diminish as oxygen supply exceeds demand. Despite the high current costs, advancements in renewable energy and electrolyzer technologies are projected to reduce significantly the total e-methanol production costs to 250-630 \$/ton by the year 2050, making it competitive with fossil-based methanol (IRENA and Methanol Institute, 2021), (Nemmour, et al., 2023).

4.2.1.3 COMPARATIVE CHART FOR METHANOL SYNTHESIS TECHNOLOGIES

Table 11. Comparative chart for methanol synthesis technologies.

METHANOL SYNTHESIS PROCESS	TRL	MAIN FEATURES & ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES & LIMITATIONS
Direct synthesis		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower energy consumption. • Simpler process flow. • Better temperature control and longer catalyst life with tube-cooled reactors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower CO₂ conversion rates (CO₂ is less reactive than CO-syngas). • Formation of unwanted by-products (CO, methane, DME). • Kinetically limited, with only 15–25% CO₂ conversion.
Indirect synthesis	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High methanol selectivity (>99%). • High-purity methanol output suitable for various applications. • Efficient heat integration. • Recycling of unreacted gases improves overall efficiency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High energy consumption due to the RWGS reaction. • Thermal deactivation of catalysts at high temperatures. • Requires larger reactors and produces more water as a by-product.

4.2.2 E-METHANOL / WATER SEPARATION

The liquid stream exiting the methanol synthesis reactor, known as raw or crude methanol, is an aqueous solution composed primarily of methanol and water, along with reaction by-products and impurities such as heavy organic compounds (e.g. higher alcohols), lighter substances (e.g. dimethyl ether, DME) and unreacted gases (H_2 , N_2 , CO , CO_2) (Sadeghi & Ahangar, 2012). To achieve the required methanol purity based on its intended application, impurities are removed from raw methanol through distillation in a methanol/water separation unit. Residual water is sent to wastewater treatment, while methanol distillates from the final columns are combined to produce the final product. The design of the distillation train downstream of the reactor depends on the required purity or grade of methanol (Dieterich, et al., 2020), (Bozzano & Manenti, 2016).

Methanol is sold in various grades: fuel grade, "A" grade and "AA" grade. The latter two require purity levels exceeding 99.85 vol.%, water content less than 0.10 vol.% and ethanol concentrations less than 10 ppmw in order to be suitable for chemical applications such as the use as a solvent. Achieving such ultra-high purity specifications requires significant energy input, primarily in the form of reboiler duty during distillation (Halager, et al., 2021). Although producing lower-purity "fuel-grade" methanol is often considered impractical for large-scale suppliers serving the chemical industry, it represents a cost-reduction opportunity for smaller plants producing renewable methanol, especially if a local fuel market is available. Furthermore, combustion engines have been shown to operate effectively with methanol purities as low as 90%. (Schröder, et al., 2020).

The basic methanol distillation system (MDS) typically consists of a single conventional distillation column. In this system, light components (mainly methanol) are collected at the top and heavy components (mainly wastewater) are removed at the bottom. This process, however, consumes significant energy due to wasted heat from the condenser and the cooling required to minimize methanol loss at the top. To address energy inefficiencies, separation tasks can be distributed across multiple distillation columns operating at different pressures, enabling multi-effect heat integration. A typical two-column system includes a pre-fractionator column (PC) that removes light ends (low-boiling by-products), which are repurposed as fuel gas. The remaining methanol, water and high boilers are sent to a refining column, where pure methanol is extracted at the top. This configuration reduces methanol loss and the associated energy consumption. Additionally, using a total condenser at the top of the PC, instead of a partial one, simplifies control. This two-column system is considered state-of-the-art for MDS and is both energy-efficient and widely accepted (Shen, et al., 2023), (Dieterich, et al., 2020).

Distillation is a critical operation in the chemical industry, accounting for over 40% of total energy consumption. Rising energy costs have made simple distillation configurations economically uncompetitive, leading to the development of multi-column designs, such as 3-column, 4-column, and 5-column systems (depicted in Figure 4.4), which are now widely implemented globally (Shen, et al., 2023). For fuel-grade methanol, a single distillation column suffices, minimizing investment costs. However, for chemical-grade methanol, more complex multiple-column systems are employed (Anicic, et al., 2014).

Figure 4.4. Schematic diagram of the typical methanol/water distillation column configurations (a) 1CS, (b) 2CS, (c) 3CS, (d) 4CS, (e) 5CS (PC: Pre fractionator column, HC: Higher pressure column, MC: Medium-pressure column, AC: Atmospheric column, RC: Recovery column) (Shen, et al., 2023).

To further enhance energy efficiency, researchers are exploring advanced configurations such as multi-effect distillation integration (MED), heat pumps, Petlyuk columns and divided-wall columns (DWC). Most of these advanced designs build upon the basic two-column scheme, making them suitable for both new plants and retrofits. This adaptability promotes large-scale implementation and improves energy efficiency across the entire process, from raw materials to refined products. Additionally, opportunities for heat exchange between adjacent chemical plant units have been explored, further enhancing integration (Shen, et al., 2023).

Advanced MDS configurations offer significant energy savings and environmental benefits but introduce added complexity in flowsheet design. The increased number of modules amplifies decision variables, complicating simultaneous optimization. Current MDS design and optimization largely depend on engineering heuristics and experience, with limited sensitivity analyses evaluating parameter impacts. These challenges hinder the development of optimal designs for systems with numerous variables. Optimization algorithms and frameworks are essential to create more compact, cost-effective, and safer plants. Further research is crucial to advance methanol distillation, improve energy efficiency, and enable process intensification (Shen, et al., 2023).

4.2.3 WASTEWATER TREATMENT

The wastewater stream exiting the distillation column system for methanol/water separation is inserting an industrial wastewater treatment system in order to purify and dispose it safely. Industrial wastewater can potentially contain a variety of pollutants, including acids, bases, soluble organic compounds that deplete dissolved oxygen, suspended solids, nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus, heavy metals (e.g., cadmium, lead, mercury, and zinc), cyanide, toxic organic chemicals, oily substances, volatile materials and thermal pollutants from elevated water temperatures. Effective control measures are essential to minimize the transfer of these pollutants to other environments, such as air, soil or subsurface layers, through robust process and engineering solutions (IFC, 2007).

Treating industrial wastewater requires a strategic approach tailored to its specific characteristics. Wastewater treatment is a complex process demanding meticulous planning, advanced technology and skilled management. The choice of treatment technologies depends on the composition of the wastewater, but their effectiveness hinges on proper design, the selection of appropriate equipment, and consistent operation and maintenance. Treatment technologies often work in combination to ensure compliance with discharge standards. Advanced systems must prevent the uncontrolled release of volatile chemicals into the air. Residuals from the treatment process, such as sludge or other by-products, should be disposed of strictly in accordance with local regulations. Where such regulations are absent, disposal methods should prioritize public health, environmental protection, and the sustainable use of land and water resources (IFC, 2007).

Wastewater treatment accelerates purification through a series of stages: primary, secondary, and, in some cases, advanced or tertiary treatments. The primary stage of industrial wastewater treatment focuses on removing solid materials such as larger debris and suspended solids through sedimentation and filtration. In this process, larger contaminants are initially filtered out by passing through screens and the wastewater is then directed into sedimentation tanks where fine particles gradually settle to form raw primary biosolids (formerly known as sludge). These biosolids are pumped out for further treatment, disposal or use as fertilizer. Mechanical equipment is commonly employed during this stage to break down larger particles. While primary treatment effectively

reduces solid waste, it often falls short of meeting modern water quality standards. By further reducing solid content, primary treatment prepares the wastewater for advanced purification in the secondary stage to achieve more thorough purification (LIQTECH, 2024), (EPA, 1998).

Secondary treatment targets the removal of soluble organic matter and smaller suspended particles through biological processes, heavily relying on oxidation to further purify the wastewater. Key techniques in secondary treatment include biofiltration, aeration through the activated sludge method, and oxidation ponds. During biofiltration, wastewater is passed through filters made of sand, contact media, trickling beds or ceramic membranes. These materials help trap additional sediments and facilitate the biological breakdown of organic matter by being covered with bacteria, which consume organic pollutants. The partially treated water then moves to another sedimentation tank to remove excess bacteria (LIQTECH, 2024), (EPA, 1998).

In the activated sludge process, wastewater is mixed with air and bacteria-laden sludge in an aeration tank. Over several hours, bacteria digest and break down organic pollutants into harmless byproducts. The activated sludge, enriched with microorganisms, is recycled back into the process. Meanwhile, oxidation ponds direct wastewater into natural or man-made lagoons where it is retained for two to three weeks. During this time, biological activity breaks down the remaining organic matter. To complete secondary treatment, the treated water is disinfected, often with chlorine, to kill harmful bacteria and reduce odors. Alternatives like ultraviolet light or ozone are increasingly used to avoid the ecological risks associated with chlorine. Some municipalities also practice dechlorination before discharging treated water into the environment. These processes collectively reduce organic content by up to 85%, producing cleaner effluent suitable for tertiary treatment (LIQTECH, 2024), (EPA, 1998).

Tertiary treatment, also known as advanced treatment, provides an additional level of purification when effluent from secondary treatment must meet higher quality standards, ensuring water suitability for industrial, agricultural, recreational, and even drinking purposes. This stage is especially important when the water is to be discharged into sensitive ecosystems or reused for specific purposes. Advanced techniques include biological or chemical methods to neutralize harmful chemicals and remove nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus. Physical-chemical processes like ceramic membrane filtration help remove fine particles and microorganisms, while activated carbon adsorption captures organic pollutants, odors and other contaminants. Sand filters are used to trap remaining fine particles. Tertiary treatment ensures the removal of even the most stubborn pollutants, making the water suitable for industrial, agricultural, recreational, or drinking purposes (LIQTECH, 2024), (EPA, 1998).

Methanol plants generate significant volumes of wastewater, especially during startup and shutdown operations, with methanol concentrations typically below 10%. Even trace amounts of methanol have a substantial impact on both living organisms and non-living environmental components. Methanol's harmful effects include retinal damage, renal disorders, and potential lethality at doses of 30–240 mL or 1 gram per kilogram of body mass for humans. Ingesting over 30 mL can cause permanent visual impairment. This wastewater is classified as an industrial waste issue due to its potential environmental impact and the challenges associated with its treatment and disposal. Addressing methanol industry waste is a critical priority to comply with environmental regulations and ensure sustainable ecosystem protection (Al-Dawery, 2013), (Rajamohan, et al., 2021).

Various methods have been studied for treating methanol-contaminated wastewater, including physical-chemical approaches such as absorption, adsorption, membrane separation, and biological methods using aerobic and anaerobic reactors. The choice of method depends on parameters like

effluent methanol concentration, chemical oxygen demand (COD) and pH. Techniques such as sorption, pervaporation, combined adsorption and photocatalytic regeneration have also been explored (Rajamohan, et al., 2021). For low methanol levels around 1 ppm, slow sand filters provide sufficient microbial activity to achieve effective treatment. However, higher concentrations, ranging from 100 to 1000 ppm, require the use of biologically activated filters (BAFs) with counter air flow (Al-Dawery, 2013).

Biosorption emerges as a cost-effective and eco-friendly alternative for wastewater treatment. It avoids secondary pollution and utilizes raw materials like plant biomass, agricultural residues and microbial biomass (bacteria, fungi, and algae). This method involves pollutant removal through passive surface attachment. Biosorbents exhibit resilience to pH fluctuations and temperature changes, making them suitable for diverse applications. Studies highlight their advantages over conventional technologies, especially for metal removal. Notable biosorbents include *Sargassum* sp., *Ulva* sp., *Saccharomyces* sp. and *Halimeda* sp., known for favorable functional groups on their cell walls that effectively remove pollutants. Marine algae, in particular, offer a promising biosorption solution due to their abundance and efficiency (Rajamohan, et al., 2021).

The treatment of industrial wastewater is a critical process that ensures the protection of the environment and the sustainability of water resources. By employing a combination of primary, secondary, and tertiary treatments, pollutants are systematically removed, and water is restored to a quality that meets regulatory and environmental standards. This multi-stage approach not only safeguards ecosystems but also supports the growing need for water reuse in various industries and communities (LIQTECH, 2024).

4.3 SPECIFIC CASE OF ICODOS E-METHANOL SYNTHESIS

The POSEIDON project aims to advance and scale up a patented hybrid process developed by the project partners at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) and ICODOS for CO₂ capture and direct e-methanol synthesis and methanol/water separation, all integrated into a single modular plant, as depicted in Figure 4.5. Currently, there is no large-scale test platform for alternative fuel production in the EU, limiting the ability to test real-world scenarios. POSEIDON's plant will be the first fully automated, remotely monitored, dynamically operated and serially produced Power-to-e-Methanol facility. It will utilize biogenic or fossil CO₂ (e.g. offgases from lime stone production) and fluctuating renewable electricity, addressing the challenges posed by decentralized sources and the need for small, modular plants. The required feedstocks include purified hydrogen and a CO₂ source either industrial or biogenic, while the outputs consist of concentrated methanol and wastewater for further treatment.

Figure 4.5. Specific case of ICODOS methanol synthesis technology.

The project seeks to build a 750 L/day plant at TRL 7, which is 15 times larger than the current 50 L/day Proof-of-Concept pilot at the KIT research facility, with the goal of commercializing fully integrated Power-to-Methanol plants using this hybrid process. This technology reduces energy requirements by 30% compared to conventional CO₂ capture methods, simplifies the process by eliminating additional solvents and is capable of removing sulfur impurities (e.g. H₂S) from biogas. Moreover, compared to conventional systems, the ICODOS process generates no CO₂ solvent waste, as the e-methanol/water mixture is used as the carbon capture agent. The hybrid process also allows the upgrading of biogas to bio-methane, expanding the use of biogas plants as carbon-neutral sources of fuel and chemicals for transportation and industry. The plant will be tested under various conditions (TRL 7) to create a digital twin for easy replication and adaptation to industrial sites. The project's results will contribute to the development of a business model for e-methanol as a shipping fuel and support the industrialization of ICODOS technology to TRL 8 after the project.

4.3.1 ICODOS E-METHANOL SYNTHESIS TECHNOLOGY

The hybrid ICODOS process offers several advantages over conventional amine-based CO₂ capture followed by e-methanol synthesis. As shown in the functional schematic of the process in Figure 4.6, the ICODOS value chain begins with CO₂ absorption at conditions of -20 to -10 °C and 3-6 bar, where CO₂ is captured using methanol/water mixture as a solvent. Absorption is followed by CO₂ desorption, occurring at 100 to 150°C and 13 to 17 bar, which operates efficiently due to the high pressure retained during desorption. Subsequently, methanol synthesis is carried out in a direct methanolation unit at 180-240°C and 40-60 bar, producing methanol from the H₂/CO₂ mixture. The methanol/water mixture from methanol synthesis is used as a CO₂ absorbent in the CO₂ capture stage, eliminating the need for additional solvents (no-CO₂ solvent waste) and simplifying the system, unlike conventional methods. The high-pressure hydrogen required for methanol synthesis is directly injected into the desorption stage to enhance CO₂ release. A commercial CuO/ZnO-based catalyst is used for methanol synthesis. The final stages include distillation for methanol/water separation and the recycling of the solvent for continued operation.

The hybrid process can be described in detail as follows, via five distinct steps:

Figure 4.6. Functional schematic of the ICODOS modular plant.

This hybrid process demonstrates exceptional energy efficiency, requiring approximately 0.55 kWh of electricity per kg of CO₂, which is up to 30% more efficient than the best state-of-the-art CO₂ capture technologies, such as amine washing with monoethanolamine (MEA) or the Rectisol process, particularly for CO₂ concentrations above 5 vol-% in off-gas. Furthermore, the technology achieves a high CO₂ capture yield exceeding 95%, underlining its effectiveness and scalability for sustainable methanol production. It can also potentially remove sulfur impurities (e.g. H₂S) from gases like biogas. ICODOS technology has been specifically developed to overcome the challenges of cost-competitiveness and scalability in e-methanol production. By combining three core innovations, the hybrid process, the dynamic and fully automated plant operation and the end-to-end modular design, it delivers significant advantages over mature, state-of-the-art e-methanol technologies as shown in Table 12. Each of these innovations contribute directly to reducing the overall cost of e-methanol production having a ripple effect, benefiting end-users in the shipping and chemical industries by making ICODOS e-methanol a cost-competitive and sustainable option.

Table 12. ICODOS e-methanol plant Value Proposition.

Value Proposition	Hybrid Process	Fully automated and dynamic production	Modular Design
Best cost-competitiveness¹³ (-20, - 48%) <i>vs. state-of-the-art e-methanol production</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ >30% less energy required for carbon capture ✓ No performance loss due to continuously regenerating solvent ✓ Longer lifetime and reduced maintenance cost due to less corrosion ✓ No solvent procurement & management needed due to lack of third-party solvent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ >10x of CAPEX for intermediate electricity or hydrogen storage ✓ Lowest energy cost by enabling direct usage of intermittent energy sources ✓ Minimization of human O&M cost through remote monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Economies of scale through modularization of main equipment, procurement advantages, and learning effects ✓ Reduction of project development cost due reduction of project complexity
Highest degree of scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Possibility to harness CO₂ point sources with >2%vol CO₂ in the off-gas ✓ No critical raw materials required ✓ No process performance limitation (in small- or large-scale) ✓ Great ease of modularizing main equipment of process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Off-grid e-methanol production enabled, thus no dependence on grid infrastructure expansion ✓ Adaptation to fluctuating CO₂ sources ✓ Adaptation to fluctuating renewable energy sources ✓ Minimization of on-site know-how needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ High degree of flexibility regarding plant size, adapting to CO₂ and energy source without time-intensive tailoring ✓ In-factory manufacturing enabled, reducing project development times by >12 months ✓ Relocation of plant enabled

For the production capacity of 750L/day, the system will require approximately a 250 kWe electrolyzer to generate sufficient hydrogen for synthesis and up to 450 m³ stp/d of CO₂. This modular plant also serves as a pilot for developing a demonstration plant with an expected production capacity of 5000-25000 L/day of e-methanol, requiring an electrolyzer between 2-10 MWe. Such a plant could process biogas (35% CO₂ content) from a plant producing approximately 10000-50000 m³ stp/d, or industrial waste gas (20% CO₂ content) from an industry generating around 20000-90000 m³ stp/d. The biogas production at the Valencia city wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) in 2023 is estimated at about 20000 m³ stp/d, with potential increases in the coming years through the addition of co-substrates like biowaste and agricultural waste in the anaerobic digesters at the WWTPs. A proposed integrated value chain diagram of the ICODOS methanol synthesis plant into the Valencia WWTP case study is depicted in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7. Value chain of the ICODOS methanol synthesis technology integrated into the Valencia case study.

5 E-METHANOL TRANSPORTATION, STORAGE AND BUNKERING FROM PLANT TO SHIP

The POSEIDON project will explore both centralized and decentralized methanol production concepts, evaluating the benefits and limitations of each system. The "decentralized" approach aims to optimize the valorization of biogenic CO₂ emissions from smaller sources, typically less than a few megawatts, which are dispersed across the landscape and not directly linked to logistics hubs or methanol consumers such as ports. This model involves establishing a small synthetic methanol production unit at the CO₂ emission site, with the resulting fuel being transported to the ports. It leverages the modularity of the ICODOS technology and potential synergies with biogas/biomethane production or onsite hydrogen generation alongside biomass combustion (for example, utilizing the co-produced oxygen for oxy-combustion). However, the economic implications of the small-scale facilities require further investigation. This concept is examined through the case study in collaboration with the GOMSL wastewater treatment plant and the port of Valencia.

In contrast, the "centralized" concept focuses on capturing larger CO₂ emissions from large industrial sources. These emissions are typically substantial and centralized, allowing for economies of scale in CO₂ capture, fuel production and logistics. This approach is examined through the case study of Thessaloniki, which involves the CaO Hellas lime production plant and the port of Thessaloniki.

In both case studies in Valencia and Thessaloniki, the methanol production facilities are situated close to their respective CO₂ emitters, such as the GOMSL wastewater treatment plant and the CaO Hellas lime production plant. As a result, the produced e-fuel must be transported to the port and temporarily stored there before being used for vessel bunkering. In this context, the value chain depicted in Figure 5.1 is under investigation, with an analysis of the main technological opportunities and barriers at each step presented in the following sections.

Figure 5.1. Value chain of e-methanol transportation, storage and bunkering from the production plant to ship.

5.1 E-METHANOL STORAGE ON-SITE AND AT THE PORT

Methanol exiting the methanol/water distillation units is temporarily stored on-site at the methanol synthesis plant before being transported to the port. After its transfer to the port, it is stored on the dock to be available for local use and ship bunkering. Improper handling poses risks to human health and the environment, with the severity of these risks depending on how methanol is stored, handled and used. On-site and on-port methanol storage generally follows guidelines similar to those for gasoline, with methanol typically stored in tank farms or portable containers (like totes and drums) under ambient temperature and pressure. Tank farms often utilize above-ground floating-roof tanks and smaller internally baffled tanks, with clearly labeled overhead piping configured in pipe racks. While general design, construction and maintenance guidelines for these tanks align with those for other flammable liquids, methanol's unique properties require additional precautions ([Methanol](#)

Institute, 2020).

Methanol is a colorless liquid with considerable hazards due to its toxic, flammable and reactive properties. Classified as a Class IB flammable liquid by both the National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) and the International Code Council (ICC) and as a “1993 Class 3 Flammable Liquid” by the United Nations, it is grouped with other volatile fuels like ethanol and gasoline. Methanol has a low flash point (11°C), resulting in substantial vapor presence near its surface. These vapors are highly flammable, with a broad flammable range (6% to 36% by volume), making ignition easier than with gasoline. Methanol vapor, slightly denser than air, can accumulate in confined spaces and lead to explosive situations. External heating and elevated ambient temperatures can cause containers to explode (Medina, 2014), (Methanol Institute, 2020).

Methanol is also classified as a Class 6.1 toxic substance, posing serious, potentially fatal risks upon single exposure via inhalation, ingestion or skin contact. It can irritate the eyes, skin and upper respiratory system. Eye exposure results in burning, tearing, redness and swelling and direct contact with the liquid can lead to conjunctivitis and corneal burns while skin contact depletes natural oils, causing dryness and cracking. Methanol is hygroscopic and mixes fully with water remaining flammable even when highly diluted, with a 25% methanol solution still considered flammable. It burns with a non-visible flame, complicating firefighting efforts (Medina, 2014), (Methanol Institute, 2020).

Unlike non-polar fuels, methanol’s polar nature and electrical conductivity heighten the risk of galvanic and dissimilar metal corrosion. Therefore, methanol storage best practices emphasize using compatible materials, regular inspection and considering corrosion protection methods to prevent failures and ensure safety. Methanol storage tanks are commonly constructed from carbon steel or 300-series austenitic stainless steel. Although carbon steel is more economical upfront, it incurs higher maintenance costs due to its susceptibility to corrosion, especially in humid or coastal areas. Tanks near coastal environments are at higher risk due to chloride accumulation, leading to under-deposit, pitting and crevice corrosion. Additionally, methanol’s hygroscopic nature makes it prone to moisture absorption, further increasing corrosion risks, particularly in carbon steel tanks. Methanol’s hygroscopic nature can also lead to contamination, particularly in humid environments where air contains chloride salts. Coatings like epoxy resin have limited effectiveness -typically lasting less than seven years- and may create non-conductive barriers that complicate grounding and bonding. However, advancements in conductive spray-on linings are helping to address this issue. Dissimilar trim materials, such as aluminum, lead and copper, can experience accelerated corrosion in methanol service. While plastic coatings are generally unsuitable due to degradation and contamination risks, certain resins, nylons and rubbers (e.g. nitrile, Teflon, neoprene) can be effectively used in methanol storage (Methanol Institute, 2020).

To minimize the risk of catastrophic incidents, methanol users should adopt a comprehensive safety management system that addresses the hazards specific to methanol handling during loading and unloading, transporting and storing, focusing on people, equipment and procedures. The key precautions focus on managing static electricity, avoiding ignition sources and preventing air exposure. To prevent static discharge hazards, all tanks must be properly grounded. Flow rates should be controlled to reduce turbulence and static build-up, with bonded and grounded equipment and liquid seals in pipes to prevent air mixing and moisture absorption. Ignition control methods include nitrogen and natural gas padding in order to displace oxygen and prevent flammable conditions while designating hazardous zones with ignition controls should exist. Methanol should be kept at least 50 feet from ignition sources like sparks, hot surfaces and equipment that generates

heat. To prevent overfilling and accommodate methanol's higher thermal expansion coefficient (0.00066/°F), storage tanks should allow a 20% volume buffer (Medina, 2014), (Methanol Institute, 2020).

Methanol storage areas should use compatible materials, like concrete, for curbing and include ventilation to prevent vapor buildup, with safe drainage away from the storage site. Tote and drum containers must be stored outdoors unless in designated flammable liquid storage rooms. Storage areas should be equipped with vapor and heat detectors, as methanol's non-luminous flame makes standard smoke detectors ineffective. Infrared detection is recommended for spotting combustion in storage areas. For larger storage setups, automatic fire suppression systems like fine water mist or alcohol-resistant foam should be considered, along with adherence to stacking and density limitations (Methanol Institute, 2018).

Tote and drum storage for methanol, though widely used, presents elevated risks due to spill potential, requiring immediate cleanup and rigorous safety practices. Spill containment should include sufficient firewater (at least five times the methanol volume) to dilute spills to non-flammable levels. Despite methanol's higher flammability limit (7% v/v) compared to gasoline (1.4% v/v), its vapor disperses more easily, necessitating safety zones that account for both flammability and toxicity considerations. Similar to gasoline, methanol storage setups require berming for spill containment and proper ventilation. Berms (a level space, shelf or raised barrier separating areas in a vertical way) should be reinforced with durable materials, as methanol's solvent properties render asphalt unsuitable for containment structures (Medina, 2014), (Methanol Institute, 2018).

Given the extensive use of totes and drums compared to bulk storage facilities, the methanol industry has focused on developing effective tote designs and strongly advises handlers to consult with suppliers for suitable containment options. Unlike tank farms, where personnel have limited contact with stored methanol, tote and drum users face higher spill risks and must be prepared for quick spill response and cleanup and should wear appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE) to minimize exposure risks (Medina, 2014), (Methanol Institute, 2018).

5.2 E-METHANOL TRANSPORTATION BY TRUCKS, TRAINS AND PIPELINES

In both the "centralized" and "decentralized" concepts under investigation, e-methanol can be transported from the production facility to port storage using trucks, rail, or pipeline networks, depending on the quantity of e-methanol produced, transportation costs, the distance covered and the associated environmental emissions. For each method, various precautions must be taken to ensure safety, reliability and integrity.

Firstly, pipelines, in their simplest form, consist of a series of steel pipes welded together with pumping stations placed at various points along the route to maintain proper flow characteristics. They range in diameter from 4 to 58 inches and can vary in length from a few kilometers to several thousand kilometers. Compressor stations in gas pipelines can be operated by gas turbines, while pumping stations in methanol pipelines can be power-driven. A crucial technical factor to consider before selecting this type of transport is material compatibility (Atkinson, 1982).

As mentioned in Section 5.1, methanol is highly corrosive to certain materials. When it comes in contact with standard carbon steel, which is commonly used in pipelines, fittings, and valves, it tends to dissolve rust and slowly corrode the steel. Although the rate of rust dissolution is relatively fast,

the corrosion of steel occurs at a much slower pace, generally not raising significant concerns. When constructing new methanol pipelines, standard practice involves welding underground piping and coating it with asphalt or plastic adhesive tape to prevent corrosion. The pumps utilized for transferring methanol are typically made of carbon steel or bronze-lined steel, with mechanical seals or square asbestos packing employed to prevent leaks. Some plastics are also vulnerable to deterioration from methanol; these plastics are often used in gaskets, O-rings, and packings. The chemical industry has encountered similar issues due to methanol's widespread use in various processes. Neoprene and neoprene-asbestos mixtures have been found to resist methanol's corrosive effects. However, certain plastics, such as polyurethane, Buna-N and Viton which are common in some pipelines and in automobile engines and pumps, should be avoided. Additionally, there is a potential issue with standard valves in transfer lines, as they can be prone to blown gaskets and valve packing due to the significant expansion of methanol when its container is heated by sunlight. Installing relief valves can help mitigate this problem (Atkinson, 1982).

Alternatively, various types of rail tank cars exist, some equipped with heating coils and insulation to facilitate the transportation of heavy fuels and asphalt. Pressurized tank cars are designed to carry LPG, while unpressurized and unheated cars are typically used for transporting gasoline, aviation fuel and distillate fuel oils. The capacities of tank cars can range up to 230 m³ or more (Atkinson, 1982). Rail transport precautions for methanol are similar to those for other flammable liquids like ethanol, gasoline, MTBE, jet fuel and distillates. Rail transport is generally safe as long as methanol remains contained in an upright tanker car. However, in the event of a derailment, methanol should be treated as highly flammable and toxic. One critical measure is grounding in order to prevent static discharge. The tanker cars are specially designed with pressure relief features to handle thermal expansion during transit and allow for temporary holding (less than 30 days) during switching or sideling. Large releases may cause “running fires,” which are particularly hazardous if they reach sewers or drains, as they can ignite distant areas through flashback (Medina, 2014).

Tank trucks are primarily used for local distribution and are optimal for distances ranging from 40 to 80 km. Truck tankers are also employed for longer hauls to supplement pipeline deliveries during seasonal peak demand periods (Atkinson, 1982). The considerations for rail tank cars also apply to tankers connected to tractor haul trucks, as well as to tank trailers towed by these trucks. Transporting methanol by truck requires adherence to similar precautions that are typically implemented for gasoline transportation (Medina, 2014).

5.3 PORT LOGISTICS AND BUNKERING

Methanol remains in liquid form at ambient temperature and pressure, allowing methanol bunkering to operate similarly to traditional marine fuels such as Marine Gas Oil (MGO) or Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO). This compatibility means that only minimal, low-cost modifications are required to accommodate methanol's low flashpoint, making it relatively straightforward to integrate into existing storage, distribution and bunkering systems (Methanol Institute, 2023). Methanol is already transported globally by ship, road and rail, with annual volumes exceeding 10 million tons, supported by a well-developed infrastructure and established bunkering guidelines. However, to meet future demand - potentially reaching hundreds of millions of tons of methanol as maritime fuel annually - significant expansion of port infrastructure, including terminals and bunkering facilities, will be needed. The primary methods for bunkering methanol as a bulk product (i.e. pumped through a hose) to ships, as illustrated in Figure 5.2, are as follows (Methanol Institute, 2017):

- “Truck to Ship” bunkering using road tankers.
- “Ship to Ship” bunkering (also called “Barge to Ship”) using bunker vessels.
- “Land storage tank to Ship” bunkering (also called “Pipe to Ship”), using a pipe or hose connection.

Figure 5.2. Value chain of e-methanol bunkering through three alternative methods.

Additionally, providing fuel in portable tanks transferred to the vessel is another option that may be suitable for smaller vessels or specific applications, such as fuel cells. For example, the MS *Innogy*, equipped with a 330-liter methanol tank for fuel cells, bunkered methanol from a portable tank brought to the jetty. Similarly, during the GreenPilot project, a portable tank on a trailer was used to supply the pilot boat, which operated solely for testing and development. This approach provided a flexible and efficient bunkering solution for limited operations. As outlined in the following subsections, all of the above methods have been successfully tested in numerous real-world cases (Ellis, et al., 2021).

It is important to note that methanol bunkering, like any fuel bunkering, carries specific risks that must be managed through strict adherence to safe procedures. Methanol’s unique properties and associated hazards, as discussed in section 5.2, must be considered when developing bunkering protocols for specific applications. Common hazards in methanol bunkering and the corresponding safety measures are outlined in Figure 5.3. To further ensure safety, hazard identification and HAZOP (Hazard and Operability) studies are recommended to identify potential risks and establish safeguards tailored to each case. Established health and safety protocols within the shipping and chemical industries provide proven procedures to ensure methanol is safely managed throughout transport and handling (Methanol Institute, 2017), (Ellis, et al., 2021).

Hazard	Examples of Safeguards
Flammability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elimination of ignition sources in zones near bunkering hoses and equipment (no smoking, no cell phones, etc.) • Use of Ex classed equipment such as bunker pump, gas detectors, etc. • Vapour detection • Bunker connections should be in open areas such as on deck • Anti-static measures such as grounding and bonding (ensuring there is no potential difference between the supplier and the receiver, and that cannot be developed during flow through a hose or pipe) <p>Elimination or minimisation of leakage or spill through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of drip-free couplings • Use of breakaway couplings • High level alarm • Automatic shutdown of pump when "high high" level is reached in the receiving tank • Emergency shut down equipment
Toxicity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal protective equipment (PPE) fit for the task • Portable gas detector for monitoring exposure • Spill/leakage minimisation measures as above
Corrosivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of materials compatible with methanol • Spill trays in areas near pipe/hose connections • Use of drip-free couplings to prevent release

Figure 5.3. Methanol main hazards and examples of safeguards during bunkering procedures (Ellis, et al., 2021).

5.3.1 “TRUCK TO SHIP” BUNKERING

Truck-to-ship bunkering involves the direct delivery of fuel to a ship at port using trucks, typically for small to medium-sized vessels or those with short stays. This method offers the advantage of not requiring specialized infrastructure, as the ship only needs to moor at a quay accessible to trucks. The process involves transferring fuel from a tanker truck to the docked or anchored vessel through hoses. The operation is closely monitored to ensure that fuel is transferred at the correct pressure and temperature, minimizing safety risks. Limitations of truck-to-ship bunkering include the truck's capacity, which is regulated by transport legislation, as well as the lower fuel flow rates compared to other methods. Additionally, this approach can disrupt cargo and passenger handling operations (Llanos Díez-Hochleitner & Rodríguez de la Rúa, 2024).

Truck-to-ship bunkering is currently the most prevalent method for supplying methanol to vessels, especially for ships other than dedicated methanol tankers. Since 2015, the ropax ferry *Stena Germanica* (depicted in Figure 5.4) has regularly bunkered methanol via truck from a specially constructed facility on the quayside, enabling its dual-fuel main engines. Methanol is bunkered into integral tanks on board the vessel. Other vessels that have utilized truck-to-ship methanol bunkering include the MV *Undine*, which used methanol in solid oxide fuel cell tests, *Stena Scanrail* as part of the SPIRETH project during 2013-2014, and the *Viking Mariella*, which was bunkered using a standard hose arrangement and has a methanol fuel cell setup for auxiliary power. Methanol's classification as a Class 3 flammable liquid under the ADR dangerous goods regulations in Europe

allows for routine transport to various consumers, though demand for methanol as a marine fuel remains in its early stages. Consequently, truck bunkering has been preferred over dedicated bunker barges, especially in pilot studies and research projects, due to methanol's relative novelty as a marine fuel and the lack of significant demand concentration in specific regions (Methanol Institute, 2023), (Ellis, et al., 2021).

Figure 5.4. Truck-to-ship methanol bunkering of *Stena Germanica* from a tanker truck with trailer (Ellis, et al., 2021).

5.3.2 “SHIP TO SHIP” BUNKERING

Ship-to-ship (or barge-to-ship) bunkering is a widely used method for refueling large vessels and involves transferring fuel from one bunkering vessel to another while both vessels are either at anchor or in motion. This method provides greater flexibility, as it eliminates the need for the vessels to dock at a port, avoiding port fees and berth clearance queues. Typically, the bunker vessel moors alongside the receiving vessel, with the two vessels connected by hoses for the transfer. However, ship-to-ship bunkering also introduces additional safety and environmental challenges, such as the potential for spills at sea, and is dependent on favorable weather and sea conditions. The process requires specialized equipment and skilled personnel to ensure that the fuel is transferred safely and efficiently, with monitoring to maintain the proper pressure and temperature to mitigate safety risks. Furthermore, it requires additional port infrastructure to replenish the bunkering vessels (Llanos Díez-Hochleitner & Rodríguez de la Rúa, 2024).

In May 2021, a notable demonstration of methanol bunkering via this method was conducted in Rotterdam, marking the world's first large-scale barge-to-ship methanol bunkering operation. In this exercise, the methanol tanker *Takaoa Sun* was successfully refueled by the barge *MTS Evidence*

(depicted in Figure 5.5), with a transfer of 300 metric tonnes of methanol. This demonstration highlighted the feasibility of using existing infrastructure to bunker methanol safely, adhering to standard mooring and signaling requirements as per the AND, the European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Inland Waterways. The operation showed that methanol bunkering requires similar safety protocols and risk assessments as conventional marine fuels, though additional refinements may be necessary for different ship types. Following this success, methanol bunker vessels have been ordered to serve major ports such as Rotterdam, Norway and Singapore, supporting the expanding use of methanol as a marine fuel (Methanol Institute, 2023), (Ellis, et al., 2021).

Figure 5.5. Barge-to-ship methanol bunkering of *Takaroa Sun* methanol tanker from *MTS Evidence* barge vessel in Rotterdam (Ellis, et al., 2021).

5.3.3 “PIPE TO SHIP” BUNKERING

Pipe-to-ship (or Port-to-ship or Terminal) bunkering involves delivering fuel from shore facilities at a port directly to the ship. This method is often considered the safest and most controlled, but it typically requires more logistical planning and lead time compared to other options. Pipe-to-ship allows for the delivery of larger fuel volumes at higher rates without interfering with cargo loading/unloading or other port operations. However, its effectiveness is limited by the availability of appropriate port facilities and the location of their installation (Llanos Díez-Hochleitner & Rodríguez de la Rúa, 2024). This method is also suitable for vessels operating from a home port, such as pilot boats and tugboats being converted for methanol use in projects like FASTWATER. Larger vessels typically bunker from terminals during cargo loading via a process similar to the procedures used for small methanol tankers. However, for smaller vessels, terminal bunkering may require modifications to pipe sizes or

delivery pressures to match the vessel's equipment. In these cases, a more practical solution could be installing a small tank or dispensing station at the home port. This approach, like the one used for the Swedish Maritime Administration's methanol-fueled pilot boat, could be more cost-effective than truck delivery, particularly for vessels needing smaller volumes of fuel. An example of pipe-to-ship bunkering of methanol occurred in October 2022, when China State Shipbuilding Corporation (CSSC) Hengyu Energy bunkered three 49000-ton tankers with 240 tons of methanol from a purpose-built terminal facility (Methanol Institute, 2023), (Ellis, et al., 2021).

Figure 5.6. Virtual 3D representation of CSSC Hengyu Energy completed methanol bunkering infrastructure (Future Fuels, 2022).

6 E-METHANOL END USE IN SHIPS AND ONBOARD OPERATIONS

Following e-methanol bunkering, the final step in the POSEIDON value chain involves the onboard use of e-methanol across various vessel types. Methanol, being one of the most widely transported chemical commodities and fuels globally, has storage facilities in over 120 ports and is used by more than 20 vessels already. According to the Methanol Institute, since 2015, 251 new methanol-powered vessels are either in service or on order books as of 2024. These include cargo vessels such as large container ships, chemical tankers, bulk carriers, container feederships and car carriers, as well as passenger and cargo ferries, workboats and specialized and support vessels like tugboats, Service Operation Vessels (SOV), banker barges and superyachts (Methanol Institute, 2023).

The popularity of methanol as a marine fuel is increasing, driven mostly by more rigorous emissions regulations and greener alternatives to shipping. The International Maritime Organization (IMO), the United Nations agency responsible for regulating security, safety and pollution prevention in international commercial shipping, has implemented measures over the past decade to reduce sulfur oxides (SO_x), nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and particulate matter (PM) emissions. In 2018, the IMO adopted a strategy to reduce total annual greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from international shipping by at least half by 2050, compared to the 2008 baseline. Additionally, the Cargo Owners for Zero Emission Vessels (CoZev) initiative is focused on eliminating GHG emissions from shipping by 2050. Methanol has emerged as a viable fuel to help meet these emission-reduction targets. Methanol serves to the most stringent IMO emission requirements when deployed in advanced engine systems. It can reduce NO_x emissions by 80%, SO_x by 99% and particulate matter (PM) by 95% relative to heavy fuel oil (HFO) (Methanol Institute, 2023).

In addition to its environmental benefits, methanol offers advantages in availability, ease of use, performance and total cost of ownership (TCO), positioning it as a strong candidate for the shipping industry's shift to alternative fuels. A key benefit of methanol is its compatibility with existing bunkering, storage and propulsion infrastructure, as it remains liquid at ambient pressure. Methanol is already routinely shipped worldwide and the marine industry has substantial experience handling it safely. Methanol's safety profile is also well-suited for marine fuel applications since it is fully miscible in water and biodegradable, meaning that in the event of a spill, the impact on marine life is likely to be temporary and reversible (Dierickx, et al., 2021), (Methanol Institute, 2023).

Methanol has a higher energy density compared to other alternative fuels, such as LNG, ammonia and hydrogen, especially when considering the space required for storage tanks, secondary barriers, and cofferdams. However, it still has a lower energy density than traditional marine fuels, like MGO, which has an energy density of 36.6 GJ/m³, compared to methanol's 15.8 GJ/m³. Methanol's energy density influences the types of vessels it is best suited for, with methanol being most efficient for vessels on fixed, round-trip routes, such as cruise ships, inland waterway bulk transport vessels, short-sea container ships, ferries, short-sea tankers, deep-sea container vessels and general cargo ships. Despite this, methanol has the advantage of being able to be stored in conventional fuel tanks or even ballast tanks, unlike LNG and hydrogen, which need cryogenic storage (Methanol Institute, 2023).

Due to its advantages, methanol has been adopted as a marine fuel by several leading shipping companies, including prominent names such as AP Moller-Maersk, CMA CGM and COSCO, who have developed methanol-compatible engines and supply systems. Currently, over two dozen methanol-powered vessels are in operation, with more than 80 new two-stroke methanol dual-fuel engines on order with MAN Energy Solutions, the leading manufacturer of methanol engines. Other major engine suppliers, including Wärtsilä, Rolls-Royce/MTU, WinGD, Anglo Belgian Corporation (ABC), Caterpillar and Hyundai Heavy Industries, are also offering or introducing new models. ([Methanol Institute, 2023](#)).

Methanol ICE (Internal Combustion Engine) technology is commercially established and has reached a high degree of technological readiness. Additionally, methanol-fueled fuel cells are being developed for marine applications with pilot tests taking place globally. Regarding methanol's use in ICEs, multiple configurations have been explored with modifications varying depending on engine type. The two most common types of ICEs used for methanol are referred to as Spark Ignition (SI) engines and Compression Ignition (CI) engines. Spark Ignition (SI) engines operate by using spark plugs to ignite a mixture of fuel and air, resulting in controlled combustion that drives the engine. Methanol's high octane number, resistance to autoignition and significant heat of vaporization make it well-suited for SI engines as a pure fuel or blended with gasoline, requiring only minor modifications. However, it may condense at lower temperatures, necessitating some operational adjustments. Flex-fuel SI engines that can run on either gasoline or alcohol blends have been developed and widely used and tests with pure methanol or methanol-gasoline blends in SI engines have shown promising results ([Verhelst , et al., 2019](#)).

In contrast, CI (Compression Ignition) engines create combustion under a different procedure which adheres a process of injecting the fuel straight into the heated air in the combustion chamber. This creates spontaneous combustion of the fuel as the temperature and pressure rises when the piston reaches the Top Dead Centre (TDC) therefore removing the need for traditional spark plugs. Given that most marine engines are CI engines and typically require fuels with higher cetane numbers and low resistance to autoignition like diesel, using methanol in CI engines presents challenges. To address this challenge, there are several potential solutions that require substantial modifications of the diesel engines to accommodate methanol. The potential solutions include: blending methanol with diesel (though this works only in small proportions without additives), adding ignition enhancers to methanol (which raises concerns about toxicity) or utilizing dual-fuel technology ([Verhelst , et al., 2019](#)), ([Dierickx, et al., 2021](#)).

In the POSEIDON project, two alternative value chain configurations are being explored for the onboard end-use of e-methanol. Both configurations involve a dual-fuel engine that combines Marine Diesel Oil (MDO) with e-methanol for ship propulsion. The main distinction between these configurations is that the second setup incorporates additional gensets (electricity generation systems) to provide energy for the vessel's "hotel load", which is the power needed for onboard amenities and operations. Specifically, the gensets being considered are Indirect Methanol Fuel Cells (IMFC), which necessitate an added methanol reforming step to produce hydrogen that would then fuel the fuel cell system. The following sections will provide a detailed analysis of the current technological advancements for each component within these configurations.

6.1 DUAL FUEL ENGINE CONFIGURATION

As previously noted, methanol's low cetane number and high resistance to spontaneous ignition make it unsuitable for conventional compression ignition (CI) engines. However, using methanol (a high-octane fuel) as the primary fuel alongside diesel (a high-cetane fuel) as a pilot fuel in a dual-fuel engine system facilitates the transition to renewable fuel use in both new-build ships and retrofitted vessels. As depicted in Figure 6.1, effective storage and safe handling of both Marine Diesel Oil (MDO) and methanol are critical, as well as adequate fuel purification and preparation before combustion, to ensure reliable operation of the dual-fuel engine. The dual-fuel engine combusts these fuels to generate power for both ship propulsion and onboard energy needs, including heating, cooling and electricity, often referred to as the "hotel load". The proportion of power allocated to ship propulsion versus hotel load will vary depending on the vessel type and operational demands. Additionally, although methanol is a sulfur-free fuel with minimal SO_x and particulate matter (PM) emissions when burned alone, the use of diesel as a pilot fuel still contributes to SO_x, NO_x and PM emissions. Therefore, exhaust gas cleaning systems (EGCS) are necessary to reduce these emissions to meet environmental regulations and achieve cleaner operation.

Figure 6.1. Value chain of dual fuel engine configuration for ship propulsion and hotel load.

6.1.1 ONBOARD MARINE DIESEL OIL (MDO) STORAGE

Marine Diesel Oil (MDO) is a blend of Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO) and marine gas oil (MGO), with a density of around 920 kg/m³ (at 15°C) and a minimum flashpoint of 61°C. With a sulfur content ranging from 0.5% to 1.5%, MDO is typically used by ships operating outside Emission Control Areas (ECAs) and is suitable for engines that can handle this lower-quality fuel compared to standard heavy fuel oil (HFO). MDO comes in different types - distillate, residual and blended - each with varying blending ratios that affect engine performance and environmental impact. Distillate MDO has lower viscosity and sulfur content, making it more environmentally friendly, but it can be problematic for the ship's main engine systems over long distances due to its low viscosity. Residual MDO contains higher concentrations of HFO, resulting in higher viscosity and sulfur content, making it ideal for long-distance propulsion, though it raises environmental concerns. Blended MDO combines distillate and residual MDO to optimize performance while reducing environmental impact. Some companies also

add biofuels to improve sustainability and comply with international standards (Shaw, 2024).

The majority of the practices for MDO storage, processing and machinery use follow the same procedures as those for HFO. After MDO bunkering, it is stored in dedicated bunker tanks on board, typically located outside the engine room, often in the wings or double-bottom areas. These bunker tanks are distinct from cargo and ballast tanks and can differ in form, size and the volume of bunker tanks depending on the ship design, dimensions and operational setup requirements. Companies have different standards on the maximum filling of a bunker tank, which should be recorded in the safety document of the company's management system. Typically, the maximum filling capacity ranges from 85% to 90%, although this can vary by vessel. It's essential to account for fuel expansion when the bunker tanks are heated; the 90% capacity should include this expansion allowance. Failing to do so has led to heavy fuel oil tank overflows in several instances. These fuel tanks must be properly maintained to ensure their safety and structural integrity, and they must meet specific safety and environmental protection standards. Regular inspections are necessary to prevent leaks, spills, or potential explosions. The tanks are equipped with proper ventilation, gauges, valves, and pumps to regulate the fuel flow during bunkering operations (Ford, 2012).

All fuel oil and waste oil tanks must have a heating system to maintain proper fuel viscosity due to the wax content in the fuel. To properly handle MDO, it is recommended to maintain the fuel in storage tanks at 30°C, particularly in colder conditions, to prevent wax formation when the fuel exposes to outside temperatures. Typically, steam from an oil-fired boiler is passed through coils inside the tank, although thermal oil may also be used. Temperature regulation can be automatic, but it is often manually adjusted by monitoring the tank's temperature. For steam heating systems, the integrity of the heating coils should be checked by inspecting steam condensate returns in the engine room. If oil is found, the source must be identified and increased steam consumption may indicate a coil failure (Ford, 2012).

One of the challenges in storing MDO onboard is the risk of bacterial growth due to the presence of oxygen and water in the storage tanks. Several factors can contribute to the accumulation of water in storage tanks, such as ambient humidity, temperature differences between the tank internals and surrounding air, vessel movement and leaking heating coils. Water that remains in the tanks can create an environment for bacteria to grow at the oil-water interface, potentially leading to clogging of filters or purifiers. Additionally, this water may enter the fuel system, damaging machinery or causing operational failures. Regularly draining water from the tanks is essential as part of routine daily maintenance. Water can emulsify with cat fines, preventing proper separation. To minimize water accumulation in the fuel, it is recommended to keep the tanks as full as possible when storing fuel for extended periods, reducing the surface area where condensation can form (Exxon Mobil, 2017).

Sediment is another common contaminant found in onboard fuel tanks, consisting of dirt, rust, scale from pipelines, and debris from the internal structures of storage tanks. It can also result from ineffective vent screening. All tank vents should be designed to prevent debris from entering fuel tanks, have good mesh screens, sized, cleaned and maintained properly. Another challenge is catalytic fines (cat fines), which are similar to sediment. Even if fuel meets ISO specifications, it may still contain sediment, and cat fines may still be entrained within the fuel affecting the reliable operation of diesel engines and other machinery. These cat fines must be reduced to acceptable levels to ensure proper fuel consumption (Exxon Mobil, 2017).

Fuel storage, settling and service tanks onboard vessels play a crucial role in separating water, sediment, and cat fines from the fuel. Settling tanks are specifically designed to facilitate this process,

with sloped bottoms that encourage the separation of suspended water and solid contaminants. These tanks also provide heating, de-aeration and thermal stabilization of the fuel. Proper temperature control is vital to support the settling process. Once a settling tank is filled, it is typically heated to a temperature of 6°C below the fuel's flashpoint. To minimize heat loss, tanks should be insulated. Once the desired temperature is reached, the heating source should be turned off to avoid disrupting the settling process with thermal currents. High tank temperature alarms and automatic regulators are commonly used to monitor and control heating systems (Exxon Mobil, 2017), (Ford, 2012).

6.1.2 MARINE DIESEL OIL (MDO) PURIFICATION SYSTEM

Fuel treatment onboard involves several processes to ensure fuel quality and performance, including the use of strainers, purifiers, clarifiers and filters. These systems handle fuel from initial transfer to final use. Fuel oil is typically transferred from storage tanks to settling tanks via a fuel transfer pump, which is equipped with a suction strainer, typically with a 30-by-30 mesh size. Once MDO (Marine Diesel Oil) settles in the settling tanks, it is transferred to service tanks using onboard purifiers. These purifiers are centrifugal separators that treat the fuel, controlling water and sediment levels. Purifiers also remove catalytic fines (cat fines). While purifiers cannot make all fuel oils suitable for use, effective design, operation and maintenance can protect against the harmful effects of most fuels delivered onboard. However, poorly maintained purifiers fail to improve fuel quality, potentially causing excessive engine wear or damage (Exxon Mobil, 2017).

Studies by manufacturers have shown that the most effective particle removal occurs when the purifier operates at 25% throughput, assuming the correct gravity disc is used. However, many modern purifiers operate without gravity discs, known as high-density purifiers. These machines function as clarifiers and include water monitoring and control systems to prevent water from passing through. Research indicates that using purifiers and clarifiers in series offers the best fuel purification method when gravity discs are used. The purifier removes water and some particles, while the clarifier removes additional particles, lowering the fuel's particle count. In modern systems, a single machine can perform both functions (Ford, 2012).

While separators remove sediment, dirt, ash and catalyst particles, they may not fully prevent engine wear. To capture finer solids and larger particles, a depth-type filtration system with a fine mesh (typically 5 microns) and a replaceable filter element is essential. Filtration systems are vital onboard, as MDO may contain harmful ash and solids that can damage high-pressure pumps, injection systems, and other critical engine components. A well-maintained filtration system protects the engine and extends its life, with filter element replacements recommended every 2000-3000 operating hours, as per engine manufacturer guidelines. The system should include a water drain, air vent and differential pressure gauge to monitor pressure drops and determine when filter elements need replacing. Many self-cleaning filters use a backflushing mechanism, but regular checks are needed to ensure they are cleaned at proper intervals to prevent oil loss. Over time, catalytic fines can clog filter mesh, requiring manual cleaning or replacement if the pressure drop becomes too high and the mesh cannot be backflushed effectively. Additionally, these filters remove trace water carried over from separators, which, though seemingly minor, can significantly extend injection pump life (Ford, 2012).

6.1.3 ONBOARD E-METHANOL STORAGE

As outlined in Section 5.1 regarding e-methanol storage both on-site and at ports, methanol is a colorless liquid with a low flashpoint of 11°C, posing significant hazards due to its toxic, flammable and reactive properties. It is classified as a Class IB flammable liquid and a Class 6.1 toxic substance. Consequently, the handling and storage of e-methanol must adhere to stringent safety guidelines, including specific requirements for the materials used in storage tank construction and the safety management systems implemented by methanol users and onboard personnel. Methanol is a widely distributed chemical, accounting for approximately 25% of the global seaborne petrochemical trade, which has led to existing onboard infrastructure designed to facilitate its storage and handling. While methanol is supplied to ships as a marine fuel in only a few locations worldwide, the processes of loading, carriage, discharge and handling are well-established among ship operators. These operations follow the same fundamental principles as handling methanol for industrial purposes, ensuring the safe transfer of the intended quantity without leaks, spills or other hazards (Ellis, et al., 2021).

The requirements for methanol are considerably simpler than those for other alternative fuels such as LNG and hydrogen, as methanol is non-cryogenic, remains liquid at ambient temperatures and does not require refrigeration or specialized, costly materials for tanks and pipelines (Probst, 2022). Methanol’s trans-oceanic transport follows methods similar to those used for other hydrocarbon liquids, such as crude oil, gasoline, diesel, and fuel additives like MTBE. As shown in Figure 6.2, for use as a fuel onboard, methanol is bunkered from dockside storage tanks into the sealed cargo holds of tanker ships. Shippers commonly use double-hulled vessels, which are expected to become standard as global methanol production continues to grow (Methanol Institute, 2020). Double hulls refer to tanker ship hulls that feature two layers of watertight surfaces. Both the inner and outer layers (the cofferdam) extend along the bottom and sides of the ship. This double-layer construction helps reduce the risk of marine pollution in the event of a collision, grounding or other types of hull damage. Additionally, it provides protection against water ingress or flooding if the outer layer is compromised (Wankhede, 2021).

Figure 6.2. Graphical illustration of methanol handling onboard of a containership (Probst, 2022).

To ensure the safe and efficient use of methanol as a marine fuel, stringent regulations and best practices govern its transport and handling onboard vessels. These include ensuring that the crew is properly trained, that coatings, tanks, piping, hoses, gaskets and pumps are specifically designed for methanol service using materials compatible with methanol (as analyzed in Section 5.1), and that firefighting equipment onboard is adequate, including alcohol-resistant foams. Key operational requirements further emphasize the importance of cleanliness to prevent methanol contamination and the implementation of leak detection systems. Additionally, ships must meet the vetting standards of ports and terminals to ensure compliance with both local and international safety protocols ([Methanol Institute, 2016](#)), ([Methanol Institute, 2020](#)).

Cargo systems for methanol transport should meet class requirements under the OSV Chemical Code. If not fully compliant, a risk assessment is required. Methanol's flashpoint of 11°C classifies it as Low Flashpoint Cargo and tanks should be constructed from suitable stainless steel or treated with methanol-resistant coatings. Tanks must be designed for nitrogen inerting while cofferdams in double-hull tanks should be wet- or dry-filled (with methanol gas detection) and inerted with nitrogen gas as per Class requirements. The maintenance of methanol tanks and inerting systems should be integrated into the vessel's planned maintenance system and regular inspections for coating degradation and repairs are essential to prevent corrosion and ensure methanol purity ([Marine Safety Forum & OCIMF, 2020](#)).

Although accidental releases into the open ocean must be avoided, methanol poses significantly less environmental risk compared to substances like crude oil, bunker fuel, gasoline or diesel. Unlike those hydrocarbons, which do not mix with water and require double hulls for added spill protection, methanol's infinite miscibility with water allows it to dissolve rapidly in the event of a spill ([Methanol Institute, 2020](#)). A study conducted by ([Malcolm Pirnie Inc, Inc., 1999](#)) demonstrated that methanol spills dilute so quickly that dangerous concentrations are never reached. This is further supported by methanol's substantially higher lethal concentration thresholds for marine life, which is 240 times higher than diesel and 1900 times higher than gasoline, ensuring that methanol concentrations quickly drop to non-toxic levels, typically within less than one mile, even in the case of large-scale releases. As suggested in the literature, this unique property also enables the use of void spaces like the cofferdam of the double-hull tank for methanol storage. In the event of a tank breach, the methanol would simply dissolve into the surrounding water, minimizing environmental impact. These characteristics highlight methanol as a safer and more environmentally friendly alternative for marine applications ([Verhelst , et al., 2019](#)).

6.1.4 E-METHANOL FUEL PREPARATION

As depicted in Figure 6.2 of Section 6.1.3, before methanol combustion in the engine room, the stored fuel is transferred through double-walled pipes from the fuel tank to the fuel preparation room for processing. A fuel preparation room refers to any space housing equipment used for fuel preparation, such as fuel pumps, fuel valve trains, heat exchangers and filters. These rooms must be located outside engine rooms or other high fire-risk machinery spaces and meet stringent safety and operational standards. They must be gastight, watertight, and fire-protected, with mechanical extraction ventilation. Ventilation must retain at least 50% capacity if a fan fails, operate during fuel equipment use, and start 10 minutes before activating equipment. Fuel system pumps must be protected against running dry and equipped with relief valves to prevent pressure exceeding system

design limits, with valves discharging upstream of the pump suction. Submerged hydraulic pumps require double barriers to prevent fuel exposure, with provisions for leakage detection and drainage. Additional safety measures include under-pressure ventilation and vapor detectors to mitigate fire risks effectively (China Classification Society, 2017).

6.1.5 DUAL FUEL ENGINE TECHNOLOGIES

Historically, dual-fuel technology was employed to retrofit older diesel engines, allowing for the use of cheaper or more readily available fuels while also reducing particulate matter (PM) emissions. These early implementations focused on cost-effectiveness and emission reductions. However, in recent years, the role of dual-fuel combustion has expanded significantly, supporting the use of low carbon but less reactive fuels (as ammonia and methanol) and facilitating advanced combustion strategies such as premixing and reactivity stratification. By utilizing fuels with differing reactivity, dual-fuel engines can achieve a better fuel-air mix, reducing hotspots and emissions while maintaining high efficiency (Kassa & Hall, 2018).

Dual-fuel combustion is a versatile strategy used in both spark ignition (SI) and compression ignition (CI) engines to improve efficiency, reduce emissions and enable the use of alternative fuels. This approach involves injecting two different fuels into the engine under the "octane-on-demand" strategy. This approach optimizes fuel consumption, improves thermal efficiency, and maintains engine reliability. By adjusting the proportion of the fuels and the pilot fuel injection timing, the timing of combustion can be precisely controlled, enhancing engine performance and stability. Additionally, dual-fuel combustion helps mitigate high peak pressures typically associated with advanced combustion modes, making their implementation possible even under high-load conditions (Dierickx, et al., 2021), (Kassa & Hall, 2018).

Several engine manufacturers are steadily increasing their orders and deliveries of dual-fuel marine methanol engines, as shown in Figure 6.3. With companies such as MAN Energy Solutions achieving enormous progress in dual-fuel, methanol-capable marine engines copy industrial traits since 2016. Currently, MAN has 82 methanol dual-fuel two-stroke engines on order and aims to launch methanol retrofits for four-stroke engines as early as 2024. These engines require modifications to components such as injectors, cylinder heads and fuel systems, but do not require changes to the core engine design (Methanol Institute, 2023).

Anglo Belgian Corporation (ABC)	DZC dual-fuel engine portfolio, with 6 and 8 cylinder inline engines and 12 and 16 cylinder V-engines, covers a power range from 600 kW up to 10.4 MW.
Caterpillar	Cat® 3500E-series marine engines can be modified to run on methanol.
China State Shipbuilding Corporation (CSSC) Power Research Institute, Anqing CSSC Diesel Engine, and Hudong Heavy Machinery	Developed the 6M320DM methanol fuel engine, first ignited on August 28. The engine can be adapted to various ships of up to 20,000 GT.
Hyundai Heavy Industries - Engine & Machinery Division (HHI-EMD)	14 methanol dual-fuel, two-stroke engines delivered, and 17 more on order (as of Feb 2022).
MAN Energy Solutions	ME-LGIM two-stroke dual-fuel methanol engines have accumulated more than 145,000 hours of operation. Four-stroke methanol engines are currently being developed.
mtu Marine solutions (by Rolls-Royce)	Launching methanol engines based on the mtu Series 4000 from 2026, and fuel cells from 2028.
Nordhavn Power Solutions A/S	Offers 13 liter/6 cylinder and 16 liter/8 cylinder marine methanol engines, in partnership with ScandiNAOS.
Wärtsilä	W32 and W46 methanol engines already in the market draws from the experience accumulated since 2015 on the conversion of a Wärtsilä Z40 engine and its operation in the ropax vessel Stena Germanica. Additionally, two-stroke engine retrofits in collaboration with MSC.
WinGD and HSD Engine	Methanol fueled engines under development in a joint development program. It aims to launch the first engines by 2024.

Figure 6.3. Methanol engine manufacturers (Methanol Institute, 2023).

Methanol-diesel operation requires some critical design choices, particularly regarding the placement of methanol injectors, which significantly affects ease of installation and engine performance. Dual-fuel technology can be implemented in different ways depending on the injection position of the high-octane fuel (HOF) such as methanol. One approach, used by Wärtsilä and MAN, involves direct injection of the HOF into the cylinder, as shown in Figure 6.4. Alternatively, methanol can be injected indirectly in the intake port where it mixes with air before entering the engine, a method called Intake Port Injection (IPI) or methanol fumigation. The two most common approaches include the use of multi-point injection (MPI) and single-point injection (SPI) systems. In MPI, the injectors are installed near the intake valves while in contrast, SPI systems are simpler to install and less costly. However, they demand careful design to ensure proper methanol-air mixing, avoid condensation, and achieve even distribution to all cylinders (Dierickx, et al., 2021).

Figure 6.4. Schematic representation of direct and indirect injection systems.

The maximum substitution ratio, meaning the proportion of diesel fuel replaced by methanol, varies between 70% and 85% achieved with direct injection, depending on engine design factors such as compression ratio and turbocharging pressures, which influence end-gas temperatures. In terms of efficiency, dual-fuel operation presents mixed outcomes. At low engine loads, efficiency may slightly decrease due to incomplete combustion, as the premixed methanol-air mixture can approach flammability limits, leading to higher emissions of unburnt fuel. Conversely, at high loads, efficiency generally improves due to methanol's faster and cooler combustion. This combustion type is closer to the thermodynamically ideal isochoric process, with reduced heat losses and quicker energy release compared to the slower diffusion combustion of diesel fuel (Verhelst , et al., 2019).

Methanol fumigation generally reduces nitrogen oxide (NO_x) and particulate matter (PM) emissions. The cooling effect of methanol and its faster combustion contribute to lower NO_x emissions, but the NO₂-to-NO ratio can increase due to radical formation during methanol combustion. Soot emissions are significantly reduced, aided by methanol's high heat of vaporization which enhances diesel-air mixing and oxidation of soot precursors. However, particulate matter shows smaller particle sizes due to unburnt hydrocarbons (Verhelst , et al., 2019).

While simpler, the potential power limitations due to end-gas auto-ignition and impacts on engine oil life due to methanol blow-by into the crankcase are presenting challenges. Furthermore, dual-fuel operation increases carbon monoxide (CO) and hydrocarbon (HC) emissions, particularly at low loads, because lower combustion temperatures hinder full oxidation. Formaldehyde emissions also rise with higher methanol substitution and load, but diesel oxidation catalysts effectively mitigate this by over 90%. The emissions profile depends heavily on the engine's operating conditions, as methanol substitution is typically zero at idling and full load (Verhelst , et al., 2019).

Internal combustion engines come in two main types: two-stroke and four-stroke engines. While both aim to convert fuel into motion, they differ significantly in operation, efficiency and applications. A two-stroke engine, also known as a two-cycle engine, completes its power cycle in just two piston strokes (one up and one down) during a single crankshaft revolution. Its operation involves simultaneous or overlapping processes, consolidating actions to deliver power with every revolution. Four-stroke engines are more fuel-efficient and operate through four distinct stages, ensuring a clear

separation between each phase for improved balance and efficiency (BISON, 2024).

Two-stroke engines dominated the marine engine market, holding a 54.3% share in 2020, due to their higher power, efficiency with low-grade fuel, and lower maintenance costs. In contrast, four-stroke engines are quieter, faster and less expensive upfront, making them increasingly popular for applications like container ships and ferries. However, rising fuel costs and the adoption of scrubbers could shift preferences back toward two-stroke engines. Although dual-fuel engines have slightly higher maintenance costs, their ability to switch between fuel types offers significant economic and environmental advantages, making them an appealing choice for ship owners (Methanol Institute, 2023).

6.1.6 EXHAUST GAS CLEANING TECHNOLOGIES

Fuel combustion on ships emits harmful pollutants such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur oxides (SO_x), carbon dioxide (CO₂) and particulate matter (PM), which harm both human health and the environment, especially in coastal areas. NO_x emissions, mainly nitrogen monoxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), result from high-temperature combustion, with NO making up 90-95% of the total. NO_x contributes to respiratory issues, acid rain, smog and water eutrophication. SO_x, primarily sulfur dioxide (SO₂), is emitted by burning sulfur-containing fuels and poses respiratory risks, contributing to acid rain and ecosystem damage. Furthermore, NO_x, CO and VOCs react to form ozone (O₃), a key component of smog, which harms air quality and ecosystems. Particulate matter, mostly fine soot particles, exacerbates health issues like asthma and heart disease. Regulations limiting these pollutants have improved environmental quality and public health, including benefits for bird populations (Zhao, et al., 2021).

To address concerns over maritime SO_x emissions, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) has set specific sulfur content limits for marine fuels to reduce SO_x emissions from diesel engines on ships. These sulfur limits are stricter in SO_x Emission Control Areas (SECAs) than globally. According to IMO Regulation 2.9, SO_x and particulate matter (PM) emission controls apply to all fuel types and on-board combustion systems, including main and auxiliary engines, boilers and inert gas generators. Within Emission Control Areas (ECAs), regulations specifically target SO_x and PM emissions, while outside ECAs, SO_x is managed globally by controlling the sulfur percentage in marine fuels. IMO Regulations 14.1 and 14.4 indicate that fuel sulfur limits, expressed as %m/m, have been progressively tightened in recent years. As established in 2020, permitted fuel Sulphur content must not exceed 0.1% m/m in SECAs and 0.5% worldwide. To meet the IMO's fuel sulfur limits for both SECAs and global waters, ships can either use low-sulfur conventional fuels that comply with IMO standards or opt for alternative fuels with minimal or no sulfur content. Methanol is one such alternative, offering an effective low-sulfur option (Zannis, et al., 2022).

In addition to SO_x emissions, the IMO has also addressed concerns over maritime NO_x emissions by setting specific NO_x limits for marine engines operating both within and outside NO_x Emission Control Areas (NECAs). Regulation 13 of MARPOL Annex VI requires ships with diesel engines producing at least 130 kW to be surveyed and certified to meet NO_x limits, which vary according to the ship's construction date and engine speed. The strictest limits, known as Tier III, apply to ships built from 2016 onward when operating in designated ECAs such as the North American or US Caribbean zones. For Tier III compliance, NO_x limits are set at 3.4 g/kWh for engines with speeds below 130 RPM (rounds per minute), 9·RPM^{-0.2} g/kWh for speeds between 130 and 2000 RPM, and 1.96 g/kWh for engines at or above 2000 RPM (Methanol Institute, 2023), (Zannis, et al., 2022).

Methanol combustion does not produce SO_x or particulate matter emissions. The emissions of methanol-diesel dual fuel combustion are considered insignificant and stem from the 3-5% of diesel used as pilot fuel. Flue gas desulfurization technologies (SO_x scrubbing), are classified into dry, semi-dry and wet methods based on the use of liquids in the desulfurization process and the form of the desulfurization by-products. A comparison of these three technologies is provided in Table 13 while a more in-depth description is given below. Though highly effective at reducing sulfur emissions, scrubbers have uncertain impacts on NO_x and can also increase maintenance demands and fuel consumption by approximately 1-3% (Sarbanha, et al., 2023).

Table 13. Comparison of three types of desulfurization technologies (based on (Zhao, et al., 2021)).

DESULFURIZATION TECHNOLOGIES	DRY	SEMI-DRY	WET
Desulfurization efficiency	30 - 60%	~ 80%	> 90%
Floor space	Large	Smaller	Moderate
Investment costs	Acceptable	Acceptable	Costly
Anti-corrosion treatment	Not required	Not required	Needed
Wastewater treatment	Not required	Not required	Needed

In brief, marine dry desulfurization scrubbers use alkaline particulate adsorbents, like metal hydroxides (Fe₂O₃, MgO, ZnO, CaO, Ca(OH)₂), to react with SO_x in exhaust gases, forming stable sulfate compounds in fixed or fluidized beds. Calcium oxide (CaO), calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂ or slaked lime), and calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) are top candidates for SO_x removal because they are widely available and inexpensive. Operating at exhaust temperatures between 240 and 450 °C, dry scrubbers achieve up to 99% SO_x removal and 80% PM reduction. Dry scrubbers offer several benefits, including a simple process with low modification costs, high exhaust temperatures (no need for reheating), water conservation (no wastewater or sludge) and low energy consumption. On the other hand, semi-dry scrubbers use lime-gypsum desulfurization in a spray-drying process where slaked lime and water react with SO₂ in the flue gas, producing desulfurization residue as powdered waste. This method is fast, highly efficient (over 90%), and discharges no wastewater. However, it is prone to clogging and scaling, produces challenging by-products with the resulting residue consisting of calcium sulfate, calcium carbonate and unreacted calcium hydroxide, requiring significant storage space and large equipment (Zhao, et al., 2021), (Sarbanha, et al., 2023).

Wet Scrubbers, or wet desulfurization systems, remove SO_x by passing exhaust gases through a liquid medium that chemically reacts with SO_x in order to remove it. Wet scrubbers are categorized into three main types: open-loop systems, closed-loop systems and hybrid systems. Open-loop systems, directly utilize natural seawater as a scrubbing medium to neutralize acidic sulfur compounds and reduce PM via counter-flow heat exchangers. Seawater scrubbing is straightforward

and conserves freshwater but may be less effective in high-sulfur environments and can harm marine ecosystems and cause nutrient enrichment and algal blooms if untreated washwater is discharged. Moreover, wet scrubbers are about 50% lighter than dry scrubbers but consume up to 10 times more energy (Sarbanha, et al., 2023).

Closed-loop systems are ideal where seawater alkalinity is inadequate or high-efficiency scrubbing is required. These systems use a mixture of fresh water and an alkaline solution (typically NaOH) as the scrubbing medium. After treatment, the washwater is cleaned to separate sludge, which is stored onboard until it can be disposed of onshore. Sodium-alkali scrubbing with NaOH or Na_2CO_3 is efficient and avoids scaling, though it is costly and may pose corrosion risks (Zhao, et al., 2021). Hybrid systems combine open- and closed-loop capabilities, offering flexibility to operate in either mode based on water quality and location. These systems allow for zero discharge (or “zero bleed-off”) operations, limited by the capacity of onboard holding tanks. By 2018, hybrid scrubbers were used on 50% of commercial ships, with 40% using open-loop scrubbers. (Sarbanha, et al., 2023).

Regarding NO_x emissions from methanol combustion, they are much lower compared to those from Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO) or Marine Gas Oil (MGO). Methanol’s lower adiabatic flame temperature compared to conventional fuels also means engine cylinders can run at reduced peak temperatures, which helps limit NO_x formation. However, methanol alone still does not meet Tier III NO_x emission standards (Methanol Institute, 2023). NO_x emissions are more challenging to treat than SO_2 , and two main technologies are currently used to reduce NO_x levels in ship exhaust to meet the IMO's Tier III emission standard: Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) and Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR) (Zhao, et al., 2021).

Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) systems effectively reduce NO_x emissions by converting them into nitrogen gas (N_2), a major component of air, through the injection of a urea solution. Most of the urea used in the reaction, but small quantities of ammonia can be released in the exhaust, something called ammonia slip. SCR systems can be applied to any engine without requiring modifications. However, they require a minimum exhaust gas temperature of approximately 300°C to operate effectively, with an optimal temperature range between 300°C and 400°C. Temperatures beyond this range can damage the catalyst and/or impair performance. During startup or before the catalyst reaches its operating temperature, the SCR system remains inactive. SCR technology is well-established, offering a wide operating temperature range, high selectivity and the capability to achieve over 90% NO_x reduction. It is particularly effective in four-stroke diesel engines, which produce higher exhaust temperatures. Its application in two-stroke engines is more challenging due to their lower exhaust temperatures. To address this, some systems place the catalyst upstream the turbocharger to achieve the required temperature (Andersson & Salazar, 2015), (Zhao, et al., 2021).

Despite its effectiveness, SCR systems face certain challenges. The catalysts are susceptible to scaling, blockage, and poisoning from impurities such as SO_x , particulate matter (PM) and hydrocarbons (HC), which can accumulate and reduce efficiency. Furthermore, issues such as space limitations, elevated HC and CO emissions and the need for precise urea injection and uniform mixing pose additional hurdles, particularly for two-stroke marine engines. These factors must be addressed to optimize the use of SCR systems on ships (Andersson & Salazar, 2015), (Zhao, et al., 2021).

Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR) is an effective technology for reducing NO_x emissions, commonly used in large two-stroke marine diesel engines. The system works by recycling a portion of the exhaust gases back into the engine's combustion chamber. This lowers the peak combustion temperature, which in turn reduces the formation of NO_x . One key benefit of an EGR system is that

it is unaffected by fuel sulfur content or reaction temperature, unlike Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) which increases its versatility. However, the introduction of recycled exhaust gases into the combustion chamber reduces the oxygen concentration, leading to unstable combustion and incomplete fuel burning. This results in increased fuel consumption and higher emissions of carbon monoxide (CO) and particulate matter (PM). Additionally, the system can accelerate engine wear and increase maintenance requirements, which means it may need to be combined with other technologies to optimize performance and efficiency (Andersson & Salazar, 2015).

6.2 DUAL FUEL ENGINE AND FUEL CELL CONFIGURATION

Methanol is a versatile fuel that can power both two-stroke and four-stroke vessel engines while also serving as an energy source for fuel cells, enabling auxiliary power or propulsion at scales reaching megawatts. Fuel cells present several advantages over traditional engines. Their compact design and flexible configurations save space, while their high energy conversion efficiency and superior power density ensure optimal performance. Companies like Blue World Technologies, e1Marine, Advent Technologies and Freudenberg Fuel Cell are leading the development of methanol-based fuel cells for maritime applications. Pilot projects incorporating fuel cell systems with onboard methanol reformers are already being implemented in the United States, Europe and China, paving the way for more sustainable energy solutions in the maritime sector. The modular nature of these systems allows for scalability and redundancy, catering to diverse operational needs. Furthermore, the absence of moving parts reduces maintenance requirements and their operation produces no emissions of NO_x, SO_x or particulate matter, making them an environmentally friendly option (Methanol Institute, 2023).

The fuel cells are broadly classified based on electrolyte or fuel that they use, five types are identified as follows: Solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC), Proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC), Phosphoric acid fuel cell (PAFC), Molten carbonate fuel cell (MCFC) and Alkaline fuel cell (AFC). A fuel cell comprises two porous electrodes which are anode and cathode and one electrolyte (Li, et al., 2023). The key characteristics, operating conditions and efficiencies of various fuel cell technologies are summarized in Table 14.

Table 14. Comparative characteristics of different fuel cell technologies (Li, et al., 2023).

Fuel cell type	PEMFC	PAFC	AFC	SOFC	MCFC
Electrolyte	Perfluorosulfonic acid (PFSA)	Liquid phosphoric acid	Aqueous alkaline solution (KOH)	Solid oxide or ceramic	Molten carbonate salt
Charge carrier	H ⁺	H ⁺	OH ⁻	O ²⁻	CO ₃ ²⁻
Fuel	H ₂	H ₂	H ₂	H ₂ , CH ₄ , biogas	H ₂ , CO, CH ₄ , C ₃ H ₈
Operating temperature (°C)	50–80	150–210	Room temperature - 250	600–1000	600–700
Electrical efficiency (%)	40–70	45–50	Up to 70	45–60	40–60
Advantages	Low operating temperature, low noise, quick start-up, fast response, high power density	High tolerance to fuel impurities, suitable for CHP	Fast electrooxidation reaction, high efficiency	High CHP efficiency, long-term stability, fuel flexibility, low emissions, low cost	Fuel flexibility, suitable for CHP, high efficiency
Disadvantages	High catalysts cost, low tolerance to impurities, poor heat and water management	Expensive catalysts, long start-up time, sulfur sensitivity	Prone to CO ₂ poisoning, high cost for fuel purification	Longer start-up times, mechanical and chemical compatibility issues	Slow start up, high cell component degradation, high performance degradation
Applications	Transportation, distributed/stationary and portable power generation, backup power,	Stationary power generation, vehicles	Military, space shuttle	Stationary power generation, CHP system, auxiliary power	Large, stationary power plants

Fuel cell technologies predominantly use hydrogen to generate clean and efficient electricity, powering various applications. Methanol is an excellent hydrogen feedstock through a reforming process, due to its advantages over other alcohols and hydrocarbons. It remains liquid at standard atmospheric conditions, offering a higher volumetric energy density (5 to 7 times that of compressed hydrogen stored at -252°C) making it practical for storage and transport. Methanol can be converted to hydrogen at relatively low temperatures ($\sim 200^{\circ}\text{C}$) due to its lack of C-C bonds, which simplifies the steam reforming process. Its reformates are sulfur-free and the low-temperature operation minimizes CO formation. Methanol can also be reformed on-site at fueling stations to supply hydrogen for fuel cell vehicles or stationary power systems, supporting primary or backup energy needs. With a boiling point of 65°C and full miscibility in water, methanol vaporizes easily, further streamlining processing and feed preparation (Garcia, et al., 2021), (Klein, 2020).

Methanol can serve as a fuel for fuel cells in two ways: directly, in Direct Methanol Fuel Cells (DMFC), or indirectly, in an Indirect or Reforming Methanol Fuel Cell (IMFC or RMFC). The Direct and Reformed Methanol Fuel Cells, are using a Proton Exchange Membrane as their electrolyte, and despite that they are named after their fuel to distinguish them from conventional PEMFCs (Giddey, et al., 2012). Direct Methanol Fuel Cells (DMFCs) are a type of proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) that utilize a liquid methanol-water mixture as fuel, eliminating the need for methanol reforming and hydrogen storage. This simplifies fuel handling and makes DMFCs particularly suitable for portable power generation, offering benefits like compactness and rapid refueling. They are often explored as replacements for rechargeable batteries in portable devices. However, DMFCs face challenges that limit their efficiency and adoption. Their electrical efficiency is typically below 30%, largely due to methanol crossover through the membrane. Maintaining proper hydration on both the anode and cathode sides to minimize crossover adds complexity and restricts operating temperature, further lowering efficiency (Araya, et al., 2020).

On the other hand, Reformed Methanol Fuel Cell (RMFC) system is a type of fuel cell system that initially converts methanol into hydrogen using a methanol reformer. The resulting hydrogen-rich gas mixture is then supplied to the PEMFC (Araya, et al., 2020). A key benefit of the RMFC is that using hydrogen boosts fuel cell efficiency compared to direct methanol systems. Additionally, RMFCs allow for cold storage, as there is no direct contact with the membrane, though they require a more complex design and incur higher costs. The start-up time of an RMFC is influenced by factors such as reformer design, hydrogen concentration and operating temperature. Since hydrogen diffuses more quickly than methanol, it reaches the catalyst layer faster, enabling quicker start-up and more rapid oxidation and proton production at the anode (Romagnoli & Testa, 2023).

In the framework of the POSEIDON project, the indirect methanol fuel cell (IMFC) implementation onboard is under investigation. This approach necessitates the integration of a methanol reforming and hydrogen purification system to ensure a consistent supply of high-purity hydrogen for the PEMFC. The available technologies for these critical steps in the value chain, along with their technical specifications, comparative advantages and limitations, are examined in the following sections. The technical specifications of the other steps in the value chain, namely fuel storage, preparation, and propulsion systems, still stand as described in Section 6.1.

Figure 6.5. Value chain of dual fuel engine and fuel cell configuration for hotel load.

6.2.1 E-METHANOL REFORMING TECHNOLOGIES

Reforming is the catalytic process of converting hydrocarbons into a hydrogen-rich gas mixture using an oxidizing agent. Common methanol reforming processes include steam reforming of methanol (SRM), partial oxidation of methanol (POM), oxidative steam reforming of methanol (OSRM), also known as autothermal reforming of methanol (ATRM), and methanol decomposition (MD) (Araya, et al., 2020). As shown in Table 15 below, each technology demonstrates varying hydrogen and CO yields, with SRM producing the highest hydrogen concentrations, ranging from 70% to 80%.

Table 15. Operational characteristics of POM, SRM and OSRM (or ATRM) (Kappis, et al., 2021).

	POM	SRM	OSRM
S/C ratio	-	1.5–2.0	1.2–1.5
O ₂ /C ratio	>0.5	-	0.10–0.25
H ₂ produced (%)	41.0	75.0	55.0–60.0
CO produced (%)	0.1–2.0	<1.0	2.0
Remarks	1. Low amount of H ₂	1. High concentration of H ₂ 2. Most widely used	1. Ideally thermo-neutral 2. Fast response rates

Steam reforming of methanol (SRM), also called Methanol Steam Reforming (MSR), is a widely recognized process due to its higher hydrogen yield (70-80 vol%, typically around 75 vol%) and lower operating temperatures, which enhance economic efficiency, making it the most widely adopted

methanol reforming technique. SRM generates reformat gas with relatively low carbon monoxide content (1-2 %vol.). However, as the reforming temperature increases, unconverted methanol concentration decreases, but CO levels in the reformat gas rise (Li, et al., 2023).

There are four types of SRM processes: (1) thermo catalytic SRM, (2) photocatalytic SRM, (3) aqueous-phase reforming of methanol and (4) high-temperature SRM. Thermocatalytic steam reforming of methanol is a widely employed industrial process for hydrogen production. It is an endothermic process in which methanol and water vapor (steam) react at high temperatures (around 250-300°C) to produce a hydrogen-rich reformat gas. The SRM kinetic mechanism can be represented by equation (11) which is the algebraic sum of the Water-Gas Shift (WGS) reaction (12) and the Methanol Decomposition (MD) reaction (13). Various researchers have proposed various mechanisms to explain these reactions (Araya, et al., 2020), (Garcia, et al., 2021).

While CO negatively impacts fuel cell performance, high-temperature PEM fuel cells (HT-PEMFCs) can tolerate up to 3% CO with minimal performance loss, especially at elevated temperatures and lower current densities. In contrast, low-temperature PEMFCs require very low CO concentrations in the anode feed. To optimize fuel cell performance and longevity, minimizing CO content in the reformat gas is essential. Optimizing the reforming process involves balancing reforming temperature and flow rate to achieve an ideal reformat mixture. Effective catalysts for SRM must exhibit high activity and rapid kinetics at low temperatures, excellent CO suppression, and strong stability. Catalysts with smaller crystallite sizes and higher specific surface areas, such as copper-based catalysts, typically perform better in minimizing byproducts like CO and unconverted methanol (Araya, et al., 2020).

Copper-based catalysts, especially Cu/ZnO, are widely utilized in industrial applications for methanol steam reforming (SRM) because of their high activity and selectivity, with copper functioning as the main active ingredient. The reforming activity of Cu/ZnO catalysts begins at 160°C, making it well-suited for integration with HT-PEMFCs in series, which typically operate within a temperature range of 160-180°C. However, at approximately 200°C, up to 8% of methanol may remain unconverted in the reformat mixture, which can adversely affect the performance and lifespan of HT-PEMFCs. To produce a sufficiently clean reformat mixture (with less than 2 vol.% of methanol and less than 1 vol.% of CO) suitable for HT-PEMFCs without requiring additional cleanup processes, the steam methanol reformer must operate at temperatures above 230°C (Araya, et al., 2020), (Li, et al., 2023).

However, at temperatures above 300°C, catalyst deactivation is often caused by thermal sintering with optimal operating temperatures typically below 260°C. Other deactivation mechanisms include coke deposition due to iron or other transition metals, carbon formation due to silica-alumina interactions and catalyst poisoning from sulfur and chloride contaminants in the feed. To maintain the stability of Cu/ZnO-based catalysts, stabilizers like Al₂O₃ or other substitutes are often added (Araya, et al., 2020). Furthermore, to address active phase sintering, group VIII metal-based catalysts (Ni, Rh, Pd, and Pt) have been explored as alternatives, offering better thermal stability and similar selectivity to Cu-based catalysts. Palladium-based catalysts are thermally stable and less prone to sintering but tend to favor syngas production over hydrogen. When alloyed with Zn or supported by ZnO, Pd shows excellent activity and selectivity for SRM, driven by the formation of

Pd-Zn alloys. Other supports like ZrO_2 enhance dispersion and activity, while additions like Ru improve performance through alloying effects and better CO desorption (Garcia, et al., 2021).

Increasing the steam-to-carbon ratio in the methanol-water mixture reduces catalyst deactivation by preventing coke formation. While conventional packed-bed reformers use low-cost pelletized catalysts, they suffer from significant thermal gradients. Advances in microprocessing have enabled the development of micro-channel reactors with wall-coated catalysts, minimizing heat and mass transfer issues. Catalytic membrane reactors (CMRs) with palladium-based membranes further enhance efficiency by allowing methanol steam reforming on the tube side, while hydrogen permeates the membrane and is collected on the shell side, shifting the reaction equilibrium to improve methanol conversion (Araya, et al., 2020).

Regarding Partial oxidation of methanol (POM), methanol is an ideal feedstock due to the absence of carbon-carbon (C-C) bonds, which minimizes coke formation and catalyst deactivation. POM involves the partial reaction of methanol and air in a reactor to form hydrogen-rich syngas by maintaining O_2 below stoichiometric concentrations for complete combustion, thus preventing full oxidation. The overall reaction for POM is described by equation (14) (Garcia, et al., 2021).

The result of this process is a mix of gases that is mainly consists of of hydrogen and carbon monoxide, as well as nitrogen and trace elements. The operating temperature for POM is above $200^\circ C$ to achieve a high methanol conversion with up to 40% of hydrogen in the reformat gas. However, POM is inherently complex, involving intermediate reactions such as methanol steam reforming, methanol decomposition, WGS, methanol combustion, methanation and oxidative hydrogenation of methanol. (Garcia, et al., 2021). Due to its exothermic nature, POM does not require external energy input, unlike SRM. However, the heat generated can cause reactor temperature control challenges, including the formation of hot spots in the catalytic bed. These hot spots can deactivate the catalyst through sintering, emphasizing the need for reactors with efficient heat management (Kappis, et al., 2021).

Autothermal reforming of methanol (ATRM) integrates partial oxidation (POM) and steam reforming (SRM) of methanol, where methanol reacts with both air and steam to produce a hydrogen-rich reformat gas stream. ATRM uses the heat generated by exothermic POM to drive the endothermic SRM reaction, optimizing the mixture of air, steam and fuel. The reactions underlying ATRM are based on SRM (equation 11) and POM (equation 14), with reactant ratios calculated to maintain thermal neutrality. The overall ATRM reaction is equation (15) below. Here, r represents the oxygen-to-methanol ratio, determining the balance between the exothermic and endothermic reactions. ATRM is typically operated at a thermoneutral point, eliminating the need for external energy input and reducing system complexity and capital costs compared to SRM. Compared to POM, ATRM offers better heat recovery, higher hydrogen yields (55-60% H_2 concentration) and faster startup and shutdown cycles. However, compared to SRM, the achieved hydrogen yield and methanol conversion are slightly lower (Garcia, et al., 2021), (Kappis, et al., 2021).

Finally, methanol decomposition (MD) is an endothermic process in which methanol dissociates into hydrogen and carbon monoxide. While MD achieves complete conversion at relatively low temperatures (around 473 K), its reaction kinetics are slower compared to steam reforming and

partial oxidation (POM). The process can effectively utilize waste heat, making it suitable for in-situ applications such as internal combustion engine reformers, gas turbines, portable power systems and chemical processing. MD employs various catalysts, including Cu, Ni, group VIII metals, and Zn/Cr combinations, with different structures and preparation methods explored to optimize performance. The reaction mechanism, following equation (13) as shown above, involves methanol adsorption on metal surfaces, forming a methoxy intermediate that undergoes successive dehydrogenation to produce CO and H₂ (Garcia, et al., 2021).

Research highlights differences in reaction pathways and rate-limiting steps for MD compared to SRM and POM, with the latter two being kinetically faster. Despite its slower kinetics, MD's ability to achieve 100% methanol conversion and its adaptability for applications requiring low-pressure and waste heat utilization make it an attractive method for hydrogen production. Table 16 summarizes comparatively the main characteristics of steam reforming of methanol (SRM or MSR), POM, ATRM and MD in terms of conversion and hydrogen yields, CO selectivity, process, equipment and catalyst technologies (Garcia, et al., 2021).

Table 16. Process and equipment characteristics of SRM, POM and ATR (Garcia, et al., 2021).

Process	MSR	POM	ATRM	MD
Conversion and hydrogen yield	High conversion of methanol. Reforming from both fuel and water which results in higher yield.	Low conversion and requires higher temperatures.	Higher efficiency and hydrogen concentration than POM.	Conversion is completed at lower temperatures (400 K) but is kinetically slower than MSR and POM.
CO selectivity	Low temperature process. Low CO generation. Cu- and Pd- based catalyst compatibility.	High CO generation that can poison the downstream processes.	High CO concentration of syngas produced. Additional clean up before fuel cell application is recommended.	CO selectivity increases. Potential combustion. Not ideal for PEMFC due to catalyst poisoning.
Process and equipment technology	Well established process. Easy temperature control. Endothermic nature of the reaction. Requires a steam generation unit. Requires external input of heat to drive the reaction.	Fast start-up. More dynamic (higher reaction rate). No steam generation unit is required. Air or oxygen is used as the oxidant.	Better dynamic response than MSR. Greater flexibility to accommodate multiple fuels. Operates ideally at a thermos-neutral point. Neither consuming nor releasing external energy.	Endothermic nature requires an initial heat input. Adsorption step into catalyst surface occurs early. The rate-limiting step of desorption of CO occurs at a temperature above 400 K.
Catalyst technology	Cu- based catalysts are highly developed. Vast studies in promoters, supporters, preparation methods, and reaction mechanisms.	Catalysts able to cold start the POM process. Catalysts are stable.	Complex catalyst synthesis. Needs to be active for both SRM and POM.	Catalysts are well established. Cu- based catalysts are active for MD. -Cr and other promoters can be used.

6.2.2 HYDROGEN PURIFICATION SYSTEM

Efficient operation of a fuel cell power system hinges on the availability of high-quality H₂. Hydrogen produced through processes such as gasification methanol reforming, by-product hydrogen recovery, or water electrolysis is generally classified as crude hydrogen. The composition of crude hydrogen produced from methanol reforming typically consists of 75-80 %vol. H₂, 20-24 %vol. CO₂ and 0.5-2 %vol. CO (Du, et al., 2021), (Huang, et al., 2024). This crude hydrogen cannot be directly utilized in fuel cells without purification. The impurity content must be strictly controlled and determined by the structure and operational characteristics of PEMFCs used in the context of the POSEIDON project.

PEMFCs can be classified by their range of working temperature into Low Temperature (or LT-) PEMFCs and High Temperature (or HT-) PEMFCs. The LT-PEMFCs are operated around 60-80°C while the HT-PEMFC are operated above 120°C up to 200°C. In both fuel cells, platinum is used as

the catalyst to improve the electrochemical reactions (Rosli, et al., 2017). Even trace amounts of certain impurities, such as carbon monoxide (CO), can irreversibly damage fuel cell performance. CO binds more strongly than H₂ to the active sites of platinum (Pt) catalysts in fuel cells, significantly reducing the effective electrochemical surface area available for H₂ adsorption and oxidation. As little as 70 ppm of CO can decrease voltage by 85% in LT-PEMFCs. Due to their extremely low tolerance for fuel impurities, LT-PEMFCs require ultra-pure hydrogen (99.999%) with CO levels below 10 ppm or trace levels. Increasing the temperature or introducing oxidizing gases can effectively mitigate CO poisoning, making HT-PEMFCs more tolerant to CO concentrations of up to 3% vol (Huang, et al., 2024), (Rosli, et al., 2017).

Regarding carbon dioxide (CO₂), although less reactive, it also affects the performance of LT-PEMFCs due to anodic polarization of Pt electrodes, primarily resulting from two factors: (1) the physical dilution of the H₂-rich gas stream, which lowers the H₂ concentration, and (2) the generation of CO via the reverse water-gas shift (RWGS) reaction. These effects can poison the electrode and further compromise the fuel cell's longevity and performance. Studies indicate that low CO₂ concentrations have minimal effects on HT-PEMFC performance. However, at elevated temperatures (160-180°C) within HT-PEMFCs, high CO₂ concentrations (above 30% vol.) can promote the RWGS reaction, generating substantial amounts of CO and potentially causing complex poisoning effects (Huang, et al., 2024), (Du, et al., 2021).

There are various hydrogen purification methods that can primarily be categorized into physical and chemical techniques as shown in Figure 6.6. Among these, the most extensively used include cryogenic separation, adsorption methods (Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA), Temperature Swing Adsorption (TSA) and Vacuum Swing Adsorption (VSA)), selective membrane separation (using inorganic and organic membranes), metal hydride separation and catalytic methods. Further reduction of CO content can be achieved by CO removal processes such as the Water Gas Shift (WGS) reaction, CO preferential oxidation (CO-PROX) and CO selective methanation (CO-SMET) (Du, et al., 2021).

Figure 6.6. Classification of hydrogen purification technologies (Du, et al., 2021).

The selection of an appropriate hydrogen purification method depends largely on the hydrogen

supply mode and gas source. The schematic diagram of Figure 6.7, as proposed by (Achomo, et al., 2024), outlines a hydrogen purification process with three potential alternative paths for CO and CO₂ removal to achieve high purity hydrogen. As shown, CO cleanup is a critical step and can be implemented prior to or in combination with hydrogen separation technologies. The resulting H₂-rich gas stream can then be purified further using PSA, membrane separation or metal-hydride separation to meet the requirements for high-purity hydrogen applications. For methanol-based reformat, the water-gas shift (WGS) reaction is generally unnecessary due to its inherently low CO content.

Figure 6.7. Schematic of hydrogen purification process for CO and CO₂ removal (Achomo, et al., 2024).

Membrane separation is an efficient and environmentally friendly method for hydrogen purification, utilizing perm-selective membranes to separate gases based on differences in pressure, concentration and potential. The success of this technology largely depends on the membrane material used, which can include metal, polymer, carbon-based and metal-organic framework (MOF) membranes reaching hydrogen purity levels up to 99.9999% (Du, et al., 2021). Metal membranes, especially palladium (Pd), are known for their high hydrogen permeability and resistance to hydrogen fluidity. However, their high manufacturing costs and susceptibility to hydrogen embrittlement, particularly at low temperatures (<300°C) and pressures (<20 bar), are major drawbacks. To overcome these issues and mitigate embrittlement, Pd alloy membranes are created by adding metals such as Ag, Cu, Y, Au, or Ni. These alloys enlarge the Pd lattice and enhance hydrogen permeation rates (Sahebdehfar & Takht Ravanchi, 2023).

Polymer membranes, made from materials like polysulfone (PSF) and polyimide (PI), rely on differing permeation rates to separate gases. To improve performance, researchers incorporate inorganic materials like zeolites, forming mixed matrix membranes (MMMs) that enhance both permeability and selectivity. Carbon-based membranes, such as carbon molecular sieves (CMS) and graphene-based membranes, offer advantages in stability and permeability. The ultra-thin structure of graphene reduces resistance and performance improves with the addition of nanopores. MOF membranes, composed of metal ions and organic linkers, offer adjustable porosity and high hydrogen selectivity. Research into MOF membranes has shown promising results, with some maintaining stability under challenging conditions, making them suitable for hydrogen separation.

These emerging membrane technologies show promise in research but face significant hurdles for industrial-scale implementation (Du, et al., 2021). Table 17 presents the main properties of hydrogen separation membranes.

Table 17. Properties of hydrogen separation membranes (Sahebdehfar & Takht Ravanchi, 2023).

Features	Dense membrane			Porous membrane	
	Polymer	Metallic	Ceramic	Ceramic	Carbon
Operating temperature (°C)	< 100	300–600	600–900	200–500	500–900
Hydrogen selectivity	low	> 1000	> 1000	5–139	4–20
Drawbacks to stability	Compaction and swelling	Phase transition	Stability in carbon dioxide	Stability in water	Brittleness
Poisoning by	HCl, SO _x	H ₂ S, HCl, CO	H ₂ S	–	Strong adsorbing vapors

Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) is a widely used, non-cryogenic process for separating gases and purifying hydrogen. It achieves high purity levels, typically ranging from 99% to 99.999%. PSA employs porous adsorbent materials to selectively retain impurities under high-pressure conditions and releases them at lower pressures during regeneration. This cyclic process requires multiple adsorption columns to ensure continuous hydrogen production, with typical setups involving six or more units. PSA units rely on the affinity between gas molecules and adsorbents like silica, alumina, molecular sieves and activated carbon, which are layered to target specific impurities such as hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) and ammonia (Besancon, et al., 2009).

Pressure swing adsorption (PSA) is commonly employed for large-scale centralized production methods with an H₂ supply exceeding 10000 Nm³/h, due to its low operating costs and long service life. However, in small-scale distributed production scenarios (≤1000 Nm³/h), traditional PSA systems face challenges like large space requirements and limited flexibility. Furthermore, traditional PSA systems are less efficient for very high purity hydrogen production, as they struggle with high impurity removal precision (e.g. CO ≤ 0.2 ppm), leading to lower recovery rates and increased costs (Du, et al., 2021).

Cryogenic distillation can be used in large-scale production similarly to PSA but typically achieves an H₂ purity of only 85-99%, which does not meet fuel cell requirements. Alternative methods such as low-temperature adsorption and metal hydride separation are better suited for removing specific impurities. Low-temperature adsorption effectively removes multiple impurities like sulfides and formaldehydes but is energy-intensive and complex. Metal hydride and palladium membrane methods perform well with inert gas-rich sources but suffer from efficiency losses due to reactions with impurities (Du, et al., 2021).

Regarding CO-removal, for small-scale PEMFC applications, CO selective methanation and CO preferential oxidation (CO-PROX) are two promising hydrogen purification technologies that effectively remove CO from hydrogen-rich gas streams. These processes rely on catalytic reactions to selectively reduce CO concentration, crucial for protecting the fuel cell's Pt anode from poisoning. Even though the structure-activity relationship of various catalysts used in these processes has been extensively studied, with efforts focusing on optimizing catalyst stability, selectivity and efficiency, issues such as catalyst deactivation, side reactions and the need for high-performance catalysts under realistic conditions continue to be areas of active research (Wang, et al., 2023).

Preferential oxidation of CO (CO-PROX) is recognized as the most cost-effective and efficient method for hydrogen purification, using air as an oxidant to selectively convert CO to CO₂ in a

hydrogen-rich gas mixture. This exothermic reaction competes with hydrogen oxidation, reducing CO removal efficiency and consuming additional hydrogen. To minimize these effects, significant efforts have focused on developing catalysts that are highly active, stable and selective at low temperatures suitable for PEMFCs (80-200°C). The main categories of catalysts used for CO-PROX include noble metal catalysts such as Platinum (Pt), Palladium (Pd), Iridium (Ir), Ruthenium (Ru) or Rhodium (Rh) supported on various substrates, gold-based catalysts and base metal oxide catalysts derived from transition metal oxides, which are cost-effective alternatives to noble metals. An ideal CO-PROX catalyst operates efficiently under PEMFC conditions, avoiding side reactions like the reverse water-gas shift (RWGS), which becomes significant above 200°C. Performance is further optimized by tailoring support materials, adding promoters and enhancing interactions between metal and support, ensuring high selectivity and hydrogen efficiency in reformat streams containing water vapor and CO₂ (Wang, et al., 2023).

Selective methanation of CO (CO-SMET) uses a hydrogenation catalyst to convert CO and CO₂ into methane in the presence of H₂. The key reactions include CO methanation, CO₂ methanation and the reverse water-gas shift (RWGS) reaction. CO methanation is promising because it directly utilizes CO and H₂ without requiring additional reactants like air, as in CO-PROX. However, at higher temperatures, side reactions such as CO₂ methanation and RWGS consume more H₂ and increase CO output. The exothermic nature of these reactions can also lead to temperature control issues, requiring catalysts that are highly active at low temperatures and minimize side reactions at higher temperatures. Ru and Ni catalysts are effective for CO-SMET in H₂- and CO₂-rich gas streams, but challenges remain, such as low activity, selectivity and high CO outlet concentration. To address these, strategies like modifying the support material, optimizing metal-support interactions, adding promoters and adjusting metal particle size are needed to improve performance (Wang, et al., 2023). Table 18 summarizes the advantages and disadvantages of common CO clean-up methods. For effective on-board fuel processors in PEMFCs, research should focus on optimizing both catalysts and reactors (Sahebdehfar & Takht Ravanchi, 2023).

Table 18. Comparison of CO removal technologies for H₂ in mobile and residential applications (Sahebdehfar & Takht Ravanchi, 2023).

Process	Operating temperature (°C)	Operating pressure (bar)	Advantages	Limitations
Pressure swing adsorption (PSA)	Ambient	10–30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High H₂ purity • Mature technology • Low adsorbent costs • Possibility of adsorbent regeneration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High operating pressure • High energy consumption • Adsorbent degradation due to regeneration cycles • Low affinity of adsorbents to CO
Membrane separation (dense metals)	300–600	0.5–1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low energy consumption • Compact structures • Flexible and simple operation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large temperature and pressure gradients • High costs • Phase transition (e.g., embrittlement)
Selective CO methanation (CO-SMET)	240–280	Atmospheric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapid kinetic • Moderate temperature • Low operating pressure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H₂ consumption • CH₄ impurity (tolerable) in product
Preferential CO oxidation (CO-PROX)	80–170	Atmospheric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low operating temperature • High kinetic rates • Low operating pressure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrow operating window • Need for oxygen source • Strong exothermicity • Complex O₂ control instrumentation • Narrow operating temperature

The water-gas shift (WGS) reaction has been used to remove CO_x from syngas in hydrogen production, followed by CO₂ absorption and methanation in processes like ammonia synthesis. The reaction is moderately exothermic and equilibrium-limited, so it can only reduce CO to low levels (around 0.5-2% by volume) at high initial H₂/CO ratios and low temperatures. At low temperatures, the reaction becomes kinetic-controlled, limiting CO concentrations in the product. The WGS process is typically carried out in two steps: a high-temperature shift (HTS, 350-450°C) using Fe-Cr oxide catalysts for rapid reaction (resulting in 3-5% CO) and a low-temperature shift (LTS, 200-250°C) with Cu-ZnO/Al₂O₃ catalysts for maximum conversion (0.5-1% CO). With the growing demand for fuel cell applications in vehicles and residential systems, a single-step LTS is preferable to minimize fuel processor size. Catalysts for these applications must have quick start-up times, be non-pyrophoric, and be tolerant to oxidation and water condensation during shut-down. Noble metals such as Pt, Rh, Ru, Pd, Au, Re, Os, Ag, Cu, Ni, and Co on oxides are commonly used for WGS catalysis. Among them, Pt shows superior activity at medium temperatures (250-400°C), while Au performs better at lower temperatures (<250°C) (Sahebdehfar & Takht Ravanchi, 2023).

(Wang, et al., 2023) and (Sahebdehfar & Takht Ravanchi, 2023) proposed a hydrogen purification systems for PEMFCs applications which involves a sequential process where the water-gas shift (WGS) reaction is employed in series with CO-selective methanation (CO-SMET) or preferential oxidation (CO-PROX) in order to reduce CO concentrations in H₂-rich reformat gas stream to levels below 10 ppm. In the WGS stage, CO present in the reformat gas is partially converted into CO₂ and H₂, reducing the CO content to approximately 0.5–2 %vol. This intermediate stream is then subjected to a CO-removal process, where either CO-SMET or CO-PROX is applied to further lower the CO concentration to below 10 ppm. This purified hydrogen stream is suitable for direct use in PEMFCs, ensuring minimal poisoning of the fuel cell electrodes.

6.2.3 FUEL CELL TECHNOLOGIES

A fuel cell is an electrochemical device that converts the chemical energy of fuels like hydrogen, methanol or methane, along with an oxidant such as oxygen or air, into electrical energy. It includes two porous electrodes (anode and cathode) and an electrolyte. Using the principle of reverse electrolysis, at the anode of fuel cells the fuel is oxidized producing electrons and protons. The electrons then pass through an external circuit and generate electricity, while the protons travel through the electrolyte to the cathode, where they combine with the oxidant to produce water. Individual cells produce around 0.6-0.7 volts, and cells are arranged in series to produce the required voltage and power for applications. Fuel cells are used in transportation, portable electronics, stationary power generation, backup power, and even aerospace and marine systems (Romagnoli & Testa, 2023).

As depicted in Figure 6.8, the elementary cell, the core component of a PEM fuel cell stack used in the context of the POSEIDON project, comprises two bipolar plates (BPPs, anode and cathode), gas diffusion layers (GDLs) and a membrane electrode assembly (MEA). The MEA includes a polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM), which conducts ions and is sandwiched between two electrodes. These electrodes are constructed from a porous, electrically conductive carbon support (carbon fibers) with a catalyst layer (CL) enabling the adsorption of reactants and facilitating the electrochemical reactions (16)-(18) presented below. The GDLs, situated on either side of the MEA, distribute reactants evenly, and the entire structure is compressed between monopolar plates. These

plates have internal flow channels that deliver reactant gases to the electrodes. Hydrogen gas flows through the GDL to the anode catalyst layer, where it is oxidized in order to dissociate into protons and electrons. Protons cross the humidified electrolyte membrane, typically as hydronium ions (H_3O^+), while the electrons are conducted through an external circuit to the cathode. At the cathode, oxygen (often from air) reacts with the transported protons and electrons to produce water and heat, completing the fuel cell's operation (Besancon, et al., 2009), (Li, et al., 2023).

Figure 6.8. Schematic representation of a Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) (Li, et al., 2023).

The chemical reactions in a PEMFC are as follows:

The bipolar plates perform multiple functions, including distributing hydrogen to the anode and oxygen to the cathode, conducting electrical current between cells, dissipating heat, and preventing gas and coolant leaks. The GDLs ensure reactant transport, collect current, support the membrane electrode assembly (MEA), and manage water drainage. Catalyst layers, made primarily of platinum (Pt), facilitate electrochemical reactions. Efforts are ongoing to reduce Pt usage and explore cost-effective, non-precious metal catalysts without compromising performance. The PEM allows only protons to pass while blocking electrons, ensuring efficient operation. Humidified hydrogen is often used to enhance proton conductivity and prevent membrane dehydration (Qasem, 2024).

Fuel cells offer high efficiency - up to 60% in certain types - and minimal emissions, with water as the primary byproduct when using hydrogen. Even when fueled by methanol or natural gas, emissions are significantly lower than those from combustion engines. By reducing greenhouse gases and pollutants like NO_x , CO_2 and particulates, fuel cells help combat climate change and improve air quality. Additionally, they contribute to sustainability by integrating renewable energy sources, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and enabling circular economy practices. For instance,

they can convert biogas from landfills or wastewater into electricity, reducing waste while generating clean energy. Despite some technical and economic challenges, the adoption of fuel cell technology is expected to grow due to its environmental and efficiency benefits (Romagnoli & Testa, 2023).

PEMFCs can be categorized into Low Temperature PEMFCs (LT-PEMFCs) and High Temperature PEMFCs (HT-PEMFCs), each with distinct operating conditions and advantages as shown in Table 19 (Giddey, et al., 2012). LT-PEMFCs operate at temperatures below 100°C and rely on water for proton conduction, requiring highly humidified polymer membranes like polyperfluorosulfonic acid (PFSA). They are characterized by simple startup, reduced material constraints and slower degradation rates although they require high-purity hydrogen due to the susceptibility of Pt-based catalysts to impurities like CO. This limitation restricts fuel flexibility and complicates large-scale deployment (Li, et al., 2023). HT-PEMFCs, on the other hand, operate at temperatures ranging from 120°C to 200°C, utilizing phosphoric acid-doped polybenzimidazole (PBI) membranes. These membranes replace water as a proton carrier, improving both water and heat management, while maintaining conductivity and mechanical stability over a wide temperature range. HT-PEMFCs are less sensitive to impurities and gain a better CO tolerance: up to 1000 ppm at 130°C, 10,000 ppm at 150°C and 30,000 ppm at >160°C with no major drop in performance. This allows the direct use of hydrogen-rich reformat gases derived from hydrocarbons or alcohols like methanol, eliminating the need for extensive pre-purification (Kappis, et al., 2021).

Table 19. Main characteristics of LT-PEMFCs and HT-PEMFCs (Kappis, et al., 2021).

	LT-PEMFCs	HT-PEMFCs
Operating temperature (°C)	60–80	≥160
Fuel	High purity H ₂	Hydrogen-rich reformat
Tolerance in CO	<10 ppm	≤3.0%
Infrastructure	Hydrogen station → high cost	Existing petrol station
Fuel Cell system	Water and heat management is required	Complicated thermal management
Operation	Quick start-up and shutdown	Slow start-up and shutdown

The high operating temperatures of HT-PEMFCs improve CO tolerance, simplify system design and enhance efficiency. These attributes make them ideal for applications involving methanol reformat gas. Unlike LT-PEMFCs, which require pure hydrogen, HT-PEMFCs can utilize reformat gases directly, making them more versatile and cost-effective. HT-PEMFCs also benefit from improved heat utilization, simplified thermal management, and greater operational efficiency. Coupling HT-PEMFCs with methanol steam reforming technology creates Reformat Methanol Fuel Cells (RMFCs), which are particularly suited for sustainable energy systems and on-board applications. RMFCs leverage the advantages of liquid methanol including the easy transportation and storage, while maintaining high efficiency and reduced emissions. In summary, HT-PEMFCs represent a significant advancement over LT-PEMFCs, especially for applications involving hydrogen-rich reformat fuels like methanol. Their higher CO tolerance, fuel flexibility and simplified operation make them a promising technology for clean and sustainable energy production (Araya, et al., 2020).

6.2.3.1 INTEGRATED STEAM METHANOL REFORMING AND HIGH TEMPERATURE – PEMFC (SRM-HT-PEMFC) SYSTEMS

The integration of steam reforming of methanol (SRM) with high-temperature proton exchange membrane fuel cells (HT-PEMFCs) in traditional Reformed Methanol Fuel Cells (RMFCs) involves converting methanol into hydrogen through a reformer operating at 250-300°C. This hydrogen-rich

gas is then used in an HT-PEMFC stack functioning at 160-180°C to produce electricity. This temperature mismatch between the fuel cell and the reformer led to the development of the externally integrated SRM-HT-PEMFC system. In this configuration, the reformer and fuel cell operate as separate subsystems at distinct working temperatures, supplemented by auxiliary equipment. The SRM-HT-PEMFC system, as illustrated in Figure 6.9, primarily consists of an SRM reformer, a combustor, an evaporator and an HT-PEMFC stack. The efficiency of the system is heavily influenced by the operating temperatures of the stack and the reformer, as these determine the carbon monoxide (CO) molar ratio in the reformat gas. Maximum system efficiency of 35% was achieved with the stack operating at 180°C and the reformer at 240°C (Li, et al., 2023).

Figure 6.9. Schematic of externally integrated SRM-HT-PEMFC system (Li, et al., 2023).

While this external integration avoids specialized component designs or catalyst requirements for the fuel cell and the reformer, it has limitations. These include low system thermal efficiency and lengthy start-up times, as the heat from the electrochemical reactions in the fuel cell cannot be directly utilized to drive the methanol steam reforming reaction. Additionally, the independent operation of the reformer and fuel cell necessitates auxiliary components such as evaporators, heat exchangers and condensers, resulting in increased system complexity, energy consumption, and weight. Consequently, conventional RMFCs achieve overall energy efficiencies below 30%, with reforming converting only 40-50% of the energy and the fuel cell converting 50-60% (Avgouropoulos & Neophytides, 2012).

To overcome these challenges, researchers have focused on enhancing thermal integration between the HT-PEMFC and the SRM system. The waste heat generated by the HT-PEMFC - approximately 50% of the input chemical energy - can be utilized to supply the heat required for fuel vaporization and the SRM reaction, significantly improving overall system performance (Li, et al., 2023). Innovative designs, such as Internal Reforming Methanol High-Temperature PEM Fuel Cells (IRMFCs), address these challenges by integrating the methanol reformer directly into the fuel cell's anode compartment. As shown in Figure 6.10, this configuration incorporates methanol reforming and hydrogen oxidation into a single, bi-functional anode. One side of the plate facilitates the

methanol reforming reaction, while the other supports hydrogen oxidation. This integration eliminates heat loss between the two processes, allowing for better recovery of waste heat from the HT-PEMFC to drive the methanol reforming reaction, thereby improving energy efficiency. Additionally, the compact design eliminates the need for separate reformer units and auxiliary components such as heat exchangers, reducing system weight and volume (Avgouropoulos & Neophytides, 2012).

Figure 6.10. Schematic of Internal Reformed Methanol Fuel Cell configuration (Avgouropoulos & Neophytides, 2012).

The success of IRMFC technology depends on advancements in high-temperature polymer electrolyte membranes, such as the ADVENT TPS® MEA developed by Advent Technologies. These membranes operate effectively at 180-200°C, offering key benefits: improved CO tolerance at the anode (enabling the use of reformat gases with minimal purification), enhanced reaction rates that increase efficiency, and simplified heat and water management compared to traditional systems (Li, et al., 2023). Studies have shown that IRMFC systems equipped with high-temperature membranes and highly active reforming catalysts can operate stably for extended periods (over 72 hours) with nearly 100% methanol conversion. The development of dual-layer methanol reformers has further enhanced conversion rates and reduced CO content, increasing efficiency and minimizing catalyst poisoning (Kappis, et al., 2021).

However, IRMFCs face several operational challenges. A critical issue is the limited operating temperature range. While temperatures above 200°C improve methanol conversion, they also accelerate the degradation of HT-PEMFC components, compromising durability. Lower temperatures, on the other hand, result in incomplete methanol conversion and necessitate larger quantities of catalyst, increasing system complexity and cost. Another challenge is methanol slip and crossover, where unreacted methanol permeates through the membrane, poisoning the anode catalyst and reducing membrane performance. Additionally, catalyst migration from the reformer to the fuel cell membrane can cause phosphoric acid leaching, degrading the membrane and reducing system reliability. To mitigate these challenges, researchers have developed advanced catalysts

and materials. For instance, (Avgouropoulos & Neophytides, 2012) developed an Al-doped CuMnO_x catalyst that allowed methanol reforming at 200°C-210°C with a high methanol conversion rate. (Ribeirinha, et al., 2017) introduced an expansion vessel in the system to reduce flow rate fluctuations, significantly improving methanol conversion. Additionally, separation layers made of different materials are often used between the reformer catalyst and the fuel cell anode to protect both catalysts from poisoning by unreacted methanol and phosphoric acid leaching (Li, et al., 2023).

6.2.4 DUAL-FUEL ENGINE GENSET

As part of the end-use value chain, the POSEIDON project examines the utilization of a second dual-fuel engine within a generator set (genset). This genset is powered by a dual-fuel methanol-diesel engine, representing a shift toward more sustainable marine power solutions. Onboard generators, typically operating with diesel engines, supply electricity for the hotel load, which includes lighting, heating, cooling, navigation, communications, refrigeration and other essential services while at sea or in port. This is particularly critical for cruise vessels and ferries, as they often rely on generators due to their extended time spent at berth (up to 40%) and frequent ferry stops. As shown in Figure 6.11, the power demand of a ship depends significantly on its type and purpose, with large cruise ships exhibiting the highest power consumption (Sadiq, et al., 2017).

Figure 6.11. Power demand of different types of ships (Sadiq, et al., 2017).

A generic genset comprises a reciprocating internal combustion (RIC) engine that generates mechanical energy and an electrical generator (alternator) that converts this mechanical energy into electrical energy. Key components of marine gensets include the engine, alternator, cooling system, exhaust, fuel system, control panel, voltage regulator and safety systems. They come in various power outputs, from small units for boats to large systems for commercial ships. Built to endure harsh marine environments, these gensets have corrosion-resistant enclosures to protect against saltwater, humidity and vibration. Seawater-based cooling systems protect against overheating, allowing continuous operation. Compliance with international safety and environmental standards is mandatory. Proper installation and regular maintenance are essential for reliable performance, requiring trained personnel to prevent malfunctions (AGG, 2024).

A generator's core components include a stationary set of conductors wound into coils on an iron core (the stator) and a rotating magnet (the rotor). The rotor generates a magnetic field that cuts across the conductors, inducing electromagnetic force as it turns. This magnetic field is created through induction in brushless alternators or by energizing rotor windings with DC current via slip rings and brushes. Onboard ships, electricity is distributed efficiently across the vessel through a

dedicated power distribution system (Marine Insight , 2021). Recent advancements in power generation and distribution technologies have introduced eco-friendly alternatives to diesel generators, enhancing energy efficiency and reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and particulate pollutants. Key developments include electrification, digitalization, onshore power supply, and energy storage systems (Sadiq, et al., 2017).

7 CONCLUSION

The detailed state-of-the-art assessment conducted in this deliverable confirms that e-methanol has strong potential as a decarbonization pathway for maritime transport, but its success depends on technological advancements, economic viability, and infrastructure development. Methanol presents several advantages as a marine fuel, making it a viable alternative for ship operators looking to reduce emissions and transition toward sustainability. It is widely available and is expected to see a fivefold increase in production by 2050, with 80% of the supply being carbon-neutral e-methanol or bio-methanol. From an environmental perspective, methanol significantly reduces SO_x (99%), PM (95%), and NO_x (up to 80%) emissions compared to conventional fuels like HFO and MGO, with e-methanol and bio-methanol offering near-zero CO₂ emissions and no methane slip concerns. Additionally, methanol is easy to handle, as it remains liquid at ambient temperature and pressure, allowing it to be stored, transported, and bunkered using existing infrastructure with minimal modifications. Safety regulations for methanol are well-established, and it is biodegradable, meaning spills would have minimal impact on marine ecosystems, unlike traditional fossil fuels. In terms of cost-effectiveness, methanol is considered one of the most affordable low-carbon marine fuels on a total cost of ownership basis, though policy support, such as carbon pricing, will be necessary to ensure its widespread adoption in the shipping industry.

Across the four key steps of the e-methanol value chain, various challenges, opportunities, and innovation needs were identified:

- **Feedstock Supply:** The production of green hydrogen and carbon capture from industrial or biogenic sources are critical for e-methanol synthesis. As analyzed, hydrogen can be produced through water electrolysis (Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM), Alkaline Water Electrolysis (AWE), Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOE), and Anion Exchange Membrane (AEM)) with each method maintaining trade-offs in efficiency, scalability, and economic feasibility, with PEM and AWE being the most commercially established options. Water and electricity supply also contribute to the overall technical complexity and economic footprint of hydrogen. Hydrogen storage also plays a crucial role, with options including compression, liquefaction, and chemical storage using liquid organic carriers. On the other hand, CO₂ can be sourced from industrial emissions, transportation, residential activities, and farming, carrying significant impacts on both the environment and the economy. As a valuable resource, it can be captured through the implementation of solvent-based (physical and chemical absorption), membrane-based, adsorption (Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA), Temperature Swing Adsorption (TSA)), cryogenic distillation, chemical looping, or hybrid carbon capture systems, with the first being the most widely adopted method. Once captured, CO₂ must be purified and stored through compression (gas or cryogenic), liquefaction, or chemical conversion, depending on its intended use.
- **E-methanol Synthesis:** The production of e-methanol relies on the conversion of hydrogen and CO₂ through catalytic processes. Two primary routes include direct CO₂ hydrogenation and

indirect methods such as Reverse Water Gas Shift (RWGS) followed by CO and CO₂ hydrogenation. The choice of synthesis pathway depends on energy efficiency, process complexity, and integration with existing industrial processes, with direct synthesis having lower energy consumption, although it is kinetically limited with low conversion rates. As a strong competitor to conventional e-methanol synthesis processes, the patented ICODOS process was also described comprehensively. After synthesis, methanol/water separation technologies such as multi-column distillation are required to purify the final methanol product to reach high purity levels. Wastewater generated from these processes must also be treated through primary, secondary, and advanced treatment methods before disposal or reuse.

- **E-methanol Transportation, Storage, and Distribution:** E-methanol must be efficiently stored, transported, and delivered to ships. Storage solutions include tank farms and portable containers (totes, drums), while transportation can be done via trucks, trains, or pipelines. At ports, bunkering technologies include truck-to-ship, ship-to-ship, and pipeline-to-ship transfer methods, each requiring specific infrastructure developments. Additional logistics considerations include port storage capacity, safety measures, and handling procedures to ensure smooth integration into the existing maritime fuel supply.
- **E-methanol End Use in Ships and Onboard Operations:** Ships can utilize e-methanol through various propulsion and energy conversion technologies. Dual-fuel combustion is a versatile strategy used in compression ignition (CI) engines to improve efficiency, reduce emissions, and enable the use of alternative fuels by injecting two different fuels into the engine simultaneously, offering significant flexibility under the "octane-on-demand" strategy, allowing vessels to transition from conventional fuels to e-methanol. Alternatively, methanol reforming technologies (Steam Reforming of Methanol (SRM), Partial Oxidation of Methanol (POM), Oxidative Steam Reforming (OSRM), and Methanol Decomposition (MD)) enable the production of hydrogen onboard, which can then be used in fuel cell systems such as low-temperature and high-temperature Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (LT-PEMFC, HT-PEMFC). Onboard fuel storage and preparation involve double-hulled storage tanks, fuel pumping systems, and purification steps. Additionally, exhaust gas cleaning technologies, such as dry, semi-dry, and wet SO_x scrubbing, as well as NO_x removal through Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) and Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR), further reduce emissions.

This comprehensive evaluation demonstrates that while many of the required technologies exist, they vary significantly in terms of maturity, efficiency, and commercial viability. Overall, this deliverable provides a solid technical foundation for future research and investment in e-methanol as a maritime fuel. Hydrogen production and CO₂ capture remain key challenges, requiring cost reductions and efficiency improvements. E-methanol synthesis is technologically feasible but needs further optimization to enhance conversion rates and reduce energy demand. Transport, storage, and bunkering infrastructures must be expanded and standardized to facilitate e-methanol adoption, and onboard utilization technologies require further testing, adaptation, and regulatory alignment. Addressing the identified challenges through technological advancements, policy support, and industry collaboration will be crucial for enabling the scaling and widespread adoption of e-methanol in the shipping sector.

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